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**The spider genera *Misumena*, *Misumenops*, *Runcinia*
and *Thomisus* (Araneae: Thomisidae)
of southern Africa**

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ABSTRACT	1
UITTREKSEL	1
INTRODUCTION	1
MATERIALS AND METHODS	2
Study area.....	2
Material studied	2
Techniques	2
Terminology	3
TAXONOMY	7
FAMILY THOMISIDAE	7
Key to the subfamilies of the Thomisidae	7
SUBFAMILY MISUMENINAE.....	7
MISUMENA-GROUP OF GENERA.....	8
Key to the genera of the <i>Misumena</i> -group of southern Africa.....	8
<i>THOMISUS</i> Walckenaer	8
Key to the species of <i>Thomisus</i> from southern Africa	11
<i>Thomisus spiculosus</i> Pocock	11
<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch	13
<i>Thomisus granulatus</i> Karsch	15
<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon).....	17
<i>Thomisus natalensis</i> Lawrence	19
<i>Thomisus zuluanus</i> Lawrence	20
<i>Thomisus schultzei</i> Simon	21
<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon.....	22
<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon	25
<i>Thomisus kalaharinus</i> Lawrence.....	27
<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock.....	28
<i>Thomisus australis</i> Comellini	30
<i>Thomisus dalmasi</i> De Lessert	33
<i>Thomisus congoensis</i> Comellini.....	35
<i>Thomisus machadoi</i> Comellini	36
Species incertae sedis	36
<i>Thomisus hottentotus</i> Strand.....	36
<i>Thomisus lenzi</i> Strand.....	36
RUNCINIA Simon.....	36
Key to the species of <i>Runcinia</i> from southern Africa	38
<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon)	39
<i>Runcinia johnstoni</i> De Lessert	40
<i>Runcinia carae</i> spec. nov.....	41
<i>Runcinia erythrina</i> Jézéquel.....	43
<i>Runcinia depressa</i> Simon	43
<i>Runcinia tropica</i> Simon	44
<i>Runcinia affinis</i> Simon	45
<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon)	46

	Page
<i>Runcinia lateralis</i> (Koch)	48
MISUMENOPS F. Pickard-Cambridge	48
<i>Misumenops rubrodecorate</i> Millot.....	51
MISUMENA Latreille.....	53
<i>Misumena tuckeri</i> De Lessert.....	55
Species incertae sedis	56
<i>Misumena natalensis</i> Lawrence	56
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	56
REFERENCES	57
APPENDIX 1	61
APPENDIX 2	64
APPENDIX 3	65
APPENDIX 4	65
INDEX	66

ABSTRACT

The southern Africa species of the genera *Misumena*, *Misumenops* and *Thomisus* are revised. A diagnosis and new distribution records are provided for the genus *Runcinia* in addition to the description of a new species. These genera belong to the *Misumena*-group of genera of the subfamily Misumeninae. Keys are provided to the subfamilies, genera and species. Biological and distributional data for all species are given. Twenty-five species are recognized, one new species is described and 13 species and eight sub-species are synonymized. Five species were recorded from this region for the first time.

New species: *Runcinia carae*. New synonyms: *Thomisus dottrensi* Comellini, 1957 = *T. spiculosus* Pocock, 1901; *T. anthobius* Pocock, 1885, *T. alboirroratus* Simon, 1907, *T. sus* Strand, 1907, *T. malevolus delesserti* Di Caporiacco, 1941, *T. malevolus ocellitibiis* Di Caporiacco, 1949 = *T. blandus* Karsch, 1880; *T. lawrencei* Roewer, 1951 = *T. granulatus* Karsch, 1880; *T. linderi* Roewer, 1956 = *T. scrupus* (Simon, 1886); *T. spinifer decorata* Millot, 1941, *T. spinifer maculitibiis* Di Caporiacco, 1947, *T. spinifer obscurus* Di Caporiacco, 1941, *T. spinifer simoni* Di Caporiacco, 1941 = *T. citrinellus* Simon, 1875; *T. lesnei* De Lessert, 1936, *T. sepius* Lawrence, 1942 = *T. daradioides* Simon, 1890; *T. urbensis* Lawrence, 1942 = *T. kalaharinus* Lawrence, 1936; *T. weberi* De Lessert, 1923 = *T. stenningi* Pocock, 1900; *T. drakensbergensis* Comellini, 1959, *T. mossambicus* Comellini, 1957, *T. mossambicus weidneri* Comellini, 1957 = *T. australis* Comellini, 1957; *T. anthobioides* Lawrence, 1942, *T. anthobioides mongbwalensis* Comellini, 1957 = *T. dalmasi* De Lessert, 1919. Species incertae sedis: *T. hottentotus* Strand, 1907; *T. lenzi* Strand, 1907; *Misumena natalensis* Lawrence, 1947.

Uittreksel

DIE SPINNEKOPGENERA MISUMENA, MISUMENOPS, RUNCINIA EN THOMISUS (ARANEAE: THOMISIDAE) VAN SUIDELIKE AFRIKA

Die Suid-Afrikaanse spesies van die genera *Misumena*, *Misumenops* en *Thomisus* is hersien. Vir die genus *Runcinia* word daar diagnostiese kenmerke en nuwe verspreidingsrekords verskaf en 'n nuwe spesie word beskryf. Hierdie genera behoort tot die *Misumena*-groep van genera van die subfamilie Misumeninae. Sleutels is voorsien vir die subfamilies, genera en spesies. Biologiese en verspreidingsdata word vir elke spesie gegee. Vyf-en-twintig spesies word herken, een nuwe spesie is beskryf en 13 spesies en agt sub-spesies is as sinonieme aangewys. Vyf van die spesies wat bestudeer is, is nuwe rekords vir hierdie area.

Nuwe spesie: *Runcinia carae*. Nuwe sinonieme: *Thomisus dottrensi* Comellini, 1957 = *T. spiculosus* Pocock, 1901; *T. anthobius* Pocock, 1885, *T. alboirroratus* Simon, 1907, *T. sus* Strand, 1907, *T. malevolus delesserti* Di Caporiacco, 1941, *T. malevolus ocellitibiis* Di Caporiacco, 1949 = *T. blandus* Karsch, 1880; *T. lawrencei* Roewer, 1951 = *T. granulatus* Karsch, 1880; *T. linderi* Roewer, 1956 = *T. scrupus* (Simon, 1886); *T. spinifer decorata* Millot, 1941, *T. spinifer maculitibiis* Di Caporiacco, 1947, *T. spinifer obscurus* Di Caporiacco, 1941, *T. spinifer simoni* Di Caporiacco, 1941 = *T. citrinellus* Simon, 1875; *T. lesnei* De Lessert, 1936, *T. sepius* Lawrence, 1942 = *T. daradioides* Simon, 1890; *T. urbensis* Lawrence, 1942 = *T. kalaharinus* Lawrence, 1936; *T. weberi* De Lessert, 1923 = *T. stenningi* Pocock, 1900; *T. drakensbergensis* Comellini, 1959, *T. mossambicus* Comellini, 1957, *T. mossambicus weidneri* Comellini, 1957 = *T. australis* Comellini, 1957; *T. anthobioides* Lawrence, 1942, *T. anthobioides mongbwalensis* Comellini, 1957 = *T. dalmasi* De Lessert, 1919. Spesies incertae sedis: *T. hottentotus* Strand, 1907; *T. lenzi* Strand, 1907; *Misumena natalensis* Lawrence, 1947.

INTRODUCTION

During the last two decades a considerable number of economically important insect and mite pests have become resistant to various pesticides. This has stimulated research world-wide on the use of predators and parasites in the biological control of pests. In this research the importance of spiders as natural enemies of agricultural pests has generally been overlooked. Recently, however, laboratory and field studies have indicated that a wide variety of insect and mite pests are taken by spiders. Spiders (mygalomorphs excluded) normally live from one to two years. They are ubiquitous and occur in high densities during most of the year. Because of their abundance on plants throughout the year, their wide food range and their dispersal by air currents, the latter characteristic which enables them to spread rapidly, spiders are increasingly being considered as playing an important role in pest control (Menhnick, 1967; Bailey & Chada, 1968; Wheeler, 1973; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1976).

Taxonomic and ecological research on spiders in South Africa has lagged behind that of other groups of arthropods, and only two ecological stu-

dies have been undertaken (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1976; Dippenaar-Schoeman, Genis, Van Ark & Viljoen, 1978). Present knowledge of the taxonomy of South African spiders is fragmentary and unsatisfactory, and this alone may tend to discourage ecological investigations. The taxonomy of South African spiders therefore requires attention if students and researchers are to be encouraged to evaluate spiders as possible agents for the biocontrol of agricultural pests.

The Thomisidae is a moderately large family of about 150 genera and 1 450 species. It has a world-wide distribution and the greatest species diversity is found in the tropical, subtropical and temperate zones. Although the family has been the subject of some studies in the past, the majority of genera still lack even preliminary revision. Most revisions of the family considered mainly the species of Central and North America.

Sixty-one of the 150 thomisid genera are known from the Afrotropical region (= Ethiopian region, see Crosskey & White, 1977) and thirty-one from southern Africa; a very rich fauna compared

with the nine genera known from North America. The true number for the southern Africa fauna is probably greater, for the spider fauna of this region is still poorly known.

The largest and most significant contribution to the taxonomy of the Thomisidae was made by the renowned French arachnologist, E. Simon. Between 1895 and 1903 he published a world revision of the thomisids as part of his revision of the Araneae. He collected and described numerous species from the Afrotropical region. Most of the species described by him are recognized today, and his work forms the basis of thomisid taxonomy in Africa. Another author who made an important contribution was Pocock (1898-1903). He described numerous species from Central, East and southern Africa. Strand (1907a-c) described some thomisids from North and South Africa and De Lessert (1915-1943) published on collections from Zaïre, Uganda, Morocco and South Africa, while Di Caporiacco (1939-1949) described thomisids from North and East Africa and Millot (1941) from East Africa. Comellini (1955-1959) published the only two revisions of thomisid genera *Tmarus* and *Thomisus* of Africa. Jézéquel (1964 and 1965) studied the thomisid fauna of the Ivory Coast. The largest and most valuable contribution to the systematics of the thomisids of southern Africa was made by the renowned South African arachnologist, R.F. Lawrence. From 1927 to 1947, he published several papers which dealt with, among other families, the thomisids of the area.

This paper, which forms part of a proposed series on the Thomisidae of southern Africa, revises the species of the genera *Misumena* Latreille, *Misumenops* F. Pickard-Cambridge and *Thomisus* Walckenaer of the *Misumena*-group of genera of the subfamily Misumeninae. The only other genus from southern Africa which belongs to the Misumena-group, *Runcinia* Simon, has been revised (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980). Species of *Runcinia* are included in this paper but only the most diagnostic characters, new information and locality records are provided.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

The area covered by the present study is southern Africa south of 15° S. latitude. This area includes the following countries: Republic of South Africa, Lesotho, Swaziland, South West Africa/Namibia, Botswana, Moçambique, Zimbabwe and Zambia (Fig. 37). Reference is also made to the distribution of the species in the remainder of the Afrotropical region and North Africa, which for this purpose is divided into the Central, East, West and North Africa.

During the course of the present study various South African homelands gained independence but, for the sake of convenience, they have been considered to fall within the territory of the Republic of South Africa.

Most of the species studied are endemic to Africa and have a pan-African distribution, probably a

result of aerial translocation of the spiders by wind. They are often collected in areas that differ greatly in vegetation, climate and topography. Locality coordinates are given only for type-localities of species and their synonyms. Distribution records were compiled from the literature while the new records refer to the material studied.

MATERIAL STUDIED

A total of 1 100 specimens were examined, and included material in the following museums and institutions.

- A.M. - Albany Museum, Grahamstown, South Africa.
- B.M. - British Museum (Natural History), London, England.
- H.E.C. - Hope Entomological Collection, University Museum, Oxford, England.
- M.N.B. - Museum für Naturkunde der Humboldt-Universität, Berlin, East Germany.
- M.N.H.G. - Museum d'Histoire naturelle, Geneva, Switzerland.
- M.N.H.P. - Museum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, France.
- M.R.A.C. - Musée royal de l'Afrique Centrale, Tervuren, Belgium.
- N.C.A. - National Collection of Arachnida, Pretoria, South Africa.
- N.M. - Natal Museum, Pietermaritzburg, South Africa.
- N.M.B. - National Museum, Bulawayo, Zimbabwe.
- S.A.M. - South African Museum, Cape Town, South Africa.
- Swe. Exp. - Swedish Expedition, material temporarily housed in the Albany Museum, Grahamstown.
- T.M. - Transvaal Museum, Pretoria, South Africa.
- Z.M.H. - Universität Hamburg, Zoologisches Institut und Zoologisches Museum, Hamburg, West Germany.

TECHNIQUES

Specimens were examined in a shallow glass vessel containing 70 % ethyl alcohol. They were manipulated with forceps and needles and held in the required position by glass chromatography beads or soft paper. Most of the drawings were made with a soft pencil on fleetpaste board using the method of Kraus (1968).

Both the external epigynum and internal spermathecae were studied and drawn. The dissected epigynum was later placed in a microvial and stored with the specimen.

The left palp of males was amputated between the femur and patella. It was then cleared in lactic acid and mounted on a cavity slide. The ventral and the retrolateral sides of the palp were studied and drawn. The amputated palp was then stored in a microvial together with the specimen.

Where numerous specimens were available for a given species, the genitalia were removed for more detailed observations. The epigynum of females was removed and freed of most of the muscle tissue with a sharp tungsten needle (see Levi, 1965). It was cleared in lactic acid and mounted on a cavity slide with Heinze's modified PVA mounting medium (see Meyer & Rodrigues, 1966).

Where enough material was available, ten individuals of both sexes of each species were measured. Lack of material often resulted in smaller samples. Specimens were selected from various parts of the range to make the sample as representative as possible. An ocular micrometer in a stereo-dissecting microscope (Wild M8) was used for the measurements. All the measurements are given in millimetres with the observed range in parentheses.

The following measurements were taken and indices calculated for the species studied (abbreviations are given in parentheses): total length (TL), carapace length (CL), carapace width (CW) and carapace index (CI). The latter is derived by dividing the length of the carapace by its width (Fig. 1a).

TERMINOLOGY

The terminology used is explained in Fig. 1-3.

Male genitalia. The tibiae of the Misumeninae are usually broader than long and armed with apophyses which vary in shape and are distinctive for the species (Fig. 2d and e). The retrolateral tibial apophysis (RTA) is situated on the more retrolateral

and dorsal side; the ventral tibial apophysis (VTA) is located more ventrally; in some species a third intermediate tibial apophysis (ITA) is present but it is seldom an independent structure, being fused with either the VTA or RTA. The tarsus is modified and enlarged into a spoon-shaped cymbium containing the genital bulb which is housed in a depression or concavity, called the alveolus. The genital bulb is characterized by the absence of a conductor for the embolus. In most of the thomisid genera a modification of the edge of the cymbium, the tutaculum is found (Comstock, 1971), which serves to protect the tip of the embolus. It consists of a protective shallow, membraneous, tutacular groove along the distal and retrolateral margin of the alveolus. When not extended in copulation the apical portion of the embolus lies in the tutacular groove. In some species a tutacular apophysis is present. This is a retrolateral structure which is formed ventrally as a smooth and setaless, sclerotized outgrowth of the alveolus and dorsally as a setaceous extension of the dorsum of the cymbium. The alveolus is a depression which is situated ventrally and contains the basal and middle division of the genital bulb. The genital bulb is a structure which functions as a sperm storage organ. It expands during copulation for sperm induction. The genital bulb consists of a tegulum and an embolus. The tegulum is a subround plate which covers most of the genital bulb. On the retrolateral side a crescent-shaped reservoir is visible through the tegulum. The embolus is divided into a basal part which is a broad, generally paler coloured structure and an apical tip, which may be long, curved or almost straight and which is usually strongly sclerotized and often black.

Female genitalia. In the Misumeninae the epigynum is usually provided with a well-defined margin

FIG. 1a-b External morphology of body/Uitwendige morfologie van liggaam. (a). Dorsal view/Dorsale aansig. (b). Ventral view/Ventrale aansig

or rim which is commonly oval or elliptical in shape (Fig. 2b). This rim surrounds a shallow to deep depression, also known as a guide pocket or atrium. It may be divided by a median septum. In some species the anterior part of the rim is covered by a sclerotized plate which is hood-like in appearance and overlies the central depression. The main female internal organs of the Misumeninae include the following (Fig. 2c): bilaterally paired copulatory tubes or bursae copulatrix which connect the intromittent (spermathecal) orifices and the spermathecae. The spermathecae are also bilaterally paired and strongly sclerotized structures which are usually visible through the integument. Spermathecal organs are small rounded lobes on the anterior side of the spermathecae and are sometimes visible dorsally. The spermathecal apophyses are small, strongly sclerotized structures located on the posterior side of the spermathecae and are usually visible as small dark structures through the integument. The spermathecal organs are small rounded lobes on the anterior side of the spermathecae and are sometimes visible dorsally. The spermathecal apophyses are small, strongly sclerotized structures located on the poste-

rior side of the spermathecae and are visible as small dark structures through the integument. The fertilizing tubes originate on the spermathecal apophyses and connect the spermathecae with the vagina.

Eyes. Eight in number, simple ocelli, arranged in two transverse rows of four each and notated in pairs as follows (abbreviations in parentheses) (Fig. 2a): anterior median eyes (AME); anterior lateral eyes (ALE); posterior lateral eyes (PLE). The area enclosed by the AME and PME is termed the median ocular quadrangle (MOQ). The terms procurved and recurved are extensively used and can be explained as follows (Fig. 2a). When the lateral eyes, as viewed from above, are situated more to the front of the median eyes, the line drawn through the eyes is said to be procurved and when the lateral eyes are situated further back than the median eyes, the line drawn through the eyes is said to be recurved. The size and arrangement of the eyes are frequently used on familial, generic and specific levels.

Carapace chaetotaxy. Formerly the chaetotaxy of spiders was mostly ignored in taxonomic descrip-

FIG. 2a-d External and internal morphology/Uitwendige en inwendige morfologie. (a). Eyes, dorsal view/Oë, dorsale aansig. (b). Epigynum of female, ventral view/Epigynium van wyfie, ventrale aansig. (c). Internal genitalia of female, dorsal view/Inwendige genitalieë van wyfie, dorsale aansig. (d). Palp of male, ventral view/Palp van mannetjie, ventrale aansig

FIG. 2e-f (e). Palp of male, retrolateral view/*Palp van mannetjie, retrolaterale aansig.* (f). Chaetotaxy of carapace/*Chaetotaksi van karapaks*

tions. Schick (1965) studied the chaetotaxy of the thomisids and he recognized two types, namely primary and secondary setae. The primary setae are usually constant in position and number throughout the group, while the secondary setae are more variable. He described 30 primary bilateral pairs of setae which he indicated by capital letters (C, P, S, T, A). These letters indicate the area where the setae occur while numeric subscripts refer to a particular pair or pairs of setae (Fig. 2f). Schick (1965) divided the cephalic area into prodiscus (P), mesodiscus (S) and metadiscus (T) and refers to the thoracic area as the allatum (A). In most of the thomisids the following pairs of primary setae are present: clypeus (8), C₁₋₈; proöiscus (ocular area) (4), P₁₋₄; mesodiscus (area posterior of eyes) (7), S₁₋₇; metadiscus (part of thoracic area) (5), T₁₋₅; allatum (5), A₁₋₅. In some genera the setae are much reduced and easily damaged or lost. However, in *Runcinia*, those which are present, although reduced, are species-specific in shape, size and position and are present in both the mature and immature stages.

Apart from the primary setae the carapace is also frequently clothed with numerous short, irregularly spaced setae. In some genera, e.g. *Thomisus*, these setae vary in shape and have specific value.

Abdomen. Two to three pairs of smooth depressions indicate the attachment of the internal muscles (Fig. 1a). The integument is usually smooth and clothed with short fine setae which vary in shape and length between genera and species. In certain genera (mainly *Misumena*-group) the abdomen is covered with striae that follow the contours of the abdomen. The striae are usually covered with rows of short setae. The abdomen varies much in appearance and usually has characteristic colours and/or patterns. It is usually oval, but may vary in shape.

Legs. Eight, arranged in four pairs and numbered from the anterior (I-IV). Each leg has seven segments and a particular segment of a leg is re-

ferred to as e.g. metatarsus II in the text. In the *Misumeninae* legs I and II are considerably longer and stronger than III and IV. In the first instar this distinction is not yet clear, but it becomes more so as it approaches maturity. In this subfamily, the anterior two pairs of legs are twisted back and held sideways so that the prolateral surface faces dorsally. This is known as laterigrade and describes the crab-like sideways motion of these spiders. By this arrangement the first pair of legs becomes an active grasping organ.

Setae. The body and legs of the spider are covered with different types of setae: macro-setae (spines), setae and micro-setae (hairs). This classification is arbitrary and it is difficult to distinguish between the different types of setae especially if all three types are not represented together. The main criterion for distinguishing between them is size. Closely related species may have structures which could undoubtedly be called setae in one species, but are represented by stronger structures in another and are then called spines or macro-setae.

Macro-setae are usually black in colour and found on the legs and palps. These setae may arise from the cuticle, but often originate from the top of a hollow tubercle. They originate from a colourless area of the exoskeleton and are surrounded by a darker ring. The shape of the base is always characteristic. Each seta is connected with a nerve ending (Fig. 3e).

Setae (Fig. 3b-d) are finer in structure than the macro-setae and often lie closer to the surface, instead of projecting at right angles to it. Unlike macro-setae, which usually form rows, the setae are found in patches. Setae are not erectile, and their bases lie inside rings surrounding pores in the cuticle. The following types of setae are found in the thomisids; club-shaped setae which vary from clavate (broader at the apex than at the base) (Fig. 2c)

to a uniform thickness (Fig. 3d) and spiniform setae which are sharply pointed (Fig. 3b).

Micro-setae (Fig. 3a) are also called hairs and are thinner and finer in structure than the setae. The main part of the body and legs are clothed with these setae. They may be smooth, finely ciliate or plumose and may be more or less erect or lie prone. If

coloured they may form patterns or reinforce an existing colour pattern on the integument.

Trichobothria (Fig. 3f) are fine, often very long and thin, erect setae, located singly or in series at various places on the legs. Each seta has its origin in a tiny circle on the surface and is usually smooth,

FIG. 3a-f

Types of setae/*Tipe seta*. (a) Micro-seta (hair)/*Mikroseta (haar)*. (b) Spiniform seta/*Stekelvormige seta*. (c-d). Club-shaped setae/*Knuppelvormige seta*. (e). Macro-seta/*Makroseta*. (f). *Trichobothrium/Trigobothrium*

sometimes ciliated. The presence, absence, and distribution of the trichobothria are of taxonomic value in certain groups. They are sensory receptors and have astrotactic and sonotactic functions as well as an orientation function.

Colour. Colour has only infrequently been helpful to identify species, as considerable intraspecific variation was observed and it invariably fades in alcohol-preserved specimens. However, the consistent presence or absence of a colour pattern in some species, e.g. the blackening of the tarsus of the male of *Thomisus granulatus*, has specific value.

The ability of some thomisid species of the *Misumena*-group to change colour to conform with the background of their habitat has intrigued naturalists for nearly 100 years. The adult females of some of the species of the genera *Misumena* and *Thomisus* have the ability to change colour reversibly. The colour range varies from white to yellow. The spiders are white on flowers of most colours but become yellow on yellow flowers. Studies on this aspect were undertaken by Packard (1905), De Kerville (1907), Pearse (1911), Rabaud (1923), Gabritschewsky (1927), Gertsch (1939).

TAXONOMY

FAMILY THOMISIDAE

"Laterigrades" Latreille, 1817: 91.

Laterigradae Latreille, 1825: 315.

Thomisides Sundevall, 1833: 27.

Thomisoidae Thorell, 1870: 170.

Thomisidae Simon, 1895: 761, 949; 1897a: 1; 1903b: 669; F. Pickard-Cambridge, 1900: 127; Dahl, 1913: 15; Mello-Leitao, 1929: 9; Gertsch, 1939: 295; Schick, 1965: 36; Suman, 1970: 792; Homann, 1975: 181.

Type-genus: *Thomisus* Walckenaer, 1805.

The family Thomisidae is a well-defined group of small to moderately large spiders. They are also known as laterigrade spiders because of the crab-like movements of most of the species, hence the popular name crab spiders. They can be distinguished from other families by their eyes which are arranged in two transverse rows of four each; the lower margin of the chelicera is unarmed (except in Stephanopsinae); each leg has two toothed tarsal claws; the legs are rather stout; legs I and II are usually longer and thicker than legs III and IV; palp of male provided with retrolateral, ventral and sometimes intermediate apophyses on tibia; embolus arising on periphery of tegulum; tegulum flattened, usually round in ventral view; epigynum of female usually with a deep and rounded atrium; atrium sometimes divided by a median septum or atrium sometimes provided with a hood anteriorly; spermathecae usually large and strongly sclerotized.

The Thomisidae are divided into six subfamilies by Simon (1895): Aphantochilinae, Strophinae, Stiphropodinae, Stephanopsinae, Misumeninae and Philodrominae. The following key to the subfamilies has been adapted from Simon (1895).

KEY TO THE SUBFAMILIES OF THE THOMISIDAE

- | | | |
|----|---|----------------|
| 1. | Labium and maxillae long, acuminate..... | 2 |
| - | Maxillae not acuminate, labium short and truncated or anteriorly rounded..... | 3 |
| 2. | Labium narrow and laminate. Sernum short, coxa III hardly exceeding sternum in size..... | |
| - | Aphantochilinae | |
| - | Labium narrow. Sternum normal..... | Strophinae |
| 3. | Tarsus of first legs longer than metatarsus, thickened; claws minute or rudimentary .. | Stiphropodinae |
| - | Tarsus and claws normal..... | 4 |
| 4. | Lower margin of chelicerae armed. First pair of legs longer than second..... | Stephanopsinae |
| - | Lower margin of chelicerae unarmed. Second pair of legs longer than first..... | 5 |
| 5. | Integument with plumose or squamose hairs. True claw tufts present. Legs about equal in length... | |
| - | Philodrominae | |
| - | Integument with simple hairs. Claw tufts, when present, consist of simple hairs. Third and fourth legs shorter than first and second..... | |
| - | Misumeninae | |

The division of the Thomisidae into six subfamilies is widely accepted. However, Dahl (1913), using the trichobothria as a characteristic, divided the thomisid genera into ten different families but his classification has never been adopted because of the variability of this character. To date the only change to the subfamilial classification of Simon (1895) is that the Philodrominae are given family status by some modern authors (Homann, 1975; Dondale & Redner, 1978).

Apart from the Aphantochilinae all the subfamilies recognized by Simon (Philodrominae included) are known from southern Africa.

SUBFAMILY MISUMENINAE

Misumena Latreille, 1804: 135.

Thomisus Walckenaer, 1805: 28.

Thomisinae Thorell, 1870: 181; Schick, 1965: 103.

Misumeninae Simon, 1895: 968; Dahl, 1913: 15; Gertsch, 1939: 296; Suman, 1970: 792; Petrunkevitch, 1928: 55, 166.

The Misumeninae is by far the largest of all the subfamilies of the Thomisidae. It consists of 75 genera and 1 062 species (Mello-Leitao, 1929). Species of the Misumeninae represent the complete thomisid fauna of the Nearctic region. The Afrotropical region has a rich fauna of 46 genera and in southern Africa alone 22 genera have been recorded to date.

The most important characters which distinguish the misumenine spiders are the height and shape of the clypeus, the size and arrangement of the eyes, the shape of the eye tubercles, the shape of the carapace and the length of the first two pairs of legs.

Simon (1895) was the only person who subdivided the Misumeninae. He grouped the existing genera into 18 groups based on the following characters: the structure of the chelicerae; the size and shape of the lateral ocular tubercles and the shape of the tarsi and claws of the anterior pairs of legs.

Simon's system of classification is not acceptable because only a few characters were used and they do not always reflect natural relationships. But a more natural system cannot be proposed until all the genera have been revised.

The genera studied here represent the *Misumena*-group of genera, containing the genera *Misu-*

mena, *Misumenops*, *Runcinia* and *Thomisus*. The *Misumena*-group corresponds to the Misumeneae group of Simon (1895).

When reference in the text is made to relationships this refers mainly to morphological similarities and does not necessarily reflect phylogenetic relationships.

MISUMENA-GROUP OF GENERA

The genera of this group are characterized by a carapace which is narrower in the cephalic area than in the thoracic area; eyes small and usually equal in size, arranged in two rows; the posterior eye row broader but usually less recurved than the anterior eye row; the lateral eyes usually situated on protuberances that vary in shape between the genera, i.e. from a carina in *Runcinia* to distinct eye tubercles in *Thomisus*; the anterior two pairs of legs longer and more robust than the posterior two pairs; the tarsi of all four pairs of legs shorter than the metatarsi; the tibiae and metatarsi of legs I and II provided with strong macro-setae ventrally.

These spiders are of small to moderate size, usually of a fawn colour while the flower inhabitants are brightly coloured. They are slow movers and catch their prey by ambush.

KEY TO THE GENERA OF THE MISUMENA-GROUP OF SOUTHERN AFRICA

- | | | |
|----|--|---|
| 1. | Eyes situated on distinct protuberances (Fig. 4c and 22a) | 2 |
| - | Eye tubercles indistinct, only slightly protuberant (Fig. 33a and 38a) | 3 |
| 2. | Eyes situated on tubercles (Fig. 4c) | |
| - | <i>Thomisus</i> Walckenaer | |
| - | Eyes situated on a carina (Fig. 22a) | |
| - | <i>Runcinia</i> Simon | |
| 3. | Body covered with numerous erect setae | |
| - | <i>Misumenops</i> F. Pickard-Cambridge | |
| - | Body smooth without erect setae | |
| - | <i>Misumena</i> Latreille | |

THOMISUS WALCKENAER, 1805

Thomisus Walckenaer, 1805: 28; Simon, 1875: 152; 1886a: 361; 1895: 1018; 1932: 787; De Lessert, 1919: 207; Millot, 1941: 43; Locket & Millidge, 1951: 171; Levy, 1973: 124.

Daradius Thorell, 1870: 170; Simon, 1886a: 361; Simon, 1895: 1018. Type-species: *Thomisus yolophus* Doumerc, 1864.

Type-species: *Thomisus onustus* Walckenaer, 1805.

The genus *Thomisus*, as described by Walckenaer (1805), includes a group of spiders characterized by short, robust bodies, with the first two pairs of legs stout and the lateral eyes situated on distinct eye tubercles.

Doumerc (1864) described *Thomisus yolophus* which was later synonymized with *Thomisus tripunctatus* Lucas (Simon, 1895). The former species was

erroneously described as having only six eyes. Thorell (1870) proposed the genus *Daradius* for *T. yolophus* and seven other *Thomisus* species on the ground that they have the AME smaller than the ALE, and the MOQ wider than long. His proposal, however, was not widely accepted. Simon (1895), in his revision of the thomisids of the world, pointed out that *Daradius* is not well demarcated since *T. daradioides* Simon and *T. boesenbergi* Lenz are intermediate between *Daradius* and *Thomisus*, while *T. grubei* Simon has an almost square MOQ.

The genus *Plancinus* which, according to Simon (1895) replaces *Thomisus* in South America, is morphologically very close to *Thomisus*, being comparable in the configuration of the carapace, abdomen and legs. However, *Plancinus* is generally darker, with the PME more closely situated than the PLE, and with the eyes situated on a slightly carinated front, as in *Runcinia*. *Thomisus* is also very similar to *Misumenoides* and *Misumena* in having the same body shape and colour. The three genera are also found in the same type of habitat. However, *Thomisus* differs from them in the position of the eyes and the presence of eye tubercles.

On the basis of the African material at hand, the genus *Thomisus* is defined as follows.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size: small to moderate (3.0-11.1 mm).

Colour: brightly coloured, varies from white to a bright yellow, sometimes with pink or brown patches. A few species are entirely brown, ocular area usually ivory-white.

Carapace: as wide as long, rather high and convex (Fig. 4a); truncated anteriorly; strongly protuberant on anterior lateral corners, to form the eye tubercles; posterior margin concave; primary setae not always present, when present not constant in number and easily lost by handling. Clypeus vertical, with primary setae on margin. Eyes in two rows, anterior row on frontal slope (Fig. 4c), posterior row situated on dorsal side; lateral eyes situated on tubercles; anterior eye row recurved, posterior row straight or slightly recurved; all eyes rather small, size varies between species; AME usually nearer to each other than to ALE; PME usually further apart from each other than from PLE. Shape of abdomen varies a little between species, usually triangular or pentagonal (Fig. 4b); truncated anteriorly and broad posteriorly with two tubercles present on the dorsal surface of abdomen, situated medially between the anterior and posterior apices (Fig. 4b); the tubercles vary slightly in size and shape between species. The integument varies from smooth (with only a few primary setae), to rugose and studded with small tubercles (each tubercle provided with a club-shaped or spiniform seta), or with entire body covered with numerous long, spiniform setae. Legs I and II robust, distinctly longer than III and IV; clothed with numerous short, irregularly spaced setae; tibiae and metatarsi I and II ventrally with double row of macro-setae, number varies between species. Epigynum small and simple, usually a rounded depression

FIG. 4a-c *Thomisus* sp. female/wyfie. (a). Carapace, dorsal view/*Karapaks, dorsale aansig*. (b). Abdomen, dorsal view/*Abdomen, dorsale aansig*. (c). Carapace, anterior view/*Karapaks, anterioraansig*

FIG. 5 Known geographical distribution of *Thomisus* Walckenaer/*Bekende geografiese verspreiding van Thomisus Walckenaer*

with a median septum or two rounded sclerotized circles.

Male. Marked sexual dimorphism is found in most of the *Thomisus* species. Size: smaller than female (1,9-3,6 mm).

Colour: usually a shade darker than the female, with some leg segments almost black in some species.

Carapace flattened; eye tubercles sharply pointed; abdomen ovate, usually without the two abdominal tubercles; integument usually clothed with numerous long, robust spiniform setae. Legs long and thin; macro-setae on tibiae and metatarsi I and II vary from robust to long and thin, covered with long, thin hairs (as in *Runcinia* males). Palp: tibia armed with RTA and VTA, which vary in shape and afford good characters to distinguish between species.

Juvenile. Very similar to females in shape, colour and the type of integument.

DISTRIBUTION

Thomisus is a large genus and comprises c. 82 species with the following distribution: Afrotropical region (43 endemic); Palaearctic region (12); Oriental region (25); Neotropical region (2) (Fig. 5). However, Simon (1895) is of the opinion that the two Neotropical species belong to another genus. Roewer (1954) lists seven species from the Nearctic region. Six of these species from Georgia were described by Walckenaer (1837). However, apart from the citation of Roewer (1954) these records have, to my knowledge, not been discussed or questioned in print, nor are species of *Thomisus* listed in check lists or revisions (e.g. Gertsch, 1939, Chickering, 1940, Schick, 1965) of the New World thomisids. The geographical distribution pattern of *Thomisus* coincides largely with that of *Runcinia*, and both genera are restricted to the eastern hemisphere.

SPECIES OF THE AFROTROPICAL REGION

Forty-seven species are known from the Afrotropical region of which 43 are endemic (Appendix 1). Fifteen of these species are known from southern Africa. Appendix 1 lists the species of *Thomisus* known from the Afrotropical region, their synonyms and distribution.

DISCUSSION

Morphological characters. Intrapopulation variation in size, colour and shape was invariably found to be extensive. These characters were unfortunately, often used for describing species and especially subspecies. The genitalia are less variable and more useful for species separation. The epigynum of the female is not always very distinctive, but fortunately the spermathecae were found to have great taxonomic value in species differentiation. The latter character has not been used in any detail in earlier studies. The palp of the male is distinctive, with dis-

tinct species-specific apophyses and setae on the tibia of the palp.

Other characters used in combination with the genitalia were: the size and configuration of the eyes; the type of integument; the type of body chaetotaxy and to a lesser extent the shape of the abdominal tubercles. The primary setae on the carapace were not very distinct and have little taxonomic value in this genus.

Due to marked sexual dimorphism, it is very difficult to match the male and female of the same species, unless they were collected together. With more material available it was possible to determine that *T. anthobioides* is the female of *T. dalmasi*; *T. drakensbergensis* the female of *T. australis*; *T. weberi* the male of *T. steningi*; *T. dottrensi* the male of *T. spiculosus* and *T. lawrencei* the male of *T. granulatus*. Four species, *kalaharinus*, *natalensis*, *schultzei* and *zuluanus* remain known only from females, while *congoensis* and *machadoi* are known only from males.

Morphological adaptations. The species of *Thomisus* produce no webs. They have lost their agility, have become semi-sedentary and excel as ambushers. They have strong bodies and robust front legs which enable them to attack insects or spiders much larger than themselves. With their cryptic colouration most species await their prey (primarily insect pollinators, e.g. bees) in the heads of flowers. Although they have weak chelicerae, they secrete extremely potent venom which enables them to attack insects 2-3 times their size. Winged insects are seized and the spider pierces the insect between the head and thorax. When an insect is accidentally bitten elsewhere, the spider turns the insect around so that it can insert its chelicerae between the head and thorax. The thomisids have no cheliceral teeth and their prey is consequently not mashed but is sucked dry. The life-like carcass is held in a natural position on the flower while it is being fed on, and thus affords some protection to the spider.

Thomisus species display an interesting range of adaptations to their habitats. *T. scrupeus*, with its brown granulated body, is primarily found on the bark of trees while *T. granulatus* and *T. spiculosus* with their spiny appearance mostly inhabit grass and resemble the inflorescence. Some species of *Thomisus* are known for their ability to change colour from white to yellow and vice versa, with some adjustment to the colour of the flower. This phenomenon was previously observed only in *T. onustus*. It is now recorded in both *T. anthobioides* and *T. steningi*.

Biology. Very little is known about the biology of *Thomisus*. Adults are commonly found from November to May. The male is much smaller than the female and makes little use of sight when mating. When he encounters a female of the same species, he immediately climbs onto her back. The female is often observed with the tiny long-legged male clinging to her back. He is much more agile and climbs around to her venter for mating. The shortness of the palpal appendage and the embolus makes it impossible for him to reach the epigynum from above.

The egg-sac is lenticular in form and consists of two equal halves which are united at the border. The egg-sac is usually fastened to a leaf or piece of plant material.

The biology of only one *Thomisus* species, *T. onustus* (known from the Palaearctic region), has been studied (Levy, 1970).

KEY TO THE SPECIES OF *THOMISUS* FROM SOUTHERN AFRICA

FEMALES

1. Integument granulated and covered with small tubercles, each tubercle provided with a club-shaped or long spiniform seta 2
- Integument smooth, no tubercles 8
2. Eyes, frontal view, with black to dark brown triangular pattern (Fig. 7b) 3
- Eyes, without pattern 4
3. Body covered with numerous, long spiniform setae (Fig. 6e) *spiculosus* Pocock
- Body covered with inconspicuous short setae *blandus* Karsch
4. Small tubercles on integument, each provided with a club-shaped seta (Fig. 9e) 5
- Small tubercles on integument, each provided with a long spiniform seta (Fig. 8b) *granulatus* Karsch
5. Integument with a few small scattered tubercles; colour of body fawn 6
- Integument rugose and granulated; colour of body brown to dark brown *scrupeus* (Simon)
6. ALE larger than AME *natalensis* Lawrence
- ALE and AME equal in size 7
7. Cephalic region of carapace slightly elevated; epigynum with narrow median septum (Fig. 11a) *zuluanus* Lawrence
- Eye region of carapace slightly elevated; epigynum with wide median septum (Fig. 12a). *schultzei* Simon
8. Eye tubercles directed slightly dorsad; legs banded; abdomen with markings and/or two black spots on abdominal tubercle 9
- Eye tubercle directed slightly laterad; legs without bands; abdomen without markings 10
9. Epigynum consisting of two sclerotized circles, copulatory tubes of internal genitalia long (Fig. 13a); abdomen with markings (Fig. 13d). *citrinellus* Simon
- Epigynum consisting of two semi-circles, copulatory tubes of internal genitalia shorter (Fig. 14b); abdomen usually with two black spots on abdominal tubercle (Fig. 14d) *daradioides* Simon
10. Epigynum a dark sclerotized plate, orifices two small circular openings (Fig. 15a and b) *kalaharinus* Lawrence
- Epigynum not a 'sclerotized' plate 11
11. Epigynum consisting of two semi-circles with a thin median septum (Fig. 16d) *steningi* Pocock
- Epigynum not semi-circles 12
12. Epigynum large, horseshoe-shaped (Fig. 17d) *australis* Comellini
- Epigynum consisting of two circles, with a small opening dorsally (Fig. 18b) *dalmasi* De Lessert

MALE

1. Legs I and II short and robust, tibiae and metatarsi provided with thick macro-setae 2
- Legs I and II thinner and longer, tibiae and metatarsi clothed with long thin hair, macro-setae not clearly visible 5
2. Integument studded with small tubercles, each tubercle with a long spiniform seta *granulatus* Karsh
- Integument studded with small tubercles, each tubercle with a club-shaped or short spiniform seta 3

3. Leg segments very short and thick, macro-setae on tibiae and metatarsi I and II very thick *scrupeus* (Simon)
- Leg segments normal, macro-setae on tibiae and metatarsi I and II of moderate thickness 4
4. Legs covered with numerous erect setae, legs I and II dark brown, except metatarsus and tarsus; palp as in Fig. 6a *spiculosus* Pocock
- Legs with fewer setae, not erect; legs I and II brown except the basal half of femur and tarsus; palp as in Fig. 7a *blandus* Karsch
5. Tegular apophysis directed ventrad (Fig. 13c) 6
- Without tegular apophysis 7
6. No RTA; tegular apophysis extending almost half the length of tibia (Fig. 13c) *citrinellus* Simon
- RTA present; tegular apophysis not extending so far down, only to edge of bulb (Fig. 14c) *daradioides* Simon
7. Patella of palp with very distinct apophysis on the retrolateral side (Fig. 16b) *steningi* Pocock
- Patella without an apophysis 8
8. Embolus very short and thick, tip directed slightly dorsad (Fig. 17a) 9
- Embolus slender and thinner, circular (Fig. 19a) 10
9. Embolus thickened at base, tip blunt (Fig. 17a) *australis* Comellini
- Embolus slender and thinner, tip more sharply pointed (Fig. 18d) *dalmasi* De Lessert
10. Retrolateral side of tibia of palp covered with very small tubercles, each tubercle provided with a strong hair; RTA without a small tubercle on retrolateral side (Fig. 19a) *congoensis* Comellini
- Retrolateral side with larger tubercles, each tubercle provided with a strong seta; small tubercle on RTA (Fig. 20a) *machadoi* Comellini

Thomisus spiculosus Pocock, Fig. 6a-f

Thomisus spiculosus Pocock, 1901: 340; Comellini, 1957: 27.

Thomisus dottrensi Comellini, 1957: 10, syn. nov.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size (n=7): TL :8,2 (7,9-8,3); CL 3,7 (3,6-3,8); CW 3,9 (3,5-4,0); CI 0,9.

Colour of body yellowish in alcohol; carapace with faint mediolateral lines; eye and cephalic region suffused with white; a distinct dark, triangular pattern between anterior eyes (Fig. 6b); femur and tibia I with a black spot in middle of each segment, prolaterally (Fig. 6f). Freshly caught specimens have a pale green carapace and legs; abdomen with green transverse bands between tubercles on abdomen.

Carapace high, slightly wider than long. Both eye rows recurved, anterior row more so than posterior row; ALE slightly larger than AME, posterior eyes almost same size; AME nearer to each other than ALE, PME slightly nearer to PLE than to each other. Tubercles on abdomen small. Leg II slightly longer than I; metatarsi I and II with 5-6 pairs of macro-setae, tibiae I and II with 5 pairs. Integument: body and legs covered with numerous long, spiniform setae, each seta situated on a small tubercle (Fig. 6e); some setae, as well as their bases, darker than rest. Epigynum larger than that of *T. blandus*, however, basic shape very similar; only median septum narrower (Fig. 6d). Internal genitalia as shown in Fig. 6c.

Male. Size (n=2): TL 3,6; CL 1,5; CW 1,8; CI 0,8.

Colour of carapace dark brown, slightly darker around edge; chelicerae dark brown; abdomen yellowish brown; legs same colour as carapace, except metatarsi and tarsi I and II which are slightly paler in colour than rest of legs; metatarsi, tarsi and basal half of femora of legs III and IV banded with cream; the joints between each segment of all legs are white.

Eye tubercles strongly pointed; both eye rows recurved; posterior eyes all equal in size; ALE larger than AME; PME nearer to PLE than to each other; AME nearer to each other than to ALE. Tubercles on abdomen smaller than in female. Integument: clothed with numerous long setae. Tibiae I and II with 3-4 pairs of macro-setae, metatarsi with 2-3 pairs. Palp (Fig. 6a) structurally very similar to that of *T. tripunctatus* Lucas.

FIG. 6a-f

Thomisus spiculosus Pocock. (a). Palp, ventral view/*Palp, ventrale aansig*. (b). Carapace of female, anterior view/*Karapaks van wyfie, anterioraansig*. (c). Internal genitalia, dorsal view/*Inwendige genitalieë, dorsale aansig*. (d). Epigynum, ventral view/*Epigynium, ventrale aansig*. (e). Abdominal setae/*Abdominale seta*. (f). Leg I, proteral view/*Poot I, proterale aansig*

Juvenile. Body grey to cream; carapace with distinct mediolateral lines; pattern between eye tubercles indistinct, legs banded. Differs from *T. blandus* in that the body is covered with numerous long, spiniform setae.

SYNONYMY AND RELATIONSHIPS

The integument of *T. spiculosus* is similar to that of *T. granulatus* and *T. albohirtus* in being clothed with numerous long setae. *T. spiculosus* is structurally closest to *T. blandus* and *T. tripunctatus*, in being comparable in size, colour, and in the triangular pattern between the front eyes.

Comellini (1957) described *T. dottrensi* on the basis of one male specimen from Zaïre. In comparing the holotype male of *T. dottrensi* with males collected with *T. spiculosus* females, I could find no differences between them, and therefore consider *T. dottrensi* the male of *T. spiculosus* and hence a synonym of the latter species.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Salisbury, Zimbabwe (17° 50' S, 31° 02' E), ♀, (B.M.?).

Type-locality of synonym: *T. dottrensi* Lukafu (Katanga), Zaïre (9° 50' S, 26° 00' E), ♂ (M.R.A.C. 96916).

DISTRIBUTION

Zimbabwe, Zaïre.

New records: Nigeria, South Africa (Transvaal).

MATERIAL EXAMINED

NIGERIA: Noraguta Hills, 31.vii.1962, ♀ (B.M. 1968 3.1.4). **ZAÏRE:** Lukafu, Katanga, ♂ holotype (M.R.A.C. 96916); Kisantu, 1927, R. Vanderyst, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 91827); Luashi, 6.xii.1958, R. de Faueaux, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 113947). **SOUTH AFRICA:** *Transvaal:* Roodeplaat Nature Reserve, 26.xi.1979, M. Stiller, ♀, ♂, juveniles (N.C.A. 80/54); Shiliowani, Leydsdorp, vi. 1903, ♀ (S.A.M. B13440); Shewasaulu, Mt Sibasa, 18.i.1965, A. Capener, 2 ♀ (N.C.A. 79/343); Blyde River Canyon, 21.ii.1978, E. v.d. Berg, juvenile (N.C.A. 78/233).

BIONOMICS

This species was collected from grass and trees. The only male was collected in November and the females during June, July and from November to January.

Thomisus blandus Karsch, Fig. 7 a-d

Thomisus blandus Karsch, 1880: 382.

Thomisus anthobius Pocock, 1898a: 225; 1898b: 445; 1901: 340; De Lessert, 1919: 208; Comellini, 1957: 5, syn. nov.

Thomisus alboirroratus Simon, 1907: 316; Comellini, 1957: 6, syn. nov.

Thomisus anthobius alboirroratus Simon; Comellini, 1957: 6.

Thomisus malevolus F. Pickard-Cambridge, 1907: 825; De Lessert, 1919: 121; 1923: 169; 1936: 258; Lawrence, 1947: 24; Di Caporiacco, 1941: 125; Comellini, 1957: 5.

Thomisus sus Strand, 1907a: 539; Comellini, 1957: 30, syn. nov.

Thomisus malevolus delessertii Di Caporiacco, 1941: 125, syn. nov.

Thomisus malevolus ocellitibiis Di Caporiacco, 1949: 455, syn. nov.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size (n=10): TL 9,1 (8,1-10,9); CL 3,9 (3,6-4,7); CW 4,3 (4,1-4,8); CI 0,9.

Colour of carapace fawn, with two broad brown lines mediolaterally, cephalic area suffused with white; anterior eyes with distinct triangular pattern between them (Fig. 7b). Abdomen usually white, with a transverse brown band over widest part. Legs fawn, with markings that vary between individuals; femora and tibiae I usually with black spots dorsolaterally. In freshly caught specimens, abdomen and legs tinged with a pale pink.

Cephalic area high; eye tubercles directed laterad and slightly dorsad; both eyes rows slightly recurved. ALE larger than AME; posterior eyes equal in size. Tubercles on abdomen prominent. Legs: femora I with 5 spiniform setae dorsally; tibiae and metatarsi I and II with 4-5 and 5-6 pairs of macrosetae respectively. Integument: body covered with small tubercles, each one provided with a short club-shaped seta; posterior part of abdomen with spiniform setae of which the bases are usually darker. Epigynum: ovate, being an elevated plate, with a pair of sub-circular pits, separated by a broad median septum (Fig. 7d). Spermathecae as shown in Fig. 7c.

Male. Size (n=10): TL 2,9 (2,6-3,6); CL 1,5 (1,3-1,8); CW 1,7 (1,6-1,7); CI 0,9.

Colour of carapace dark brown, with mediolateral lines which are a shade darker. Abdomen yellow to orange-brown. Legs brown, except the basal half of femora of all legs, which is cream; joints between all the leg segments white; metatarsi and tarsi of legs III and IV banded with white.

Abdomen oval, without distinct tubercles on abdomen. Femora I-IV with short setae dorsally; metatarsi and tibiae I and II with 2-3 and 4 pairs of macrosetae respectively. Integument: body clothed with spiniform setae. Palp as shown in Fig. 7a; shape and number of tubercles ventrally on tibia vary a little in shape.

Juvenile. Triangular pattern present between anterior eyes, pale in colour; carapace with distinct lines mediolaterally; body cream. Abdomen triangular in shape.

SYNONYMY AND RELATIONSHIPS

Comellini (1957) synonymized *T. malevolus* [described by Pickard-Cambridge (1907) from the

FIG. 7a-d *Thomisus blandus* Karsch. (a). Palp, ventral view/Palp, ventrale aansig. (b). Carapace of female, anterior view/Karapaks van wyfie, anterioraansig. (c). Internal genitalia, dorsal view/Inwendige genitalieë, dorsale aansig. (d). Epigynum, ventral view/Epigynium, ventrale aansig

Cape Province], and *T. alboirroratus* [described by Simon (1907) from Portuguese Guinea/Guinea-Bissau], with *T. anthobius* [described by Pocock (1898a) from Estcourt, Natal]. Comellini (1957) gave *T. alboirroratus* subspecies status based on minor colour differences.

I studied the type-material of the following species: *T. alboirroratus* (M.N.H.P.), *T. anthobius* (B.M.), *T. malevolus* (H.E.C.), *T. sus* (M.N.B.) and *T. blandus* (M.N.B.) and consider them conspecific, with the last species as senior synonym. This species is very characteristic and easy to identify. In the male the RTA is very distinct and in the female the epigynum and the dark triangular pattern between the anterior eyes are very characteristic.

Di Caporiacco (1941; 1949) described two new subspecies of *malevolus*, namely *delessertii* and *ocellobiis* respectively, on the basis of small colour differences. As these types of colour differences were frequently observed between individuals of this species, the two subspecies are not recognized.

De Lessert (1919) described *T. chubbi*, from Ngare, Tanzania based on one male specimen. In another publication De Lessert (1936) suggested

that *T. chubbi* may be a synonym of *T. anthobius*, but he did not synonymize the two species. Comellini (1957) compared the type-material of *T. chubbi* with that of *T. sus*, a species described from Tanzania by Strand (1907a), and concluded that they are conspecific. The type-material of *T. chubbi* was unfortunately not available for study, but based on the findings of De Lessert (1936) and Comellini (1957) it remains possible that *T. chubbi* is also a synonym of *T. blandus*.

The palp of the male *T. blandus* resembles that of *T. tripunctatus*, whereas it resembles *T. spiculosus* in body size and the triangular pattern between the front eyes.

TYPE-LOCALITY

South Africa (no exact locality), ♂ (M.N.B.)

Type-localities of the synonyms: *T. anthobius* Estcourt, Natal, South Africa (29° 03'S, 29° 07'E), ♀ (B.M.). *T. alboirroratus* Bolama, Guinea-Bissau (11° 30'N, 15° 48'W), ♀ (M.N.H.P.). *T. malevolus* Cape Province (no exact locality), South Africa, ♀ (H.E.C.). *T. malevolus delessertii* Asile, Ethiopia (04° 52'N, 36° 41'E), ♂ (? type-material). *T. male-*

volus ocellitibiis Mau, Kenya (00° 10'S, 35° 31'E), ♀ (? type-material), *T. sus* Amani, Tanzania (05° 06'S, 38° 38'E), ♂ (M.N.B.)

DISTRIBUTION

South Africa (Natal and Cape Province), Guinea-Bissau, Zaïre, Moçambique, Zambia, Tanzania, Sudan, Ethiopia, Kenya.

New records: Zimbabwe, Ivory Coast, Togo, Somali, South Africa (Transvaal).

MATERIAL EXAMINED

IVORY COAST: Zatta, 12.ix.1974, R. Jocqué, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 149.652); Lake Kossou, 27.ix.1974, R. Jocqué, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 149.729). TOGO: Palimé, v.1963, Y. Duc, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 124.360). GUINEA-BISSAU: Bolama, Simon, 2 ♀ type-material *T. alboirroratus* (M.N.H.P. 6976). SUDAN: Darfur, x.1962, J. Cloudsley-Thompson, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 148.509). SOMALI: Giuba, 1946, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 131.230). UGANDA: Lake Victoria, Bugaya, ii-iv.1968, E. Vertriest, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 134.764), 2 ♂ (M.R.A.C. 134.723). TANZANIA: Amani, 20.vii.1903, Vosseler, ♂-holotype *T. sus* (M.N.B. 17970). ZAÏRE: Mundu, Mongbwalu, 1939, Lepersonne, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 73892); Shaba, Luiswishi, ii-iii.1974, F. Malaisse, 2 ♀ (M.R.A.C. 149.207); Kasongo, river Lumani, iii.1960, P.L.G. Benoit, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 120.367), ♀ (M.R.A.C. 121.002); Kinshasa, ii.1941, G. Marlier, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 69058); Kivu, Butemba, 13.vi.1972, ♀, R.P.M. Lejeune, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 144.512); Lubumbashi (Elizabethville), 7.v.1957, ♀, R.P. de Corters, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 103.225); Kivu, Kabilonbo, 12-16. vii. 1949, D. Laurent, 1 immature ♀, (M.R.A.C. 666.07); Kivu, Uvira, iii.1962, R. Kiss, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 122.132); ZAMBIA: Mumbwa, 1.iv.1978, R. Stjernstedt, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 151.995); Kashiji, Chongwe, 5.iii.1978, R. Stjernstedt, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 151.958). ZIMBABWE: Umtali, 13.i.1979, C. Car, 2 immature ♀, 1 immature ♂ (N.M.B. A0042 and 1083). SOUTH AFRICA: no exact locality, ♂-holotype *T. blandus* (M.N.B. 1888). Natal: Estcourt, ♀-holotype *T. anthobius* (B.M.); Lake Sibayi, 1-13.i.1968, R.F. Lawrence, 2 ♂, 3 immature ♀ (A.M.); Hluhluwe Game Reserve, 18.iv.1951, 2 ♀, ♂ (swe. exp. A.M.); Mfongosi, Zululand, ii.1918, W.C. Jones, ♀ (S.A.M. B4167); Jozini (Ndumu road), 3-4.iv.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, 3 ♀, 6 ♂ (N.C.A. 77/712 & 693); Jozini (Mkuzi road), 5.iv. 1977, A.S. Dippenaar, 3 ♂ (N.C.A. 77/735); Makatini Flats, 3.iv.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, 4 ♂ (N.C.A. 79/369); Sodwana Bay, 3-9.v.1981, C. Car, 2 ♀, 10 ♂ (S.A.M. C391, 610, 523); Ngoye Forest, 1.xii.1976, P. Reavell, ♀ (N.C.A. 78/188); Pongola, 27.vi.1968, H. van Ark, ♀ (N.C.A. 76/744); Pennington, 13.iii.1979, C.J. Cilliers, 3 juveniles (N.C.A. 79/392); Empangeni, 20.v. 1978, P. Reavell, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/365); Margate, 14.ii. 1979, C.J. Cilliers, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/168); Illovo Beach 5.i.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, 2 ♂, juveniles (N.C.A. 77/234); Shakaskraal, 13.ii.1979, C.J. Cilliers, ♀

(N.C.A. 79/171); Mt Edgecombe, 16.i.1979, C.J. Cilliers, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/366); Durban, G.P. Staunton, ♀ (B.M. 03.7.10.39). Cape Province: no exact locality, ♀-holotype *T. malevolus* (H.E.C.); East London, Fort Grey Forest Reserve, 2.ii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, 6 juveniles (N.C.A. 79/347); East London, Pineapple Research Station, 7.xii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 78/377); Sundays River Research Station, near Addo, 5-6.xii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, 2 ♂, juveniles (N.C.A. 77/1217); Port Alfred, 1.xii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 77/1187); Kenton-on-Sea xi.1967, R. Jubb, 2 ♀ (A.M.); Port St. Johns, 24-30.xi.1956, R.M. Martin, juveniles (T.M.); Uitenhage, 12.v.1978, N.J. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/390); Port Elizabeth, i.1900, J. Drèje, ♀ (S.A.M. B8463); Kentani, 1899, F. Kolbe, 5 ♀ (S.A.M. B5308); Grahamstown, 9.i.1979, V. Heemstra, ♀ (A.M.); Jeffreys Bay, 6.i.1979, S. Nesor, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/88); Keiskamma River, 5.xii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 78/379); Uniondale, 19.i. 1979, C. Kok, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/67); Cradock 23.iii.1976, A.S. Dippenaar, juveniles (N.C.A. 76/634). Transvaal: Pretoria, 8.ii.1978, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀, 2 ♂ (N.C.A. 79/332); Warmbaths, 17.ii.1977, I. Vosloo, ♀ (N.C.A. 77/479); Brits, 1.ii.1972, G. Newlands, ♂ (T.M.); Kameeldrift, 7.xii.1977, I. van Zyl, immature ♂ (N.C.A. 78/32); Loskopdam, 20.iv.1979, A.S. Dippenaar, juvenile (N.C.A. 79/393); Roodeplaat, 24.x.1978, E. Ueckermann, juveniles (N.C.A. 79/391); Rustenburg Nature Reserve, 5.ii.1980, M. Stiller, 3 ♂ (N.C.A. 80/236); Oudestad, near Groblersdal, 10.i.1980, M. Stiller, 2 ♂ (N.C.A. 80/299); Roodeplaat Nature Reserve, 28.xi.1979, M. Stiller, 5 ♀, 6 ♂ (N.C.A. 80/257, 273, 263-5).

BIONOMICS

T. blandus was collected from trees, grass, herbs and flowers. It was also collected from the following crops: pomelo and pawpaw trees, pumpkins and cotton plants. Mature specimens were collected throughout the year.

Thomisus granulatus Karsch, Fig. 8 a-f

Thomisus granulatus Karsch, 1880: 382; De Lessert, 1923: 173.

Thomisus hystrix Lawrence, 1974: 25 (name preoccupied, Nicolet, 1849).

Thomisus lawrencei Roewer, 1951: 449, syn. nov.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size (n=5): TL 8,8 (7,3-11,1); CL 4,1 (3,5-4,6); CW 4,0 (3,4-4,6); CI 1,0.

Colour of body and legs cream to fawn, covered with small tubercles of which the tips are cream, thus giving a spotted appearance to the body. Carapace with a white line medially. Eye area and prolateral sides of legs sometimes tinged with black.

Carapace as wide as long, flattened; eye tubercles sharp, directed dorsad and slightly laterad; ante-

rior row of eyes recurved, posterior row almost straight. AME a little smaller than ALE and slightly nearer to each other than to ALE; PLE a little larger than PME, equidistant; anterior eyes a little larger than posterior eyes. Abdomen triangular in shape, tubercles on abdomen prominent, pointing laterad. Legs clothed with numerous long setae, legs III and IV with fewer setae than I and II; tibiae I and II with 3-4 pairs of macro-setae, metatarsi I and II with 5-6 pairs. Integument: body and legs covered with numerous small tubercles, which resemble polyps, each tubercle provided with a long spiniform seta (Fig. 8b); some setae and tubercles of a darker colour than the rest, especially on the abdomen. Epigynum: varies slightly in shape between individuals (probably because of the age of the indi-

dual) from trilobate to membranous (Fig. 8d and f); spermathecae shown in Fig. 8e.

Male. Size (n=2): TL 3,6; CL 1,7; CW 1,8; CI 0,9.

Colour of carapace yellowish brown, faintly tinged with black; area around eyes cream. Abdomen yellowish brown, clothed with brown setae. Legs: coxae, trochanters and femora of legs I and II same colour as carapace; patellae, tibiae and metatarsi of these legs blackish brown, tarsi a paler colour.

Smaller than females; eye tubercles sharply pointed, dorsad and slightly laterad. Legs: tibiae and metatarsi I clothed with numerous long, black hairs; with macro-setae not clearly visible; legs III and IV

FIG. 8a-f *Thomisus granulatus* Karsch. (a). Male, dorsal view/*Mannetje, dorsale aansig.* (b). Body setae/*Liggaamseta.* (c). Palp, ventral view/*Palp, ventrale aansig.* (d). Epigynum, ventral view/*Epigynium, ventrale aansig.* (e). Internal genitalia, dorsal view/*Inwendige genitalieë, dorsale aansig.* (f). Epigynum, ventral view (variation)/*Epigynium, ventrale aansig (variasie)*

with fewer setae. Integument: body and legs clothed with numerous thick, and very long spiniform setae (Fig. 8a). Palp as shown in Fig. 8c.

Juvenile. Similar to females; tubercles of abdomen sharply pointed; abdomen triangular in shape; colour of body greyish white, tinged with black.

SYNONYMY AND RELATIONSHIPS

T. granulatus is morphologically closest to *T. spiculosus* and *T. albohirtus*. The three species are clothed with numerous long spiniform setae. However, they differ as follows: *T. albohirtus*, is a more robust spider with strong legs, the tubercles of the abdomen are blunt and pointing dorsad, while *T. granulatus* is a more slender spider, with longer and thinner front legs. *T. spiculosus* differs from both species in having a triangular dark pattern between the anterior eyes.

Lawrence (1947) described *T. hystrix* from Durban, on the basis of a single male specimen. According to Roewer (1951) the name *T. hystrix* was preoccupied by Nicolet (1849) and he consequently changed the name of the species to *T. lawrencei*. Lawrence was of the opinion that *T. hystrix* could be the male of *T. albohirtus* or *T. spiculosus*. However, the male of *T. albohirtus* from Gondaraba was described by Di Caporiacco (1941) and the male of *T. spiculosus* (collected with females) is described for the first time in this paper. The palps of both these species differ from that of *T. lawrencei*.

T. lawrencei was collected during an expedition of Dr I. Trägård (Sweden) to Natal and Zululand in 1904 and 1905. Dr Lawrence (formerly from Natal Museum) was asked to identify the spiders. According to Dr Waldén (in litt.) of the Naturhistoriska Museet Göteborg, Sweden, the material was probably lost in transit as it could not be found in either museum. Although the type-material was not seen, Lawrence (1947) made clear drawings and gave a detailed description of the species. Due to its apparent similarity to *T. granulatus*, especially as regards the palp and spinosity of the body, I consider *T. lawrencei* a synonym of *T. granulatus*.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Malawi (exact locality not known), ♀ (M.N.B. 2997).

Type-locality of synonym: *T. lawrencei* Durban, Natal, South Africa (29° 57'S, 30° 59'E), ♂ (type-material lost).

DISTRIBUTION

Malawi, South Africa (Natal).

New records: Zambia, South Africa (Transvaal, Cape Province).

MATERIAL EXAMINED

MALAWI: (no exact locality), Van Heyne, ♀-holotype (M.N.B. 2997). ZAMBIA: Nabu-

sanga, 1.ix.1978, R. Stjernstedt, juvenile (M.R.A.C. 151.953). SOUTH AFRICA: *Cape Province*: Pineapple Research Station, East London, 28.ix.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/344); Port St Johns, 24.xi.1972, M. Martin, ♂ (N.C.A. 76/765), 7.xii.1977, ♂ (N.C.A. 78/14); Fort Grey Forest Reserve, East London, 2.xii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 77/1151); Cape Town, 14.i.1915, R.W. Tucker, 1 immature ♀ (S.A.M. B893). *Transvaal*: Malip's Drift, 7.xii.1965, A. Capener, ♀ (N.M.); Thabazimbi, 2.ix.1979, A. le Roy, juvenile (N.C.A. 79/354); Levubu, 28.iii.1973, A.S. Dippenaar, juvenile (N.C.A. 76/746); Nelspruit, 17.v.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, juvenile (N.C.A. 77/867); White River, 26.ii.1976, E. Ueckermann, juvenile (N.C.A. 76/981); Tzaneen, 24.ii.1978, E. van den Berg, juvenile (N.C.A. 78/258); Blyde River Canyon, 21.ii.1978, E. van den Berg, juvenile (N.C.A. 78/223) Strydom Tunnel, 22.ii.1978, E. van den Berg, juvenile (N.C.A. 78/246); Kaapmuiden, 14.iv.1979, A. le Roy, juveniles (N.C.A. 79/216). *Natal*: Sodwana Bay 6.v.1981, C. Car, juvenile (S.A.M. C510); Lake Sibayi, 14.v.1981, C. Car, juvenile (S.A.M. C467); Umzumbe River, 16.viii.1979, C.J. Cilliers, immature ♀ (N.C.A. 79/348); Jozini, 1.iv.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, juvenile (N.C.A. 79/360); Dukuduku Nature Reserve 31.iii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, juveniles (N.C.A. 77/629); Hluhluwe, 30.iii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, juvenile (N.C.A. 77/664); Makatini Flats, 2-3.iv.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, juveniles (N.C.A. 77/613); Mt Edgecombe, 21.iv.1977, C.J. Cilliers, juvenile (N.C.A. 77/773); Sodwana Bay, 2.iv.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, juveniles (N.C.A. 77/697); Shakaskraal, 13.ii.1979, C.J. Cilliers, juveniles (N.C.A. 77/170).

Two females from S.A.M. (B862) were measured and examined, their localities on the labels are only "K kloof".

BIONOMICS

Females were collected from September to December, and males during November and December. They were collected mainly from grass. This species is well camouflaged on dry grass and closely resembles grass seed.

Thomisus scrupeus (Simon), Fig. 9a-g

Daradius scrupeus Simon, 1886a: 363.

Thomisus scrupeus (Simon); De Lessert, 1919: 210; Comellini, 1957: 26; Jèzèquel, 1964, 1121.

Thomisus caffer Simon, 1904: 69; De Lessert, 1919: 171; 1923: 171; Lawrence, 1927: 36; 1942: 157; Di Caporiacco, 1949: 455; Comellini, 1957: 26.

Thomisus amanicus Strand, 1907a: 537; 1907b: 652; Comellini, 1957: 26.

Thomisus quadrituberculatus De Lessert, 1943: 327; Comellini, 1957: 26.

Thomisus lindneri Roewer, 1956: 47, syn. nov.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size (n=10): TL 7,1 (6,5-9,8); CL 3,1 (2,7-3,6); CW 3,6 (3,2-4,1); CI 0,9.

Colour of body varies from off-white to dark brown; abdomen usually with a dark brown band between tubercles of abdomen; area posterior to this band sometimes a darker colour than rest. Tibiae and metatarsi I sometimes banded.

Carapace: wider than long (Fig. 9f); eye tubercles flattened dorsally, sharply pointed, directed laterad; both eye rows recurved; ALE larger than AME; AME nearer to each other than the ALE; PLE slightly larger than PME. Abdomen bell-shaped (Fig. 9f). Legs I and II robust (Fig. 9d) with femora, patellae and tibiae thickened; tibiae I and II with 3-4 pairs of short and thick macro-setae, metatarsi I and II with 4-5 pairs. Integument: granulated, covered with small tubercles, polyp-like in appearance (Fig. 9e); some tubercles on abdomen darker than rest, giving abdomen a spotted appearance; each tubercle with a short club-shaped seta. Epigynum: shape varies a little between individuals (Fig. 9b and c); internal genitalia shown in Fig. 9a (see also Jèzèquel, 1964: 1121, Fig. 21a-c).

Male. Size (n=5): TL 3,1 (2,5-3,4); CL 1,6 (1,6-1,7); CW 1,7 (1,6-1,8); CI 1,0.

Structurally very similar to female, differs as follows. Smaller; body more flattened; abdomen without prominent tubercles on abdomen; macrosetae longer on tibiae and metatarsi of legs I and II. Palp: large with embolus short and tegulum enlarged, protuberant (Fig. 9g).

Juvenile. Similar to adult spider.

SYNONYMY AND RELATIONSHIPS

T. scrupeus can be readily separated from its African congeners by the shape of both the male and female genitalia, the granulated integument and the sturdy bodies.

I studied the type-material of *T. amanicus* (M.N.B.) and *T. quadrituberculatus* (M.R.A.C.) and agree with Comellini (1957) who synonymized both species with *T. scrupeus*. Comellini also considered *T. caffer* a synonym of *T. scrupeus*. The type-material of the former species was unfortunately not available for study but its description by Simon (1886a) and a redescription by De Lessert (1923) indicate that it is indistinguishable from *scrupeus* at the specific level.

FIG. 9a-g

Thomisus scrupeus (Simon). (a). Internal genitalia, dorsal view/*Inwendige genitalieë, dorsale aansig*. (b-c). Epigynum, ventral view (variations)/*Epigynium, ventrale aansig (variasies)*. (d). Leg I, lateral view/*Poot I, laterale aansig*. (e). Body setae/*Liggaamseta*. (f). Female, dorsal view/*Wyfie, dorsale aansig*. (g). Palp, ventral view/*Palp, ventrale aansig*

Roewer (1956) described *T. lindneri* from East Africa and it was hitherto known only from the female holotype. The type-specimen was not available for study but the description as well as the clear drawings of Roewer (1956) corresponds so well with that of *scrupeus* that I have no doubt that *T. lindneri* is a synonym of *T. scrupeus*.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Dakar, Senegal, West Africa (14° 45'N, 17° 08'W), ♂, 1 immature ♂ (M.N.H.P. 7914).

Type-localities of synonyms: *T. amanicus* Amani, Tanzania (05° 06'S, 38° 38'E), ♀ (M.N.B.); *T. caffer* Soutpansberg, Transvaal, South Africa (23° 03'S, 29° 57'E), (M.N.H.G.); *T. quadrituberculatus* Sankisia, Zaïre (09° 12'S, 25° 46'E), ♂ (M.R.A.C.); *T. lindneri* Msingi, near Mt Kilimanjaro, Tanzania (03° 12'S, 37° 03'E), ♀ (? type-material).

DISTRIBUTION

Senegal, Tanzania, Zaïre, South Africa (Natal, Cape Province, Transvaal), Kenya, Ivory Coast.

New records: South West Africa, Malawi, Rwanda.

MATERIAL EXAMINED

MALAWI: Chinthche, i-ii.1976, R. Jocqué, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 148.009), ♀ (M.R.A.C.147.940), 1.xii.1977, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 153.339); Forest Chisaira, 16.ii.1976, R. Jocqué, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 148.073). RWANDA: Bugesera, 25.ii.1960, N. Leleup, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 154.402). IVORY COAST: Bingoville, 1.ii.1963, J. Decelle. TANZANIA: Amani, 10.xii.1903, Vosseler, ♀-holotype *T. amanicus* (M.N.B. 17969). SENEGAL: Dakar, ♂-holotype, immature ♀ (M.N.H.P. 7914). ZAÏRE: Sankisia, Dr Rodhain, ♂-holotype *T. quadrituberculatus* (M.R.A.C. 11397); Rwanki, viii, 1951, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 72139); Kivu, v.1946, J. le Roy, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 58.300). SOUTH WEST AFRICA: Kunene River, Erikson's Drift, iii.1923, R.F. Lawrence, ♀ (S.A.M. B6139). SOUTH AFRICA: Transvaal: Thabazimbi, 2.ix.1979, A. le Roy, juvenile (N.C.A. 79/353); Nylsvley, Naboomspruit, iv-viii.1977, G. Ferreira, juveniles (N.C.A. 78/434 and 553); farm Enkeldoorn, Molotto, 6.viii.1974, A.S. Dippenaar, juvenile (N.C.A. 76/296); Zanzibar (border post), 23.viii.1976, A.S. Dippenaar, juveniles (N.C.A. 76/1468); Hartbeespoortdam, 12.xi.1976, N.J. Dippenaar, juvenile (N.C.A. 76/1969); Roodeplaat, 18.ix.1979, M. Bolton, juvenile (N.C.A. 79/358); White River, 22.ii.1965, ♀ (A.M.); farm Swellendam, Maasstroom, 26.viii.1976, A.S. Dippenaar, juveniles (N.C.A. 79/382); Rustenburg Nature Reserve, 7.xi.1979, A.S. Dippenaar, juvenile (N.C.A. 79/400); Roodeplaat Nature Reserve, 26.xi.1979, A.S. Dippenaar, immature ♀ (N.C.A. 80/33); Buffelspoort, 10.i.1980, C.J. Cilliers, ♂ (N.C.A. 80/34). Cape Province: East London, 2.xii.1977, G. Petty, juvenile (N.C.A. 79/387); Fort Grey, 12.ii.1974, C. Co-

lijn, juvenile (N.C.A. 76/1945); Greta farm, Grahamstown, ix.1978, P. Croeser, juvenile (A.M.); Knysna Diepwalle Forest Reserve, 12.vi.1976, N.J. Dippenaar, juvenile (N.C.A. 76/932); Grahams-town, 22.x.1978, P. Croeser, immature ♂ (A.M.); Port Elizabeth, ♀ (A.M.); Kentani, Pegar, ♀ (S.A.M. B150.849); Bathurst, 2.ii.1968, A. Capener, juvenile (N.C.A. 79/388). Natal: Cape Vidal, St Lucia, 14.ix.1972, M.K.P. Meyer, juvenile (N.C.A. 76/1902); Lake Sibayi, 1-31.i.1968, R.F. Lawrence, ♂, ♀, juveniles (A.M.); Port Alfred, 30.xi.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 77/1176); Port Alfred, 7.ii.1968, A. Capener, 5♀ (N.C.A. 79/349); farm Vergeval, Pongola, 3.v.1967, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 76/1293); Empangeni, 25.x.1977, P.Reavell, juvenile (N.C.A. 79/389); Lake Sibayi, 18.v.1981, N. Car, ♀ (S.A.M. C282); Sodwana Bay, v.1981, C.Car, ♀, juveniles (S.A.M. C327, C507, C543).

BIONOMICS

The mature females were collected from December to May and the males from November to January. They were collected mainly from trees but also from grass.

Thomisus natalensis Lawrence, Fig. 10a-d

Thomisus natalensis Lawrence, 1942: 156; Comellini, 1957:21.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size (n=2): TL 8,8; CL 4,3; CW 4,7; CI 0,9.

Colour: carapace and legs uniformly yellow, abdomen white; front pair of legs suffused with white dorsolaterally.

Carapace: a little wider than long, high; eye tubercles not strongly pointed; tubercles form a distinct edge between clypeus and the dorsal part of carapace (like the carina of *Runcinia*) (Fig.10c); both eye rows recurved; AME smaller than ALE; posterior eyes equal in size. Abdomen as seen from above pentagonal in shape with almost straight sides; tubercles on abdomen not strongly developed. Legs: tibiae I and II with 2-3 pairs of macro-setae, metatarsi I and II with 5-6 pairs. Integument: body and legs covered with numerous minute tubercles, each tubercle provided with a club-shaped seta; generally a smoother appearance than *T. scrupeus*. Epigynum: very characteristic, ovate with the edge slightly darkened (Fig. 10b), internal genitalia shown in Fig. 10a.

Male. Unknown.

Juvenile. The immature female studied from Zimbabwe (T.M. 8062) is very similar to adult female; the body shape and the eye tubercles are very characteristic.

RELATIONSHIPS

Morphologically closest to *T. scrupeus* and *T. zuluanus*.

FIG. 10a-d *Thomisus natalensis* Lawrence female/wyfie. (a). Internal genitalia, dorsal view/*Inwendige genitalieë, dorsale aansig.* (b). Epigynum, ventral view/*Epigynium, ventrale aansig.* (c). Carapace, anterior view/*Karapaks, anterioraansig.* (d). Body setae/*Liggaamseta*

TYPE-LOCALITY

Umhlali, North Coast, Natal, South Africa (29° 28'S, 31° 16'E), ♀ (N.M.2923).

DISTRIBUTION

South Africa (Natal).
New records: Zimbabwe.

MATERIAL EXAMINED

ZIMBABWE: Changadzi River, 5m E of Birchenough Bridge, i. 1938, V. FitzSimons, immature ♀ (T.M. 8062). SOUTH AFRICA: *Natal*: Umhlali, North Coast, ♀-holotype (N.M. 2923); Lake Sibayi, 10.i.1969, A. Boshoff, ♀ (N.C.A. 80/35); Sodwana Bay, 19.v.1981, 2 juveniles (S.A.M. C326).

BIONOMICS

A poorly known species. The specimens from Sodwana Bay were collected from low growing vegetation.

Thomisus zuluanus Lawrence, Fig. 11 a-c
Thomisus zuluanus Lawrence, 1942: 155.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size (n=1): TL 7,5; CL 3,7; CW 4,0; CI 0,9.

Colour: carapace and legs yellow, mottled with white; carapace with a triangular pattern when viewed from front, tinged with brown (Fig. 11c); cephalic area with a few faint white broken lines. Abdomen ivory-white.

Carapace: elevated in cephalic area; both eye rows slightly recurved; anterior eyes equal in size but larger than posterior eyes; posterior eyes equal in size. Abdomen pentagonal in shape; tubercles on abdomen indistinct. Legs I and II stout; femora I and II with strong setae dorsally; tibiae I and II with 4-5 pairs of macro-setae and metatarsi I and II with 8-9 pairs, which are stronger than those of tibiae. *Integument*: body covered with small tubercles, each tubercle provided with a stout seta (Fig. 11b), which are, however, easily lost; abdomen with more tubercles than carapace; setae on abdomen slightly longer. *Epigynum*: not very distinct; with narrow median septum (Fig. 11a); the internal genitalia were not studied due to the lack of material.

FIG. 11a-c *Thomisus zuluanus* Lawrence female/wyfie. (a). Epigynum, ventral view/Epigynium, ventrale aansig. (b). Body setae/Liggaamseta. (c). Carapace, anterior view/Karapaks, anterioraansig

Male. Unknown.

Juvenile. Unknown.

RELATIONSHIPS

The shape of the body resembles *T. natalensis*, but their genitalia differ. Resembles *T. schultzei* in the basic shape of the genitalia, but the shape of the carapace and eye tubercles differ.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Kosi Bay, Natal (Zululand), South Africa (2° 03' S, 33° 01' E), ♀ (N.M. 1992).

DISTRIBUTION

Known only from type-specimen.

MATERIAL EXAMINED

SOUTH AFRICA: Natal: Kosi Bay, Toppin, ♀-holotype (N.M. 1992).

BIONOMICS

Unknown.

Thomisus schultzei Simon, Fig. 12 a-c

Thomisus schultzei Simon, 1910: 194; Lawrence, 1936: 153; Comellini, 1957:25.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size (n=10): TL 7,8 (4,9-9,8); CL 3,1 (2,2-3,6); CW 3,2 (2,3-3,6); CI 1,0.

Colour: carapace and legs fawn; cephalic area suffused with white and triangle between anterior eyes brownish. Abdomen white.

Carapace: area in which eyes are situated slightly elevated (Fig. 12c); eye tubercles blunt, not very prominent; anterior eye row recurved; posterior row straight; anterior eyes equal in size; AME nearer to each other than the ALE; posterior eyes equal in size; PME nearer to PLE than to each other; posterior eyes smaller than anterior eyes. Abdomen bell-shaped. Legs: front pairs strong; tibiae I and II with 3-4 pairs of macro-setae; metatarsi I and II with 6 pairs. Integument: covered with numerous small tubercles, each tubercle provided with a short club-shaped seta; abdomen also with spiniform setae. Epigynum: elevated, two semi-circular pits anteriorly divided by a median septum (Fig. 12a); spermathecae figured in Fig. 12b.

Male. Unknown.

Juvenile. Unknown.

RELATIONSHIPS

This species resembles *T. zuluanus* in shape and size, and has the same type of setae on the body. However, the genitalia and eye tubercles differ.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Keetmanshoop, Great Namaqualand, South West Africa (26° 30' S, 18° 05' E), ♀ (M.N.H.P. 24491).

DISTRIBUTION

South West Africa, South Africa (Cape Province).

MATERIAL EXAMINED

SOUTH WEST AFRICA: Gobabeb (dunes south of station), 6.iv.1967, C. Koch, ♀ (A.M.); Gobabeb, 26.vi.1969, M. Jenson, ♀ (A.M.); Gobabeb, 30.i.1976, B. Wharton, ♀ (N.C.A. 80/55); Outjo, iv. 1925, ♀ (S.A.M. B6730); Kaoko Otavi, i-iv.1926, ♀ (S.A.M. B7037); Kunene River, xi.1960, F. Gaerdes, ♀ (S.A.M. B8022); Belle-rode farm, Windhoek, 24.ii.1975, F.C. de Moor, ♀ (N.M.B.); Sesfontein, ♀ (S.A.M. B6634); Okahandja, iv.1970, F. Gaerdes, ♀ (A.M.); Rosh Pinab Mines, Lüderitz district, iv. 1973, A. Moritz, ♀ (N.C.A. 76/443). **SOUTH AFRICA:** *Cape Province:* Calvinia, 1.vi.1902, Dr Marloth, ♀ (Z.M.H.).

BIONOMICS

Known only from the warm and dry regions of southern Africa. The females were collected between November and June. According to Wharton (1980) *T. schultzei* was present almost throughout the year on *Zygophyllum simplex* in the central

Namib Desert. It was observed feeding on Halictid and Tinaegeriid adults.

Thomisus citrinellus Simon, Fig. 13 a-e

Thomisus spinifer O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872: 308; Simon, 1886a: 360; 1898: 379; 1932: 787; Pocock, 1903: 264; De Lessert, 1936: 255; Millot, 1941: 45; Di Caporiacco, 1941: 125; Comellini, 1957: 27 (name preoccupied, Blackwall, 1862).

Thomisus citrinellus Simon, 1875: 253; Bonnet, 1959: 4578; Levy, 1973: 127; Benoit, 1978: 900.

Thomisus spinifer decorata Millot, 1941: 47, syn. nov.

Thomisus spinifer obscurus Di Caporiacco, 1941: 127; 1949: 456, syn. nov.

Thomisus spinifer simoni Di Caporiacco, 1941: 126; 1949: 456, syn. nov.

Thomisus spinifer maculitibiis Di Caporiacco, 1947a: 216, syn. nov.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size (n=10): TL 5,9 (5,3-6,6); CL 2,0 (1,9-2,3); CW 1,9 (1,7-2,3); CI 1,1.

FIG. 12a-c *Thomisus schultzei* Simon female/wyfie. (a). Epigynum, ventral view/Epigynium, ventrale aansig. (b). Internal genitalia, dorsal view/Inwendige genitalieë, dorsale aansig. (c). Carapace, anterior view/Karapaks, anterioraansig

Colour: varies between individuals. Carapace fawn; clypeus and eye area suffused with white; sometimes with white line medially and two dark brown lines mediolaterally. Abdomen white, usually with dark patterns and spots (Fig. 13d). Legs fawn, banded with white and brown; legs I and II more distinctly banded than III and IV.

Carapace: slightly longer than wide, eye area elevated; eye tubercles distinct, pointing laterad and slightly dorsad (Fig. 13e), both eye rows recurved; anterior eyes equal in size; AME nearer to each other than to ALE; posterior eyes same size, equidistant. Abdomen rounded; tubercles on abdomen blunt and directed dorsad; anterior margin of abdomen usually with two small protuberances. Legs not very strong; femora I with 3 setae dorsally; tibiae I and II with 2-3 pairs of macro-setae, and metatarsi I and II with 4-5 pairs. Integument: smooth, no tubercles. Epigynum: externally very similar to that of *T. daradioides* (Fig. 13b and 14a), but the internal genitalia differ (Fig. 13a and 14b).

Male. Size (n=10): TL 2,3 (2,1-2,6); CL 1,0 (1,0-1,2); CW 1,0 (1,0-1,2); CI 1,0.

Colour: carapace fawn to brown; sometimes with lines mediolaterally. Abdomen fawn with faint white and brown markings dorsally. Legs fawn with joints between each segment white; tibiae and metatarsi I and II slightly darker than other segments.

Carapace: eye tubercles sharply pointed. Abdomen: tubercles indistinct. Legs: tibiae and metatarsi I and II with long hairs. Integument: carapace and abdomen with numerous spiniform setae. Palp: large, tegulum on lateral margin large, downwards inclined; tegular apophysis extending for almost half the length of tibia (Fig. 13c).

Juvenile. Similar to females with mediolateral lines on carapace, spotted abdomen and banded legs. However, it is difficult to distinguish between juveniles of *T. citrinellus* and *T. daradioides*.

SYNONYMY AND RELATIONSHIPS

Pickard-Cambridge (1872) described *T. spinifer* but the name had already been preoccupied (Blackwall, 1862). Simon (1875) therefore proposed *T. citrinellus* as a replacement name. This species is not very common in southern Africa.

The subspecies *T. spinifer decorata* (Millot, 1941) and *T. s. simoni*, *T. s. obscurus* and *T. s. maculitibiis* described by Di Caporiacco (1941; 1949) differ from *T. citrinellus* only in colour. As this kind of colour variation was frequently observed in thomisids I consider them to be mere colour variants, rather than subspecies of *T. citrinellus*.

An examination of the type-material of *T. sepiosus*, *T. citrinellus* and *T. daradioides* indicated that,

FIG. 13a-b *Thomisus citrinellus* Simon. (a). Internal genitalia, dorsal view/*Inwendige genitalieën, dorsale aansig.* (b). Epigynum, ventral view/*Epigynium, ventrale aansig.*

FIG. 13c-e (c). Palp, ventral view/*Palp, ventrale aansig.* (d). Female, dorsal view/*Wyfie, dorsale aansig.* (e). Female carapace, anterior view/*Wyfiekarapaks, anterioraansig.*

T. citrinellus and *T. daradioides*, although closely related, are species in their own right. Although their external genitalia are very similar (Fig. 13b and 14a) their spermathecae differ (Fig. 13a and 14b). *T. daradioides*, like *T. citrinellus*, has different colour variants. I differ from Comellini (1957), who synonymized *T. sepiosus* with *T. spinifer decorata*. Therefore *T. sepiosus* is here considered a colour variant of *T. daradioides* and is conspecific with the latter species, and not with *T. spinifer decorata*, as it closely resembles *T. daradioides* in the shape of both the epigynum and the body.

De Lessert (1943) described *T. ghesquierei* which resembles *T. citrinellus*. The two species differ

in the shape of the epigynum and the eye tubercles which are directed more dorsad in *T. ghesquierei*.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Plains of Jordan, Israel (32° 15'N, 35° 32'E), ♀♀ and ♂♂ (H.E.C.).

Type-locality of synonyms: *T. spinifer decorata* Kindia, Guinea (10° 0'N, 12° 52'W), ♀ (M.N.H.P.?); *T. spinifer obscurus* 11 ♂-paratypes from Senegal and Ethiopia (? type-material); *T. spinifer simoni* 3 ♀-paratypes from Senegal and Ethiopia (? type-material); *T. spinifer maculitibiis* Nairobi, Kenya (1° 12'S, 36° 49'E), ♀ (? type-material).

DISTRIBUTION

Israel, Arabia, Yemen, France, Socotra, India, Egypt, Guinea, Ethiopia, Somali Republic, Djibouti, Sudan, Kenya, Upper Volta, Niger, Senegal, Moçambique, Zaïre, South Africa (Natal, Cape Province).

New records: Mali, Chad, Ethiopia, Zimbabwe, Uganda, South Africa (Transvaal).

MATERIAL EXAMINED

ISRAEL: ♀, 2 ♂, juveniles (H.E.C.). EGYPT: 7 ♀, 16 ♂, 4 juveniles (H.E.C.). ETHIOPIA: Gorgora, 1961, F. Hartman, ♂ (M.R.A.C.131.209). CHAD: Bebedjira, Moundou, 16.x.1977, G. Ruella, ♀, 3 ♂ (M.R.A.C. 151.426). MALI: Cincana, viii-ix.1969, G. Pierrard, 2 ♂ (M.R.A.C. 136.807); Mpésoba, viii-ix.1971, G. Pierrard, 3 ♂ (M.R.A.C. 142.367 and 142.371 and 136.775). UGANDA: Entebbe, 1959, P.L.G. Benoit, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 131.129). ZIMBABWE: Bulawayo, ii.1963, ♀ (N.M.B.). SOUTH AFRICA: Transvaal; Pretoria, 28.ix.1978, B. Fourie, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/346); Pretoria, 20.viii.1973, C.J. Cilliers, juvenile (N.C.A. 76/1649); Nylsvley, Naboomspruit, i-xii. 1976, G. Ferreira, juveniles, (N.C.A. 78/491, 540); Rustenburg Nature Reserve, 27.iii.1980, N.J. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 80/215). Natal: Lions River, Howick, 1961, N. Leleup, juvenile (M.R.A.C.132.562).

BIONOMICS

The mature spiders were collected from August to March from grass and trees.

Thomisus daradioides Simon, Fig. 14 a-d

Thomisus daradioides Simon, 1890: 108; Di Caporiacco, 1947b: 849; Comellini, 1957: 10.

Thomisus lesnei De Lessert, 1936: 256; Comellini, 1957: 17; 1959: 117, syn. nov.

Thomisus sepiosus Lawrence, 1942: 152; Comellini, 1957: 27, syn. nov.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size (n=10): TL 5,3 (4,6-7,1); CL 2,3 (2,0-2,6); CW 2,4 (2,1-2,7); CI 1,0

Colour: variation in colour and colour patterns was observed. a description of the ♀-holotype is given first, followed by a short description of the colour variations. Carapace fawn, clypeus, chelicerae and eye area suffused with white; pale brown triangular pattern present between front eyes. Abdomen white; tips of tubercles of abdomen each with a black spot (Fig. 14d). Legs same colour as carapace; anterior two pairs suffused with white dorsolaterally and faintly banded; femur I with setae dorsally of which bases are darkened. Colour variations: carapace fawn, white line medially and two broad dark brown lines mediolaterally; abdomen white; patterns on abdomen vary from spots on tubercles to a black band between the tubercles, or distinct patterns, as in *T. citrinellus* (Fig. 13d). Legs fawn; very distinctly

banded with white and brown on femora, tibiae and coxae of legs I and II.

Carapace: eyes are less elevated than in *T. citrinellus*; eye tubercles directed slightly dorsad and laterad; anterior eye row recurved, posterior row straight; anterior eyes equal in size; AME nearer to each other than the ALE; posterior eyes same size; PME slightly nearer to PLE than to each other. Abdomen: tubercles on abdomen small; clothed with short spiniform setae. Legs: femur I with 3-4 strong spiniform setae dorsolaterally, bases darkened; legs I and II with 2-3 pairs of macro-setae on tibiae and 5-6 pairs on metatarsi. Epigynum: orifices two brown sclerotized circles (Fig. 14a); spermathecae shown in Fig. 14b.

Male. Size (n=10): TL 1,9 (1,6-2,1); CL 1,0 (0,8-1,1); CW 1,0 (0,9-1,2); CI 0,9.

Colour: carapace yellowish brown; legs same colour as carapace, except legs I and II with tibiae and metatarsi dark brown. Abdomen paler than carapace.

Carapace: eye tubercles strongly directed dorsad and slightly laterad. Tibiae and metatarsi I and II without macro-setae, clothed with long, thin dark hairs. Integument: body covered with numerous long thick, erect spiniform setae. Palp: tegular apophysis directed ventrally not so far down as in *T. citrinellus*; tibia with two tubercles on the retrolateral side (Fig. 14c).

Juvenile. Similar to female. Carapace fawn and abdomen white. Two distinct dots on tubercles of abdomen.

SYNONYMY AND RELATIONSHIPS

De Lessert (1936) described *T. lesnei* from Moçambique on the basis of one male specimen. Numerous males were collected later in southern Africa which closely resemble *T. lesnei*. Females and juveniles collected with these males are, however, referable to *T. daradioides*. This indicates that *T. lesnei* is actually the male of *T. daradioides* and I therefore consider *T. lesnei* conspecific with *T. daradioides*.

The same type of colour variation as observed in *T. citrinellus*, also occurs in *T. daradioides*. Comellini (1957) synonymized *T. sepiosus* with *T. citrinellus decorata*. A comparison of the type-material of these species indicated that *T. sepiosus* is only a colour variant of *T. daradioides* and they closely resemble each other in the shape of both the epigynum and the body. *T. sepiosus* is therefore considered a synonym of *T. daradioides*.

T. daradioides and *T. citrinellus* are closely related; they are comparable in the shape of both the epigynum and the body, but their internal genitalia differ distinctly.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Ethiopia, Province Saana, East Africa (8° 0' N, 40° 0' E), ♀ (M.N.H.P. 10647).

Type-localities of synonyms; *T. lesnei* Mocam-

FIG. 14a-d *Thomisus daradioides* Simon. (a). Epigynum, ventral view/*Epigynium, ventrale aansig*. (b). Internal genitalia, dorsal view/*Inwendige genitalië, dorsale aansig*. (c). Palp, ventral view/*Palp, ventrale aansig*. (d). Female, dorsal view/*Wyfie, dorsale aansig*

bique, Bas Sangadze (co-ordinates unknown), ♂ (M.N.H.G.); *T. sepiosus* Pietermaritzburg, Natal, South Africa (29° 38'S, 30° 28'E), ♀ (N.M. 2945).

DISTRIBUTION

Ethiopia, Angola, Moçambique, South Africa (Natal), India, Arabia.

New records: Afars & Issas, Somali, Sudan, Mali, Upper-Volta, Ivory Coast, Zaïre, Zambia, Zimbabwe, South Africa (Transvaal, Cape Province).

MATERIAL EXAMINED

ETHIOPIA: Saana, ♀ (M.N.H.P. 10647). AFARS & ISSAS: Djibouti, vii. 1974, P. Leriche, 9 ♀, 3 juveniles (M.R.A.C. 146.268). SOMALI: Giuba river, 1946, R. Accigliano, ♂ (M.R.A.C.

131.2281). SUDAN: Khartoum, 1960/61, J. Cloudsley-Thompson, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 120.781), 1962/63 ♀, juvenile (M.R.A.C. 123.037). MALI: Kogoni (60 km N Nioro), xii. 1969, G. Pierrard, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 136.757). UPPER-VOLTA: Ouagadougou, iv.-v. 1965, B. Roman, ♀, 4 juveniles (M.R.A.C. 128.053). IVORY COAST: Kossou, 23.ii.1975, R. Jocqué, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 149.656). ZAÏRE: Bamanya, i.1967, R.P. Hubstaert, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 132.884); Kasongo, viii.1959, P.L.G. Benoit, ♀, 3 juveniles (M.R.A.C. 114.980 and 154.399); Kivu, Uvira (Kakasi), vi. 1961, N. Leleup, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 154.007); Kivu, Kaisola, 3.vii.1972, R. Lejeune, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 144.495); Kivu, Kabasha, 23.vi.1972, R. Lejeune, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 144.450); Kivu, Uvira (Kolundu), vi.1961, R. Kiss, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 119.909); Kivu, Bukavu, xii. 1954, H. Bomans, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 85563); Shaba, Luiswishi, xii.1976, F. Malaisse, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 151.528); Kakanda, 22.iv.1959, R. de Foveaux, ♀

(M.R.A.C. 114.794). ZAMBIA: Lusaka, ii.1978, R. Stjernstedt, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 151.937). ZIMBABWE: Bulawayo, ii.1966, ♀ (N.M.B.); Bulawayo, xi.1964-i.1965, S. Bucklin, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 128.098). SOUTH AFRICA: *Cape Province*: Addo National Elephant Park, 5.xii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/355, 377); East London, 1.xii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/403); Port Alfred, 1.xii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/376); Pineapple Research Station, East London, 7.xii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 78/25); Kei River Mouth, 3.xii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 77/1234); Grahamstown, Dasielkran, xii.1969, R.F. Lawrence, 2 ♂ (A.M.); Grahamstown, 3.xii.1978, M.E. Dacombe, ♀ (A.M.); Grahamstown Botanical Gardens, 3.vii.1978, P. Croeser, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/404); Kuru-man, 7.ii.1979, E. Ueckermann, juvenile (N.C.A. 79/405). *Transvaal*: Sabi-Sand, 6.ix.1965, ♀ (A.M.); Letaba River, 28.ii.1968, S. van Rooyen, ♂ (N.C.A. 76/1750); Letaba Estates, Tzaneen, 3.v.1979, C.J. Cilliers, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/256); Barberton Research Station, 9.iii.1967, P. Luus, ♂ (N.C.A. 76-1302); Blyde River Canyon, 23.ii.1978, M.K.P. Meyer, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/364). *Natal*: Pietermaritzburg, iv.1940, R.F. Lawrence, ♀ (N.M. 2954); Pietermaritzburg, vi.1951, A. Lawrence, ♂ (N.M. 6394); Lebombo Mountains, near Jozini, 4.iv.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀, ♂, juveniles (N.C.A. 79/402, 77/710); Makatini Flats, 2.iv.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, 9 ♂, juveniles (N.C.A. 77/611); Manderston, iv.1963, H. Bustin, ♀ (N.M. 8865); Sodwana Bay, 3.v.1981, C. Car, ♂ (S.A.M. C394).

BIONOMICS

The adults were collected from November to July, mainly from flowers, grass and shrubs.

Thomisus kalaharinus Lawrence, Fig. 15a-c

Thomisus kalaharinus Lawrence, 1936: 153.

Thomisus urbensis Lawrence, 1942: 153, syn. nov.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size (n=10): TL 5,9 (4,6-6,8); CL 2,5 (2,2-3,0); CW 2,6 (2,1-2,9); CI 0,9.

Colour: *T. kalaharinus* has the ability to change colour, which varies from white to yellow to a pale shade of pink; body and legs uniformly coloured; clypeus, cephalic region and eye tubercles suffused with ivory.

Carapace: cephalic area elevated; eye tubercles not sharply pointed; anterior eye row recurved, posterior row slightly recurved; ALE a little smaller than AME; AME nearer to each other than the ALE; posterior eyes equal in size, smaller than the anterior eyes; PME nearer to PLE than to each other. Carapace clothed with numerous short, spiniform setae; primary seta S_1 present posterior to PLE. *Abdomen*: tubercles on abdomen blunt; covered with spiniform setae. *Legs*: tibiae I and II with 3 pairs of macro-setae; metatarsi I and II with 6-7 pairs. *Epigynum*: orifices situated close together (Fig. 15a and b); sometimes completely covered with a brown mass, which makes it difficult to see the ori-

FIG. 15a-c

Thomisus kalaharinus Lawrence female/wyfie. (a and b). Epigynum, ventral view (variations)/Epigynum, ventrale aansig (variasies). (c). Internal genitalia, dorsal view/Inwendige genitalie, dorsale aansig

fices. Internal genitalia shown in Fig. 15c.

Male. Unknown.

Juvenile. Similar to female.

SYNONYMY AND RELATIONSHIP

Lawrence (1936) described *T. kalaharinus* from Botswana and in 1942 *T. urbensis* from Pietermaritzburg. A critical examination of the type-material of both species (borrowed from the T.M. and N.M. respectively) indicated that the epigyna of the two species are very similar. In both species the orifices are surrounded by a dark mass, but under strong light the orifices as drawn in Fig. 14a are readily distinguishable. I am of the opinion that these two taxa are conspecific.

T. kalaharinus is morphologically closest to *T. stenningi*, *T. australis* and *T. dalmasi*.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Tsotsoroga Pan, Botswana (18° 44'S, 24° 21'E), ♀ (T.M. 5918).

Type-locality of synonym: *T. urbensis* Pietermaritzburg, Natal, South Africa (29° 38'S, 30° 28'E), ♀ (N.M. 2194).

DISTRIBUTION

Botswana, South Africa (Natal).

New records: Ivory Coast, Central African Republic, Kenya, Rwanda, Burundi, Zaïre, Zambia, Zimbabwe, South Africa.

MATERIAL EXAMINED

IVORY COAST: Kossau, 20.v.1974, R. Jockué, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 151.850); 7.v.1975, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 149.805); Bouaké, ii.1963, G. Schmitz, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 126.154). CENTRAL AFRICAN REPUBLIC: Bambari, ii.1969, G. Pierrard, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 136.611). KENYA: Sankuri, 1956, R. Roiseux, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 862.38). RWANDA: Gabiro, vii-x.1946, R. Verhulst, 3 ♀, 3 juveniles (M.R.A.C. 149.574). BURUNDI: Ruzizi, 1968, S. Ndani, ♀, juvenile (M.R.A.C. 134.287). ZAÏRE: Tshuapa river, Bokungu, 1949 Dupvis, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 67359); Bukavu (Costermansville), 1951, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 69618); Kivu, Butembo, ix-x.1965, U. Celis, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 130.101); Mbandaka (Coquilhatville), 1959, R.P. Hulstaert, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 154.397); Kigali, A. Lestrade, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 81651); Lubumbashi, 8.vii. 1959, C. Leydel, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 154.403); Gangala, Doruma, 1959, A.B. Stam, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 114.282); Ituri river, Bunia, 1938, R.R. Maristes, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 1470); Mongwalu, v-vi.1939, M. Lepersonne, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 4171); Shaba, Luiswishi, xii.1976, F. Malaisse, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 151.528); Poko, vii.1959, U. Peckeur, 2 ♀ (M.R.A.C. 1181416); Bambesa, 16.ix.1934, J.M. Vrijdagh, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 20801); Bokuma, vii.1952, P. Lootens,

3 ♀ (M.R.A.C. 80868 and 7381811); Rutshuru, v. 1936, L. Lippens, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 20846); Kasongo, iii.1960, P.L.G. Benoit, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 120.379); Jadotville, x.1956, Z. Baeq, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 90376), iii. 1957, A. de Decker, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 97108); 1948, R. Adelaide, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 57924). ZAMBIA: Lusaka, ii-iii.1978, R. Stjernstedt, 2 ♀ (M.R.A.C. 151.935 and 151.937). ZIMBABWE: Matsheumhlope, Bulawayo, 23.x.1979, C.A. Car, 4 ♀, juveniles (N.M.B. A0009 and A0036); Bulawayo, xi.1963, ♀ (N.M.B.); Bulawayo, 17.v.1980, C. Car, ♀ (N.M.B. A774); Salisbury, 2.v.1973, G. Bell, ♀ (N.M.B.). BOTSWANA: Tsotsoronga Pan, R.F. Lawrence, ♀ (T.M. 5919). SOUTH WEST AFRICA: Kabulabula, ♀ (T.M. 5950), SOUTH AFRICA: Natal: Margate, 23.iv.1977, C.J. Cilliers, juveniles (N.C.A. 77/775); La Mercy, North Coast, 23.i.1980, C.J. Cilliers, juveniles (N.C.A. 80/56); Ntabanana, Zululand, H. Curson, ♀ (N.M.); Mapeleen Coastal Dune Forest, 1.v.1977, P. Reavell, ♀ (N.C.A. 78/193); Ngoye forest, 1.xii.1976, P. Reavell, ♀ (N.C.A. 78/167); Lake Sibayi, vi.1967, R.F. Lawrence, ♀ (A.M.); Sodwana Bay, 6.v.1981, C. Car, ♀ (S.A.M. C506); Pietermaritzburg, iv.1938, R. Veysly, ♀ (N.M. 2194); Manderston, iv.1963, H. Bustin, ♀ (N.M. 8865). Transvaal: Pretoria, 28.ix.1978, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/340); Pretoria, 15.i.1980, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 80/212); Pretoria, 20.ix.1978, B. Fourie, ♀ (N.C.A. 80/214); Pretoria, 12.x.1977, D. Uys, ♀ (N.C.A. 77/1065); Pretoria, viii.1976, H. Bence, ♀ (N.C.A. 76/1535); Pretoria, 2.iii.1972, M.E. Coetzer, ♀ (T.M.); Pretoria North, 10.vii.1974, ♀ (N.C.A. 76/1759); Waverley, Pretoria, 22.v.1975, E. Theron, ♀ (N.C.A. 76/1586); Roodeplaat, 18.xi.1971, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 77/853); Roodeplaat, i.1970, T. Coates, ♀ (A.M.); Hartebeespoortdam, 10.iii.1966, ♀ (N.C.A. 76/1284); Witbank, xii.1966, P. Luus, ♀ (N.C.A. 76/1290); Bronkhorstspuit, 12.ii.1967, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 76/1294); Komatipoort, 2 ♀ (A.M.); Groblersdal, 19.iv.1979, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 80/213). Cape Province: Kleinmond, 27.ix.1977, S. Nesor, juvenile (N.C.A. 78/70); Dasielkrans, Grahamstown, xii.1969, R.F. Lawrence, ♀ (A.M.). Orange Free State: Oranjeville, 5.iv.1981, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 81/74).

BIONOMICS

The females were collected throughout the year but most were found during November and January. They have been collected mainly from flowers and grass and on several occasions in strawberry lands.

Thomisus stenningi Pocock, Fig. 16a-d

Thomisus stenningi Pocock, 1900: 332; Strand, 1907c: 109; Comellini, 1957: 29; 1959: 119.

Thomisus weberi De Lessert, 1923: 174; 1928: 319; 1933: 118; 1936: 258; Millot, 1941: 44; Comellini, 1957: 32; 1959: 119, syn. nov.

DESCRIPTION

Female: Size (n=10): TL 5,3 (4,6-6,0); CL 2,1 (1,7-2,6); CW 2,3 (2,0-2,6); CI 0,9.

Colour: *T. stenningi* can change colour, body colour usually white or yellow, an occasional specimen with pink patches over entire body; carapace sometimes with two broad brown bands mediolaterally; eye area and cephalic region suffused with white; abdomen and legs similar in colour to carapace; tubercles on abdomen sometimes with a black spot.

Carapace: as wide as long, cephalic region raised; eye tubercles not sharply pointed; both eye rows recurved; posterior eyes smaller than anterior eyes, anterior eyes equal in size; AME nearer to each other than to ALE; posterior eyes equal in size; PME nearer to PLE than to each other. Abdomen wider than long with two blunt tubercles. Legs: dorsally with a few long setae; tibiae I and II with 3 pairs of macro-setae and metatarsi I and II with 5-6 pairs.

Integument: body and legs covered with numerous short setae. *Epigynum*: two circular pits with median septum (Fig. 16d); spermathecae shown in Fig. 16c.

Male. Size (n=10): TL 2,8 (2,5-3,2); CL 1,3 (1,2-1,5); CW 1,5 (1,3-1,6); CI 0,9.

Colour: varies between individuals; body and legs fawn to off-white; carapace and legs occasionally decorated with red markings, which fade in alcohol.

Carapace: cephalic area elevated; eye tubercles pointed. Body clothed with strong spiniform setae. Tibiae and metatarsi I and II without strong macrosetae, clothed with long thin hairs. *Palp*: embolus short; palp distinctive in that patella bears an apophysis on the retrolateral side (Fig. 16a and b). This is the only African species with such an apophysis.

Juvenile. Very similar to females. It is difficult to distinguish juveniles of *T. kalaharinus* from those of *T. stenningi*.

FIG. 16a-d *Thomisus stenningi* Pocock. (a). Palp, tibial apophysis, retrolateral view/*Palp, tibiale apofieses, retrolaterale aansig.* (b). Palp, ventral view/*Palp, ventrale aansig.* (c). Internal genitalia, dorsal view/*Inwendige genitalieë, dorsale aansig.* (d). Epigynum, ventral view/*Epigynium, ventrale aansig.*

SYNONYMY AND RELATIONSHIPS

Numerous females which correspond with the description of *T. stenningi* were collected. Males collected with these females (occasionally on the body of the female) correspond with the description of *T. weberi* (De Lessert, 1923). As both the male of *T. stenningi* and the female of *T. weberi* were hitherto unknown, I consider *T. weberi* to be the male of *T. stenningi*, and therefore a synonym of the latter species.

T. stenningi is very similar to *T. onustus* in body shape and both species have the ability to change colour. The drawings of *T. onustus* (Levy, 1973: 126, Fig. 39-42) indicate that the two species differ in the shape of both the male and female genitalia. The shape of the embolus of the palp of *T. stenningi* is very similar to that of *T. boesenbergi* and *T. dalmasi*. However, it differs from them in the presence of the apophysis on the patella.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Pirie Bush (Pirie forest), King William's Town, Cape Province, South Africa (27° 27'E, 32° 35'S), ♀ (B.M.).

Type-locality of synonym: *T. weberi* Amatola Mountains, Hogsback, Cape Province, South Africa (27° 05'E, 32° 35'S), ♂ (according to De Lessert, ♂-holotype is housed in the A.M. but I could not locate it in that collection).

DISTRIBUTION

South Africa (Natal, Cape Province), Zaïre, Kenya, Angola, Guinea.

New records: Uganda, Zambia, Lesotho, Zimbabwe, South Africa (Orange Free State, Transvaal).

MATERIAL EXAMINED

ZAÏRE: Ngombe, 5.xi.1927, H. Schoutedeni, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 155.33). UGANDA: Kasai, Kampala, 27.viii.1971, C. Massin, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 139.510). ZAMBIA: Lusaka, ii.1978, R. Stjernerstedt, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 151.937). LESOTHO: 5 km N. Nasaret Mission Station, 24.iii.1951, ♂, ♀, juveniles (swe. exp. A.M.); Maseru, 1951, ♂, ♀ (swe. exp. A.M.). ZIMBABWE: Umtali, Palgrave, Greenside, 20.xi.1965, ♂ (N.M.B. UM 15319). SOUTH AFRICA: *Transvaal*: Johannesburg 5.iii.1966, P. Brits, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/375); Brits, xi.1975, A.S. Dippenaar, 2 ♂ (N.C.A. 76/1658); Rust de Winter, 6.xii.1971, L. Pretorius, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/374); Bronkhorstspuit, 26.ii.1978, N.J. Dippenaar, ♂, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/327); Heidelberg Nature Reserve, 14.ii.1979, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/153); Pretoria 5.ix.1978, B. Fourie, 2 ♂ (N.C.A. 79/371); Zeerust 30.iii.1975, J. Oosthuizen, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/91); Levubu, 28.iii.1973, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/356); Roodeplaat, 1972, A.S. Dippenaar, 2 ♂ (N.C.A. 76/496); Enkeldoorn, near Molotto, 6.viii.1974, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 76/300); Piet Retief, xii.1976, L. Klingenberg, ♀ (N.C.A. 76/2003); Potchef-

stroom, xi.1965, P. Ryke, ♀ (N.M. 9501); Kensington, xii.1973, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 76/1596); Springs, 27.ii.1965, 2 ♀ (swe. exp. A.M.); Dendron, 5.vi.1967, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 76/1283). *Orange Free State*: Reddersburg, 8.i.1979, C. Kok, 2 ♂ (N.C.A. 79/69). *Natal*: Margate, 8.v.1979, C.J. Cilliers, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/246); Makatini Flats, 5.v.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, 2 ♂ (N.C.A. 79/370); Dukuduku, 29.iii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 77/650); Loteni Nature Reserve, 25.xii.1979, E. van den Berg, 2 ♀, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/383), *Cape Province*: Knysna, Diepwalle, Forest Reserve, 14.vi.1976, N.J. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 76/933); Mountain Zebra National Park near Cradock, 23.iii.1976, A.S. Dippenaar, 2 ♂ (N.C.A. 76/600); 12 km N Komgha, 1.xii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 77/1205); Stellenbosch, 1973, M. Volschenk, ♂ (N.C.A. 77/814); Hermanus, 21.xii.1950, 2 ♂ (swe. exp. A.M.); Fort Grey, East London, 2.xii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 77/1197); Ladysmith, 1.xii.1977, S. Nesor, ♂ (N.C.A. 78/381); Jessievale, Warburton, 8.iii.1978, N.J. van Rensburg, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/361); Keiskamma River, 5.xii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 78/47); Elsenburg, 14.ii.1972, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 76/808); Jeffreys Bay, 25.iii.1978, S. Stiemie, ♂ (N.C.A. 78/416); Humansdorp, De Vaselot Nature Reserve, 24.v.1978, N.J. Dippenaar, 2 ♂ (N.C.A. 78/566); Addo Elephant National Park, 14.ii.1974, M.K.P. Meyer, ♂ (N.C.A. 76/1954); Stellenbosch, 30.v.1975, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 76/171); 20 km ENE Bredasdorp, 1.i.1951, ♀ (swe. exp. A.M.); Somerset West, 29.viii.1979, S. Nesor, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/357); Dassiékran, Grahamstown, xii.1969, R.F. Lawrence, ♀ (A.M.); East London Pineapple Research Station, 29.ix.1978, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/342); Tsitsikamma, 13.i.1951, ♀ (swe. exp. A.M.); Herold, 25.xi.1977, S. Nesor, ♀ (N.C.A. 78/389); Storms River, 25.xi.1977, S. Nesor, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/334); Port Alfred, 7.ii.1968, A. Capener, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/351); Plettenberg Bay, 16.i.1979, C. Kok, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/85).

BIONOMICS

Adults were collected throughout the year, i.e. including winter. Their numbers were the highest from October to March. Specimens of this species were frequently collected from flowers. Some were also collected from grass and crops such as strawberries, cotton and lucerne.

The females are able to change their colour from white to yellow and occasionally some freshly caught specimens have a pink tint.

Thomisus australis Comellini, Fig. 17a-e

Thomisus australis Comellini, 1957: 6; 1959: 112.

Thomisus drakensbergensis Comellini, 1959: 114, syn. nov.

Thomisus mossambicus Comellini, 1957: 20, syn. nov.

Thomisus mossambicus weidneri Comellini, 1957: 20, syn. nov.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size (n=10): TL 6,5 (5,2-8,2); CL 2,6 (2,2-3,2); CW 2,7 (2,2-2,8); CI 1,0.

Colour: carapace yellowish, cephalic area white; brown triangular pattern between anterior eyes as viewed from the front. Abdomen yellow. *Legs:* dorsolateral side of front legs suffused with white; tarsi of front legs reddish brown.

Carapace: as wide as long; cephalic region slightly elevated; eye tubercle blunt, anterior eye row recurved; posterior row almost straight; anterior eyes same size; slightly larger than posterior eyes; AME nearer to each other than to ALE; posterior eyes equal in size; PME slightly nearer to PLE than to each other. *Abdomen:* bell-shaped and tubercles of moderate length. *Legs:* femora I and II with a few macro-setae dorsally; tibiae I and II with 3-4 pairs of macro-setae and metatarsi I and II with 6-7 pairs. *Integument:* carapace clothed with numerous short spiniform setae; abdomen clothed with spiniform setae that are of moderate length, arranged in rows; legs with short spiniform setae. *Epigynum:* large and horseshoe-shaped (Fig. 17d), sclerotized. Varies a little in shape between individuals (see Comellini, 1959: 112, Fig. 1 and 2 and p. 114, Fig. 7 and 8); not sclerotized in immature specimens (Fig. 17c). *Spermathecae* as shown in Fig. 17e.

Male. Size (n=8): TL 3,0 (2,8-3,2); CL 1,4 (1,3-1,5); CW 1,5 (1,4-1,5); CI 1,0.

Carapace and *abdomen* more flattened than those of female; *abdomen* ovate; clothed with numerous dark spiniform setae dorsally with a few faint white markings on integument; macro-setae on the tibiae and metatarsi of legs I and II reduced, the segments covered instead with long, thin hairs. *Palp:* embolus short and thick (Fig. 17a); RTA long; on retrolateral side of tibia a dark tubercle and seta as shown in Fig. 17b.

Juvenile. Similar to female, body yellow and triangle between eyes brown. Horseshoe-shaped epigynum, already discernable in immature females (Fig. 17c).

SYNONYMY AND RELATIONSHIPS

Comellini (1957) described *T. australis* from two males collected at Champagne Castle, Drakensberg Mountains. Comellini (1959) recorded a female from the same locality and considered it to be the female of *T. australis*. He (1959) also described *T. drakensbergensis* on the basis of three females from Champagne Castle. Mr P. Croeser collected a male and female, which were mating (N.C.A. 79/380) at Hogsback in the Amatola Mountains. In comparing these specimens with the type-material of *T. australis* and *T. drakensbergensis*, I found that the male corresponds with those of *T. australis* and the female with those of *T. drakensbergensis*. Additional material indicated that the specimens described as the female of *T. australis* are immature, while *T. drakensbergensis* is in fact the female of *T. australis*.

Comellini (1957) described *T. mossambicus* on the basis of one female from Moçambique. He also

named *T. mossambicus weidneri*, a new subspecies from Johannesburg. The holotype of *T. mossambicus* was not available for study but I compared identified material of *T. mossambicus* from the B.M., and the type-material of *T. mossambicus weidneri* (Z.M.H.), with the type-material of *T. australis*. The epigynum of *T. mossambicus* differs only slightly from that of *T. australis* in being somewhat more darkly sclerotized. However, the epigynum of *T. mossambicus* falls within the range of variation of that of *T. australis* and I therefore regard the former species and *T.m. weidneri* as synonyms of *T. australis*.

T. australis bears a close resemblance to *T. dalmasi*, *T. stenningi* and *T. kalaharinus* in size, shape and colour but differs from them in the shape of the genitalia.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Champagne Castle, Drakensberg Mountains, Natal (29° 10' S, 29° 28' E), ♂ (M. 5689).

Type-localities of synonyms: *T. drakensbergensis* same locality as given above for *T. australis*, ♀ [N.M. 6996, accession number given by Comellini (1959) as N.M. 6968]. *T. mossambicus* Shilowana, Moçambique [I could not trace Shilowana on the map of Moçambique but only a Shilowa in the Kruger National Park, picket on the Moçambique border (23° 28' S, 31° 34' E), ♀ (M.N.H.G.)]. *T. mossambicus weidneri* Johannesburg, Transvaal, South-Africa (26° 15' S, 28° 04' E), ♀ (Z.M.H.).

DISTRIBUTION

South Africa (Natal, Transvaal), Moçambique.

New records: Tanzania, Burundi, Zaïre, Malawi, South Africa (Cape Province), Lesotho.

MATERIAL EXAMINED

TANZANIA: Mazumbai, W. Usambara Mountains, v.1969, K.M. Howell, immature ♀ (M.R.A.C. 147.251). **BURUNDI:** Kitega, 4.iii.1953, P. Basilevsky, immature ♀ (M.R.A.C. 75130). **ZAÏRE:** Kivu, Kasongwere, iv.1970, R.P.M. Lejeune, 3 immature ♀ (M.R.A.C. 137.585); Kivu, Handa, 1952, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 74638). **MA-LAWI:** Viphya Mt, Chikangawa, iii-iv.1978, R. Jocqué, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 153.651). **LESOTHO:** Maseru, 8.x.1907, Dr Maclean, ♀ (B.M.07.10.8.4-15). **SOUTH AFRICA:** *Natal:* Champagne Castle Hotel, Drakensberg Mountains, i.1958, R.F. Lawrence, ♂-holotype (N.M. 5689), 4 juveniles (N.M. 5690); from the same locality ♀-holotype of *T. drakensbergensis* and ♀-allotype *T. australis* (N.M. 6968); Royal Natal National Park, 5.iv.1951, ♀ (swe. exp. A.M.); Loteni Nature Reserve, Drakensburg Mountains, 25.xii.1978, E. van den Berg, ♂, juveniles (N.C.A. 79/384); Estcourt, ♀ (swe. exp. A.M.). *Cape Province:* Rondebosch, 30.i.1951, ♀ (swe. exp. A.M.); Plettenberg Bay, 16.i.1979, C. Kok, 7 juveniles (N.C.A. 79/385); King William's Town, 20.i.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/335); The Crags, 28.ii.1977, S.

a

b

c

d

e

FIG. 17a-e

Thomisus australis Comellini. (a). Palp, ventral view/*Palp, ventrale aansig*. (b). Palp, tibial apophysis, retrolateral view/*Palp, tibiale apofieses, retrolaterale aansig*. (c). Immature female epigynum, ventral view/*Onvolwasse wyfie, epigynium, ventrale aansig*. (d). Epigynum, ventral view/*Epigynium, ventrale aansig*. (e). Internal genitalia, dorsal view/*Inwendige genitalieë, dorsale aansig*

Neser, ♂ (N.C.A. 78/380); Pineapple Research Station, East London, 7.xii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 78/378); Hogsback, near Alice in the Amatola Mountains, 2-25.iii.1978, P. Croeser, ♀, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/380); Knysna, 15.iv.1980, N. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 81/349). *Transvaal*: Johannesburg, 5.iii.1903, A. Lippert, ♀-holotype, ♀-paratype (*T. mossambicus weidneri*) (Z.M.H.); Sabie Forestry Station, 30.iv.1979, N. van Rensburg, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/251); Smitsdrift, Pietersburg, ♀ (swe. exp. A.M.); Blyde River Canyon, 23.ii.1978, E. Ueckermann, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/367); Jessievale, Warburton, 8.iii.1978, N. van Rensburg, 3 ♂ (N.C.A. 79/362 and 363); Sabie, 20.ii.1978, E. van den Berg, 2 ♀ (N.C.A. 78/215); Magoebaskloof, 7.iv.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/379); Graskop, iii.1960, R.F. Lawrence, 3 ♀, ♂ (N.M. 7476). *LESOTHO*: 3 km Pachus Neck, 7.iii.1951, 2 ♀, ♂ (swe. exp. A.M.).

BIONOMICS

Females were collected from December to April and males from November to March, mainly from grass and flowers.

Thomisus dalmasi De Lessert, Fig. 18a-d

Thomisus dalmasi De Lessert, 1919:119; Comellini, 1957:10.

Thomisus dalmasoides Millot, 1941: 47; Comellini, 1957:10.

Thomisus anthobioides Lawrence, 1942: 154; Comellini, 1957: 4, syn. nov.

Thomisus anthobioides mongbwalensis Comellini, 1957: 4, syn. nov.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size (n=10): TL 8,1 (7,1-9,4); CL 3,7 (3,1-4,1); CW 3,6 (2,8-4,1); CI 1,0.

Colour: body and legs pale yellow; carapace with chelicerae and clypeus ivory-white.

Carapace: as wide as long; both eye rows recurved; AME slightly larger than ALE; AME nearer to each other than to ALE. PME slightly smaller than PLE; PME nearer to each other than to PLE; eye tubercles directed more laterad than dorsad. Abdomen pentagonal; weakly developed tubercles on abdomen. Legs: tibia I and II with 3 pairs of macro-setae; metatarsi I and II with 5-6 pairs. Integument: smooth with few short setae. Epigynum: two blackish rounded pits (Fig. 18b); spermathecae as shown in Fig. 18a.

Male. Size (n=9): TL 2,5 (2,3-2,7); CL 1,2 (1,0-1,2); CW 1,2 (1,1-1,3); CI 0,9.

Colour: body yellowish brown; carapace a little darker than the rest of body; with two brown lines mediolaterally; eye area white. Abdomen occasionally with faint white markings. Legs similar in colour to carapace with the following exceptions; patellae, tibiae and metatarsi I and II darker than rest; tibiae faintly banded. In freshly caught specimens the legs are greenish with reddish brown bands and the abdomen is reddish brown on the anterolateral side.

Carapace: eye tubercles strongly pointed; integument clothed with numerous long and spiniform setae; primary setae C₂ and S₁ very distinct. Abdomen ovate; clothed with long spiniform setae dorsally. Legs I-IV with setae on femora, patellae and tibiae dorsally; tibiae and metatarsi I and II without macro-setae, but clothed with numerous long hairs. Palp: embolus short (Fig. 18d), on the retrolateral side of VTA a sharp, strongly pointed tubercle; a strong black seta is situated close to the tubercle (Fig. 18c).

Juvenile. Similar to females, primary setae C₁ and S₁ prominent. Tubercles in abdomen sometimes with a red spot.

a

b

FIG. 18a-b

Thomisus dalmasi De Lessert. (a). Internal genitalia, dorsal view/*Inwendige genitalieë, dorsale aansig*. (b). Epigynum, ventral view/*Epigynium, ventrale aansig*

FIG. 18c-d (c). Palp, tibial apophysis, retrolateral view/Palp, tibiale apofieses, retrolaterale aansig. (d). Palp, ventral view/Palp, ventrale aansig

SYNONYMY AND RELATIONSHIPS

Immature specimens and females collected together with males of *T. dalmasi* correspond with the females of *T. anthobioides*. As the female of *T. dalmasi* was hitherto unknown, I consider *T. anthobioides* the female of *T. dalmasi*, and therefore synonymous with the latter species.

Comellini (1957) named a new subspecies *T. anthobioides mongbwalensis* which differs from the nominate subspecies in the shape of the eye tubercles and body colour. I compared the type-material of *T. a. mongbwalensis* (M.R.A.C. 1869) with the type and other specimens of *T. anthobioides* (N.M. 2924) but could not support its subspecies status.

The colour and shape of the body of *T. dalmasi* are very similar to those of *T. australis*, *T. stenningi* and *T. kalaharinus*, but it can easily be distinguished from them by the shape of the genitalia. The epigynum of *T. dalmasi* is similar to that of *T. hararinus* (Di Caporiacco, 1947a); however, the holotype of the latter species was not available for detailed comparisons.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Kibonoto, Kilimanjaro. It is likely that Kibonoto is a misspelling of Kibongoto in the south-western foothills of Mt Kilimanjaro, Moshi District, Tanzania (03° 12'S, 37° 07'E), ♂(M.N.H.G.).

Type-locality of synonyms: *T. dalmasoides* Dalaba, Guinea, West Africa 10° 33'N, 12° 25'W), ♂ (M.N.H.P.). *T. anthobioides* Umhlali, North Coast, Natal, South Africa (29° 28'S, 31° 28'E), ♀ (N.M. 2924). *T. an-*

thobioides mongbwalensis Mongbwalu, Zaïre (01° 56'N, 30° 03'E), ♀ (M.R.A.C. 1869).

DISTRIBUTION

Tanzania, Guinea, Zaïre, South Africa (Natal).

New records: Cameroun, Rwanda, Mocambique.

MATERIAL EXAMINED

ZAIËRE (Mongbwalu, 1938, Scheitz, ♀-holotype (*T. anthobioides mongbwalensis*) (M.R.A.C. 1869); Bunia, 1937, R.R. Maristes, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 20695); Kivu, Lubere, iv.1969, M. Lejeune, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 136.207); Kivu, Kambaila, vi.1973, M. Lejeune, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 145.780); Kivu, Kibati, 1953, J. Heeg, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 781067); Kivu, Handa, 1952, Vandellanotte, 4 ♀ (M.R.A.C. 78509, 788193 and 788182); Kivu, Butembo, v.1967, R. Lejeune, 5♀ (M.R.A.C. 140.861, 132.805 and 132.818); Djugu, v.1977, Bzedo, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 213.51). CAMEROUN: Buea, 2.ix.1968, J. van Mol, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 135.325); Bakossi, 10.iii.1913, Comellini, ♀ (Z.M.H.). RWANDA: Kisenyi (Gisenyi), 13.ii.1953, P. Basilensky, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 75298); Butare (=Astrida), ii-vii.1971, P. Nyalugaka, 4 ♀ (M.R.A.C. 139.073 and 140.701), 22.x.1952, R. Laurent, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 85129), 20.vi.1979, A. Vandenberghe, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 152.012); Kisenyi (Gisenyi), 13.ii.1953, P. Basilensky, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 75294). MOÇAMBIQUE: Gorondoza Mts (800 m), ix.1951, 4 ♂ (N.M. 6935). SOUTH AFRICA: Natal: Umhlali, North Coast, ii.1940,

R.F. Lawrence, ♀-holotype, (N.M. 2924); Mape-laan (dune forest), 1.v.1977, P. Reavell, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/336); Empangeni, 25.x.1977, P. Reavell, ♀ (N.C.A. 78/185); Margate, 8.v.1979, C.J. Cilliers, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/368), 8.vi.1977, ♂ (N.C.A. 77/969).

BIONOMICS

Females were collected almost throughout the year.

Thomisus congoensis Comellini, Fig. 19 a-b

Thomisus congoensis Comellini, 1957: 9.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Unknown.

Male. Size (n=4): TL 2,5 (2,2-2,6); CL 1,3 (1,2-1,3); CW 1,3 (1,2-1,3); CI 1,0.

Colour: carapace pale brown with abdomen yellow; leg I dark brown except tarsus which is yellow; leg II dark brown except coxa, trochanter and basal half of femur and tarsus which are yellow; joints between segments of all legs white.

Carapace: eye tubercles sharply pointed; both eye rows slightly recurved; anterior eyes larger than posterior eyes; anterior eyes equal in size; AME nearer to ALE than to each other; PME slightly smaller than PLE; PME nearer to PLE than to each other. Legs I and II without macro-setae. Integument: body covered with small tubercles, each tu-

bercle provided with a short, stout erect seta. Palp: RTA broad; small tubercles on retrolateral side of tibia, at base of RTA each provided with a long thin seta (Fig. 19a-b); these setae are easily lost (not present on drawing of ♂-holotype, Comellini, 1957: 9).

Juvenile. Unknown.

RELATIONSHIPS

This species was hitherto known only from the holotype. The palp is similar to that of *T. machadoi* but the two species differ in the shape of the embolus and RTA. The eye tubercles are more pointed in *T. congoensis* and with more setae on body.

TYPE-LOCALITY

The type-locality is given only as Zaïre by the collector, De Lessert. The holotype is housed in the M.N.H.G.

DISTRIBUTION

Zaïre.

New records: South Africa (Transvaal).

MATERIAL EXAMINED

SOUTH AFRICA: Transvaal: Naboomspruit, Nylsvley, xii.1977, G. Ferreira, ♂ (N.C.A. 78/525); Rust de Winter, 10.v.1972, L. Pretorius, ♂ (N.C.A. 76/1706); farm Amsterdam, 17 km NE Dendron, 7.i.1970, J. Viljoen, 2 ♂ (N.C.A. 77/846); Rustenburg Nature Reserve, 11.xii.1979, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 80/57).

FIG. 19a-b *Thomisus congoensis* Comellini male/mannetjie. (a). Palp, ventral view/Palp, ventrale aansig. (b). Tibial apophysis, retrolateral view/Tibiale apofiese, retrolaterale aansig

BIONOMICS

Males were collected from trees, grass and on cotton during December, January and May.

Thomisus machadoi Comellini, Fig. 20 a-b

Thomisus machadoi Comellini, 1959: 117.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Unknown.

Male. Size (n=1): TL 3,2; CL 2,1; CW 2,1; CI 1,0.

Colour: carapace brown; eye area slightly paler; abdomen a pale brown; lateral sides a darker brown; legs I-IV brown with legs I and II darker than rest; metatarsi and tibiae I and II slightly banded.

Carapace: elevated; eye tubercles not sharply pointed; directed slightly dorsad; anterior eyes larger than posterior eyes. Abdomen bell-shaped. Tibiae and metatarsi I and II with long, thin macrosetae. Integument: body clothed with short setae, less numerous than in *T. congoensis*. Palp: tip of RTA rounded, near tip a small tubercle (Fig. 20a and b); retrolateral side of tibia covered with small tubercles, each provided with a hair. Tubercles larger than those of *T. congoensis*.

Juvenile. Unknown.

RELATIONSHIPS

Closely related to *T. congoensis*.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Angola, Mocamedes (15° 20'S, 12° 11'E), ♂-holotype (Museum de Dundo 19554).

DISTRIBUTION

Angola.

New records: Cape Verde Islands, South Africa (Transvaal).

MATERIAL EXAMINED

CAPE VERDE: Brava, 1959, L. Pequeno, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 131.151). SOUTH AFRICA: *Transvaal*: farm Amsterdam, 17 km NE Dendron, district Soutpansberg, 7.i.1970, J. Viljoen, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/373).

BIONOMICS

A poorly known and collected species. The male from Transvaal was collected in January by means of a suction trap.

SPECIES INCERTAE SEDIS

Thomisus hottentotus Strand

Thomisus hottentotus Strand, 1907a: 538; 1907b: 656; Roewer, 1954: 859; Comellini, 1957: 14.

The holotype of this species (♀, collected in the Cape Province, no exact locality) is believed to have been deposited in the Museum of Natural History, Lübeck and destroyed during the Second World War. The species cannot be positively identified from the original description.

Thomisus lenzi Strand

Thomisus lenzi Strand, 1907a:538; 1907b:654.

The holotype (♀, collected in the Cape Province, no exact locality) also believed to have been deposited in the Museum of Natural History,

FIG. 20a-b

Thomisus machadoi Comellini male/mannetje. (a). Palp, ventral view/Palp, ventrale aansig. (b). Tibial apophysis, retrolateral view/Tibiale apofieses, retrolaterale aansig

Lübeck and destroyed during the Second World War.

RUNCINIA Simon, 1875

Runcinia Simon, 1875: 254; 1895: 1018; 1903b: 1012; 1932: 787, 789; Scudder, 1882: 282; Chyzer & Kulczynski, 1891: 81, 84; O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1900: 134, 140; Bösenberg, 1901: 17; 1902: 369; Planet, 1905: 170; Banks, 1905: 317; 1907: 732; Petrunkevitch, 1928: 170; Berland, 1929: 53; Levy, 1973: 107; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980: 303.

Runciniopsis Simon, 1881: 1; 1895: 1019; 1901: 21; 1903b: 1012. Type-species: *Runciniopsis flavida* Simon, 1881.

Machomenus Marx, 1893: 589; Simon 1903b: 1012.

Type-species: *Machomenus albidus* Marx, 1893.

Type-species: *Thomisus lateralis* Koch, 1838.

The genus *Runcinia* was redescribed by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1980). Eight species from southern Africa were recognized, of which six were new records for this area. In a collection of Araneae recently received from Mrs C. Car, formerly of the Bulawayo Museum, I have encountered a ninth species, from the Okavango Delta. This species is described here, and the key to the species is altered accordingly.

Runcinia as delimited by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1980) includes a group of spiders characterized by slightly flattened bodies with shapes which vary from triangular or oval to long and narrow and with the eyes situated on a carina.

Runcinia is most closely related to *Bonapruncinia*, a genus from St Helena described by Benoit (1977). The two genera differ only in the shape of the carina, the integument, and the type of setae present on the carapace. *Plancinus*, a genus from South America described by Simon (1886b) is according to him morphologically very similar to *Runcinia*. They differ only in the shape of the carina, which is angular and less prolonged in *Plancinus* with the median ocular quadrangle wider than long and narrower in front.

On the basis of the African material at hand, the genus *Runcinia* is defined as follows.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size: small to moderate-size (5,1-12,0 mm). Colour: body and legs fawn. Carapace with a white longitudinal line medially and two broad brown lines mediolaterally; edge of carapace sometimes with dark rim. Abdomen usually with two longitudinal lines mediolaterally or with transverse bands on the posterior striae; some species with distinct patterns.

Carapace: as wide as long or slightly longer, flattened above; anterior margin straight medially with two low tubercles (carinae) on each side; posterior margin concave; surface clothed with numerous short irregularly spaced setae, with a row of short

setae around edge of carapace; 1-3 pairs of primary setae usually present (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980). Eyes in two rows (Fig. 22a); anterior row on frontal slope, posterior row situated on dorsal side; lateral eyes situated on carina; both eye rows straight or slightly recurved; lateral eyes larger than median eyes; MOQ wider posteriorly than anteriorly. Clypeus vertical, with 1-4 pairs of long primary setae on margin. Sternum heart-shaped. Abdomen variable: triangular, oval, or long and narrow; truncated anteriorly; truncated, rounded or extending caudally posteriorly; abdomen with longitudinal striae that follow the contour of the abdomen; striae with rows of setae, differing in shape between species. Ventrally without striae, clothed with numerous short hairs. Legs covered with numerous short irregularly spaced setae varying in shape between species; anterior two pairs of legs longer and much stronger than posterior pairs; ventral surfaces of tibiae and metatarsi I and II with double row of long macrosetae, number varies between species. Epigynum small and simple, usually a rounded depression bordered by a thickened rim.

Male. Size: smaller than female. Colour largely as in female. The male differs structurally from the female as follows. Carapace more flattened; setae longer and more distinct, especially row round carapace margin. Abdomen oval, setae more prominent and spiniform in shape. Legs longer and thinner; macrosetae on tibiae and metatarsi I and II long and thin, covered with numerous long, thin and dark hairs. Palp with two tibial apophyses; VTA hook-like, RTA longer and thinner, extending almost half the length of tegulum.

Juvenile. Very similar to females in shape and colour.

DISTRIBUTION

Runcinia comprises 27 species with the following distribution (endemic species, based on type-localities): Afrotropical region (12), Palaearctic region (4), Oriental region (10), Australian region (1). Their distribution is restricted to the eastern hemisphere (Fig. 21).

In the Americas they are replaced according to Gertsch (1939) by a related group of species belonging to *Misumenoides* F. Pickard-Cambridge, and he is of the opinion that *Runcinia plana* Simon from Paraguay belongs somewhere else.

SPECIES FROM THE AFROTROPICAL REGION

Most of the species, endemic to this region, have a pan-African distribution (Appendix 2). Unfortunately most areas in this region are still poorly sampled. Millot (1941) believed *Runcinia erythrina* Jézéquel to have a very localized distribution in the Ivory Coast, but this species was found to occur throughout southern Africa. *R. lateralis* (Koch) known from the Palaearctic region, is now for the first time recorded from the Afrotropical region but

FIG. 21 Known geographical distribution of *Runcinia* Simon / Bekende geografiese verspreiding van *Runcinia* Simon

only from Cape Town and Hout Bay in the extreme south. It remains possible that this species was introduced by sea freight.

DISCUSSION

Morphological adaptations. *Runcinia* species display an interesting range of adaptations to their habitats. They have been collected primarily on grass, and most frequently on dry grass. Their colour is like that of dry grass with the darker longitudinal lines of the body resembling veins of grass blades.

Spiders of this genus typically sit with their bodies pressed close to the grass, with the first two pairs of legs pointing directly forward. This holds especially in those species with long abdomens, e.g. *R. flavida* (Simon) and *R. johnstoni* De Lessert. The species with more oval bodies are more frequently found in the inflorescence, on which they position their bodies, or between the seeds, with their front legs pointing forwards or sideways.

The movements of *Runcinia* species are sluggish and their bodies and front legs are usually kept very rigidly in a particular position. When resting the front legs are placed close to or on the substratum but when waiting for prey the front legs are pointed sideways. When disturbed they usually drop to the ground with their bodies and legs kept in this rigid position, still resembling a piece of grass or grass seed.

Biology. Very little is known about the biology of the species of *Runcinia*. *R. flavida* is by far the most common species of this genus in southern Af-

rica. It is a diurnal species found only on grass. Immature forms, which were collected in March, reached maturity after a year in captivity.

The following observations were made in captivity. Females are fertilized once. The chalk-white egg-sac is a convex, slightly flattened, lenticular object which consists of two discs which are held together on the margin with silk. It is fastened to grass by means of silk spun over the entire sac. The female spends most of her time on, or close to the egg-sac. One female constructed four egg-sacs after an initial fertilization. Spiderlings emerged after an average of 25 days with the number of young emerging per sac varying between 20 and 85. The young spiderlings are immediately positively phototropic. They readily fed on the red spider mite, *Tetranychus cinnabarinus* (Boisduval).

KEY TO THE SPECIES OF *RUNCINIA* FROM SOUTHERN AFRICA

- | | | |
|----|--|---|
| 1. | Abdomen long and narrow; carina directed anterad ... | 2 |
| - | Abdomen shorter, oval to triangular in shape; carina directed laterad | 3 |
| 2. | Abdomen long, truncated posteriorly | |
| - | Abdomen long, caudally extending past spinnerets, tail-like in appearance | |
| 3. | Setae S_1 (posterior to PLE) and A_4 (on posterior declivity) present on carapace; abdominal setae spiniform or club-shaped or alternating more or less regularly with spiniform setae | 4 |
| - | Setae S_1 present on carapace; abdominal setae club-shaped | 8 |
| 4. | Abdominal setae numerous, dark and spiniform; carapace convex; carina blunt | 5 |

- Abdominal setae club-shaped or alternating more or less regularly with spiniform setae; carapace more flattened; carina more sharply pointed.....
- 5. Legs long; setae S₁ very long and distinct; setae on abdomen long..... *carae* spec. nov.
- Legs not so long; setae S₁ not so long; setae on abdomen shorter..... *erythrina* Jézéquel
- 6. Body flattened; setae P₄ present on the tip of the carina; abdomen with patterns *depressa* Simon
- Body not flattened; setae P₄ absent; abdomen with dark longitudinal lines laterally.....
- 7. Striae on abdomen covered with club-shaped setae alternating more or less regularly with spiniform setae *tropica* (Simon)
- Striae on abdomen covered with long and short club-shaped setae *affinis* Simon

- 8. Abdomen triangular in shape; carapace, legs and abdomen mottled with black; setae S₁ spiniform; carina sharply pointed *aethiops* (Simon)
- 6. Abdomen oval; longer than wide; body without black mottling; setae S₁ short, club-shaped; carina blunt *lateralis* (Koch)

Runcinia flavida (Simon), Fig. 22b-d

7 *Runciniopsis flavida* Simon, 1881: 1; 1895: 1021, 1024.

Runcinia flavida Simon, 1909: 28; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980: 307.

a

b

c

d

FIG. 22a-d *Runcinia* sp. (a). Carapace, anterior view/*Karapaks, anterioraansig.* (b-d). *Runcinia flavida* (Simon). (b). Epigynum, ventral view/*Epigynium, ventrale aansig.* (c). Female, dorsal view/*Wyfie, dorsale aansig.* (d). Palp, ventral view/*Palp, ventrale aansig*

Runcinia (Runciniopsis) flavida (Simon): De Lessert, 1919: 191.

Runcinia (Runciniopsis) proxima De Lessert, 1919: 129; Millot, 1941: 41; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980: 307.

Runcinia proxima voltaensis Millot, 1941: 39; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980-307.

Runcinia littorina Lawrence, 1942: 157; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980: 307.

DESCRIPTION

This species can be distinguished from related species by the abdomen which is 3-4 times longer than wider (Fig.22c) and truncated anteriorly and posteriorly. The carina is directed anterad (Fig.22c). Epigynum small; central depression bordered by an elevated ridge; upper half convex in shape (Fig.22b). Male resembles female but differs as follows: tibiae and metatarsi I and II dark brown; abdomen darker in colour. Palp shown in Fig. 22d.

SYNONYMY AND RELATIONSHIP

Dippenaar-Schoeman (1980) synonymized *R. littorina*, *R. proxima*, *R.p. voltaensis* with *R. flavida*.

The only other species from southern Africa with a long abdomen is *R. johnstoni*, which is related to *R. flavida*. It differs from the latter in the abdo-

men which extends caudally past the spinnerets as well as in the shape of the genitalia.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Zanzibar, a small island off the coast of Tanzania (6° 0'S, 39° 17'E), 1 ♀ (M.N.H.P.).

Type-localities of synonyms: *R. littorina* Umhláli, North Coast of Natal, South Africa (29° 28'S, 31° 16'E), ♀ (N.M. 2439); *R. proxima* Ngare River, eastern part of Zambia (14° 39'S, 30° 25'E), ♀ (M.N.H.G.); *R. proxima voltaensis* Batié, Upper Volta (10° 15'S, 2° 20'E), ♂ (M.N.H.P.).

DISTRIBUTION

Zanzibar, Morocco, Senegal, Guinea, Dahomey, Upper Volta, Kenya, Zambia, Rwanda, Zimbabwe, South Africa.

NEW RECORDS

KENYA: Lake Nakuru, 19.xii.1979, P. Reavell, juveniles (N.C.A. 80/44). ZIMBABWE: Bulawayo, ii.1963, juveniles (N.M.B.); Kezi, 5.iv.1980, C.A. Car, 7 immature ♀ (N.M.B. A845). ZAIRE: Rutshuru, vi.1936, L. Lippens, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 20850).

FIG. 23a-c

Runcinia johnstoni De Lessert. (a). Abdomen of female, lateral view/Wyfie se abdomen, laterale aansig. (b). Epigynum, ventral view/Epigynium, ventrale aansig. (c). Palp, ventral view/Palp, ventrale aansig

Runcinia johnstoni De Lessert, Fig. 23a-c

Runcinia (Runciniopsis) johnstoni De Lessert, 1919: 127; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980: 310.

Runcinia (Runciniopsis) sjoestedti De Lessert, 1919: 131; Dippenaar-Schoeman 1980:310.

Runcinia sjoestedti De Lessert, 1928: 330; 1943: 330.

DESCRIPTION

Resembles *R. flavida*. Depressed dorsally; longer than wide. Carina directed anterad. Abdomen long and narrow; caudal extension reaching beyond the spinnerets (Fig. 23a). Epigynum with central depression bordered by an elevated ridge (Fig. 23b). Male resembles female rather closely. Palp very similar to *R. flavida*, only RTA a little longer and more sharply pointed (Fig. 23c).

SYNONYMY AND RELATIONSHIPS

Dippenaar-Schoeman (1980) synonymized *R. sjoestedti* with *R. johnstoni*.

Runcinia johnstoni resembles *R. flavida* in colour and shape but differs from it in the shape of the genitalia and the caudal end of the abdomen, which is not posteriorly truncated but extends past the spinnerets. The palp is similar to that of *R. flavida* but differs from it in having a longer retrolateral apophysis.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Kibonoto, Kilimanjaro. It is likely that Kibonoto is a misspelling of Kibongoto, the south-western foot of Kilimanjaro, Moshi district, Tanzania (03° 12'S, 37° 07'E), ♀ (M.N.H.G.).

Type-locality of synonyms: *R. sjoestedti*, collected from a place named Merou, Kilimanjaro. It is likely that Merou is a misspelling of Meru, a mountain west of Kilimanjaro, Tanzania (3° 15'S, 36° 45'E), ♀, ♂ (M.N.H.G.).

DISTRIBUTION

Tanzania, Ivory Coast, Senegal, Zaïre, Zimbabwe, South Africa (Cape Province, Natal and Transvaal).

Runcinia carae spec. nov., Fig. 24a-e

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size: measurements of holotype [range of paratypes (n=4) in parentheses]: TL 5,7 (5,8-6,4); CL 2,3 (2,1-2,3); CW 2,2 (2,0-2,2); CI 1,1; carina ant. 1,4 (1,2-1,4); carina post. 1,3 (1,2-1,4); carina index 1,1.

Colour: carapace fawn, eye area white; two brown lines mediolaterally, an indistinct white line medially. Sternum and coxae I almost brown. Abdomen cream to pale brown, with distinct brown and white patterns, which vary a little between individuals (Fig. 24a). Legs cream to fawn, I and II darker than III and IV; coxae and femora of legs I and II suffused with brown and mottled with dark brown and patellae and tibiae indistinctly banded.

Carapace: slightly longer than wide (CI 1.1); convex in shape with highest part in the thoracic area; carapace clothed with numerous irregularly spaced, spiniform setae; setae S_1 very long and spiniform; A_3 and A_4 present, shorter than S_1 but still very distinct. Carina slightly convex, index 1,1; clothed with sort setae. On clypeal margin C_{2-5} present, long and spiniform. Abdomen longer than wide, ovate (Fig. 24a); striae covered with numerous long and dark spiniform setae. Legs long, clothed with short setae; macro-setae on legs I and II long, tibiae with 4-5 pairs and metatarsi 7-8 pairs. Epigynum with central depression, a transparent hood present anteriorly, not so distinct as in *R. erythrina*, central area faintly embraced by two elevated ridges (Fig. 24c). Internal genitalia as shown in Fig. 24b.

Male. Size (n=3): TL 3,6 (3,2-4,2); CL 1,6 (1,4-1,7); CW 1,8 (1,7-1,9); CI 0,9; carina ant. 1,1 (1,0-1,1); carina post. 1,0 (1,0-1,1); carina index 1,0.

Resembles female closely: setae S_1 also very long and dark; carina slightly more convex (index 1,0); patterns on abdomen less distinct than in female; setae

FIG. 24a-b

Runcinia carae spec. nov. (a). Female, dorsal view/Wyfie, dorsale aansig. (b). Internal genitalia, dorsal view/Inwendige genitalieë, dorsale aansig

FIG. 24c-e (c). Epigynum, ventral view/*Epigynium, ventrale aansig*. (d). Palp, ventral view/*Palp, ventrale aansig*. (e). Palp, tibial apophysis, retrolateral view/*Palp, tibiale apofieses, retrolaterale aansig*

on striae very long and distinct; legs long and thin, covered with numerous hairs and setae, femora I-IV with 4-5 setae dorsally; macro-setae on tibiae and metatarsi of front legs very distinct; legs I and II darker than legs III and IV; the front pairs have the distal parts of the patellae darkly banded as well as the distal parts of the tibiae. Palp closely resembling that of *R. erythrina*, VTA typically hook-like (Fig. 24e); RTA longer than that of *R. erythrina*, tip slightly twisted (Fig. 24d).

RELATIONSHIPS

Closely related to *R. erythrina* but they differ as follows. *R. carae* is larger and more robust, with longer and thinner legs; setae S_1 and A_{3-4} on the carapace longer and more distinct; pattern on abdomen different; carapace elevated in thoracic area. The genitalia of the two species differ slightly.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Botswana, Okavango Delta 19° 03'S, 23° 10'E), ♀, ♂ (N.M.B. A756 and A915).

DISTRIBUTION

Botswana, Kenya.

MATERIAL EXAMINED

♀-holotype, 4 ♀ and 3 ♂-paratypes with the following collecting data. BOTSWANA: Okavango Delta, 9.xii.1975, National Museum Bulawayo, ♀-holotype and 1 ♂-paratype (N.M.B. A756); 3 ♂-paratypes collected from same locality, 3.iii.1975, 2 ♂ (N.M.B. A915), 1 ♂, (N.C.A. 80/320). KENYA: Lake Nakuru, 19.xii.1979, P. Reavell, 3 ♀-paratypes (N.C.A. 80/45). The types are deposited in the National Mu-

seum, Bulawayo, Zimbabwe and the National Arachnida Collection, Pretoria.

BIONOMICS

R. carae was obtained by sweep-netting grass. Mature forms were collected in November.

ETYMOLOGY

This species is named for Mrs Cathy Car, South African Museum, Cape Town.

Runcinia erythrina Jézéquel, Fig. 25a-d

Runcinia (Runciniopsis) erythrina Jézéquel, 1964: 1123; Blandin, 1972: 1281; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980: 312.

DESCRIPTION

Carapace fawn with two mediolateral lines present, reddish brown. Abdomen white to pale cream with distinct reddish brown patterns. Carapace clothed with numerous irregularly spaced, short spi-

niform setae; setae S_1 and A_{3-4} present, shorter than those of *R. carae*. Carina convex. Abdomen slightly longer than wide (Fig. 25b), oval in outline; striae covered with numerous long, spiniform setae (Fig. 25d). Epigynum with central depression partly covered with transparent hood (Fig. 25a). Male resembles female. Palp with RTA shorter than that of *R. carae* (Fig. 25c).

RELATIONSHIPS

Most closely related to *R. carae*, but differs from it and other African species of *Runcinia* in the convex carapace and blunt carina.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Lamto, Ivory Coast ($6^{\circ} 12'N$, $4^{\circ} 58'W$, 1 immature ♀ (M.N.H.P.)).

DISTRIBUTION

Ivory Coast, Zimbabwe, Kenya, South Africa (Transvaal, Orange Free State and Natal).

FIG. 25a-d *Runcinia erythrina* Jézéquel. (a). Epigynum, ventral view/Epigynium, ventrale aansig. (b). Female, dorsal view/Wyfie, dorsale aansig. (c). Palp, ventral view/Palp, ventrale aansig. (d). Abdominal setae/Abdominale seta

FIG. 26a-e *Runcinia depressa* Simon. (a). Female, dorsal view/Wyfie, dorsale aansig. (b). Palp, ventral view/Palp, ventrale aansig. (c). Male, abdominal setae/Mannetjie, abdominale seta. (d). Female, abdominal setae/Wyfie, abdominale seta. (e). Epigynum, ventral view/Epigynium, ventrale aansig

NEW RECORDS

KENYA: Lake Nakuru, 19.xii.1979, P. Reavell, 2 ♀ (N.C.A. 80/45). RWANDA: Gabiro, vii-x.1946, R. Verhulst, 2 ♀ (M.R.A.C. 149.563).

Runcinia depressa Simon, Fig. 26a-e

Runcinia depressa Simon, 1906: 1166; 1910: 195; De Lessert, 1919: 123; 1928: 320; Millot, 1941: 39; Di Caporiacco, 1949: 458; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980: 314.

DESCRIPTION

Carapace flattened, yellowish brown with a dark line round margin of carapace, setae S_1 and A_4 present, short and spiniform (Fig. 26a). Abdomen oval to slightly elongated; striae covered with spiniform and club-shaped setae, alternating more or less regularly (Fig. 26d). Epigynum shown in Fig. 26e. Male similar to female except tarsi I and II, and distal part of tibiae I and II dark brown. Striae on abdomen with rows of short and longer club-shaped setae alternating (Fig.

26c). Palp with VTA short, RTA broad at base curved slightly outwards apically (Fig. 26b).

RELATIONSHIPS

Most closely related to *R. tropica* and *R. affinis*. *R. depressa* can be distinguished from all African species by its flattened body and the spiniform and club-shaped setae on the abdomen.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Mongalla, Sudan, on the banks of the white Nile ($5^{\circ} 10'N$, $32^{\circ} 50'E$), ♀ (M.N.H.P.).

DISTRIBUTION

Sudan, Morocco, Egypt, Ivory Coast, Algeria, Kenya, Zaïre, Zambia, Botswana, South Africa (Transvaal, Natal and Cape Province).

NEW RECORDS

ZAIËRE: Bibwango, 24.iii.1964, A. Fain, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 126572).

Runcinia tropica Simon, Fig. 27a-b

Runcinia affinis tropica Simon, 1907: 316; De Lessert, 1915: 37; 1919: 123; 1933: 118; Lawrence, 1947: 26; Di Caporaicco, 1949: 458.

Runcinia tropica Simon, Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980: 316.

DESCRIPTION

Carapace clothed with short club-shaped setae, setae S_1 and A_4 present, long and spiniform. Abdomen oval (Fig. 27b); striae provided with long transparent spiniform setae interspersed by shorter, club-shaped setae, similar to those of *R. depressa*. Epigynum (Fig. 27a) very similar to that of *R. depressa* but a little longer than wide in *R. tropica*. Male palp is illustrated by De Lessert (1919) showing a sharply pointed, slightly outwardly directed RTA with the LTA typically hook-like.

SYNONYMY AND RELATIONSHIP

Simon (1907) described *R. affinis tropica* as a

subspecies of *R. affinis*, a difference based only on size and colour. Dippenaar-Schoeman (1980), however, recognized *R. tropica* as a distinct species because *R. tropica* can be separated from *R. affinis* by the shape of both the external and internal genitalia and by the difference in the shape of the abdominal setae.

R. tropica is related to *R. depressa* but can be easily separated from the latter by the shape of the internal genitalia and the unflattened body.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Annobon, a small island off the West Coast of Africa, in the Gulf of Guinea ($1^{\circ} 35'S$, $5^{\circ} 35'E$), ♀, ♂ (M.N.H.P.).

DISTRIBUTION

Annobon, Zaïre, Kenya, Tanzania, Angola, South Africa (Natal), Cabinda, South West Africa, Rwanda, Sao Thomé.

FIG. 27a-b *Runcinia tropica* (Simon). (a). Epigynum, ventral view/*Epigynium, ventrale aansig*. (b). Female, dorsal view/*Wyfie, dorsale aansig*

NEW RECORDS

RWANDA: Kisenyi, ix.1951, E. Bertrand, 1 immature ♂ (M.R.A.C. 70090). SAO THOMÉ: 8-10.x.1973, G. Schmitz, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 147.694).

Runcinia affinis Simon, Fig. 28a-c

Runcinia affinis Simon, 1897b: 289, 292; 1903a: 96; 1906: 1166; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980: 317.

Runcinia cataracta Lawrence, 1927: 36; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980: 317.

DESCRIPTION

Setae S_5 and A_4 present on carapace, of medium length and spiniform. Abdomen longer than wide, ovate (Fig. 28b); abdominal striae clothed with club-shaped setae, interspersed with longer setae of the same shape. Epigynum small; a small depression situated centrally; anterior partly covered by a cone-shaped hood (Fig. 27a). Male resembles the female, but differs in the following. Carapace somewhat flattened, with a row of short setae very prominent bordering the carapace edge. Male palp illustrated in Fig. 28c.

SYNONYMY AND RELATIONSHIPS

Dippenaar-Schoeman (1980) synonymized *R. cataracta* Lawrence with *R. affinis*.

Runcinia affinis resembles *R. tropica* in the shape and colour of the body, but differs in the shape of the abdominal setae and the shape of the external genitalia.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Kurrachee, India, 1 ♀ (M.N.H.P.).

Type-locality of synonym: *R. cataracta* Kunene River, South West Africa (17° 15'S, 11° 46'E), ♀ (S.A.M. B6149).

DISTRIBUTION

India, Egypt, Algeria, South West Africa, Zimbabwe, South Africa.

NEW RECORDS

ZAÏRE: Ishanga, 26-29.xii.1968, R.P. Lejeune, 2 ♀, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 135.383); Kivu, 13.vi.1972, R.P. Lejeune, ♀, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 144.517); Kasongo, ix.1959, P.L.G. Benoit, 2 ♀ (M.R.A.C. 154.400+401). TOGO: Vangan, 1963, Y. Due, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 124430).

Runcinia aethiops (Simon), Fig. 29a-d

Runciniopsis aethiops Simon, 1901: 21.

Runcinia (Runciniopsis) aethiops (Simon), De Lessert, 1915: 39; Di Caporiacco, 1939: 361.

Runcinia aethiops (Simon), Strand, 1907c: 110; De Lessert, 1919: 126; 1928: 320; Di Caporiacco, 1949: 458; Jézéquel, 1964: 1122; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980: 320.

DESCRIPTION

Carapace and legs usually mottled, white and dark brown. Carapace slightly flattened; setae S_1 present, long and spiniform. Carina sharply pointed. Abdomen triangular in shape (Fig. 29a), covered with club-shaped setae (Fig. 29d). Epigynum large and very distinct (Fig. 29b). Male smaller and darker in colour; abdomen more oval; striae on abdomen with longer and stronger setae. Palp large (Fig. 29c); RTA broad at base with a slight knob laterally near terminal end, which is broad with a corrugated edge.

RELATIONSHIPS

Runcinia aethiops is characterized by the triangular abdomen and the distinct markings on the body. The epigynum and palp are large in comparison with the other African species. *R. aethiops* and *R. lateralis* are the only African species bearing club-shaped setae on the abdomen.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Ethiopia, East Africa (no exact locality) (8° 0'N, 40° 0'E), ♀, ♂ (M.N.H.P. 1800).

DISTRIBUTION

Ethiopia, Tanzania, Kenya, Ivory Coast, Zaïre, Botswana, Rwanda, Uganda, Togo, South Africa.

NEW RECORDS

BOTSWANA: Okavango Delta, Xugana Lagoon, U. Wilmot, juveniles (N.M.B. A286). ZAÏRE: Kivu, 13.vii.1968, R.P. Lejeune, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 135.645); Kivu, reserve Kasongweri, iv.1970, R.P. Lejeune 2 ♀ (M.R.A.C. 137.590 + 593); Kivu, valley Kiharo, vi.1973, R.P. Lejeune, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 146.077); Kivu, near Ruindi,

FIG. 28a *Runcinia affinis* Simon. (a). Epigynum, ventral view/Epigynium, ventrale aansig.

b

c

FIG. 28b-c (b). Female, dorsal view/*Wyfie, dorsale aansig*. (c). Palp, ventral view/*Palp, ventrale aansig*

a

b

FIG. 29a-b *Runcinia aethiops* (Simon). (a). Female, dorsal view/*Wyfie, dorsale aansig*. (b). Epigynum, ventral view/*Epigynium, ventrale aansig*

FIG. 29c-d (c). Palp, ventral view/*Palp, ventrale aansig.* (d). Abdominal setae/*Abdominale seta*

10.vii.1972, R.P. Lejeune, ♀, 2 immature (M.R.A.C. 144.644); Kivu, near Semliki, 8.viii.1968, R.P. Lejeune, ♀, 4 ♂ (M.R.A.C. 135.440); Lokandu, v.1939. Marice, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 3989); Uvira, vi.1958, juvenile (M.R.A.C. 112.622). KENYA: Karura Forest, 8.xii.1979, P. Reavell, juveniles (N.C.A. 80/46). RWANDA: Nyanza, 5.viii.1953, P. Basilensky, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 75.761). UGANDA: Musenyi Bay, Lake Victoria, iv.1968, E. Verriest, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 134.789). TOGO: Mt Agou, 26.vi.1963, Y. Duc, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 124435); Palime, 1963, Y. Duc, 3 juveniles (M.R.A.C. 124425).

Runcinia lateralis (Koch), Fig. 3a-b

Thomisus lateralis Koch, 1938: 43.

Runcinia lateralis (Koch); Simon, 1875: 255; Levy, 1973: 132; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980: 323.

DESCRIPTION

Carapace not much flattened (Fig. 30b); covered with a few club-shaped setae, irregularly spaced; carina and margin of carapace with a few short club-shaped setae; setae S_1 short, club-shaped. Abdomen oval (Fig. 30b); striae bearing short transparent club-shaped setae, evenly spaced. Epigynum unguiform, with a thickened rim (Fig. 30a); lower margin forming two loops medially; spermathecae

open as two dark sclerotic rings ventrally to epigynal plate.

No males were examined. Levy (1973) gives a description of the male palp.

RELATIONSHIPS

In *R. lateralis* the abdomen is oval, yellowish white in colour and the legs stout, with the epigynum very distinct. It has the same type of abdominal setae as *R. aethiops*.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Europe, exact locality not known.

DISTRIBUTION

Widely distributed throughout Europe, the Middle East, Turkestan and China. In Africa known from Egypt, Algeria, Tunisia, Morocco and South Africa (Cape Town). It is possible that this species was introduced into South Africa by marine traffic.

MISUMENOPS F. Pickard-Cambridge, 1900

Misumenops F. Pickard-Cambridge, 1900: 141; Petrunkevitch, 1911: 410; Gertsch, 1939: 318; Schick, 1965: 108; Suman, 1970: 800; Comstock, 1971: 542; Dondale & Redner, 1978: 140.

FIG. 30a-b *Runcinia lateralis* (Koch). (a). Epigynum, ventral view/Epigynium, ventrale aansig. (b). Female, dorsal view/Wyfie, dorsale aansig

Type-species: *Misumena maculisparsa* Keyserling, 1891.

Misumenops was established by Pickard-Cambridge (1900) and contains some species formerly referred to the genera *Diaea*, *Misumena* and *Synaema*. He regarded *Misumenops* as a genus of convenience, intermediate between *Misumena* and *Diaea*. Gertsch (1939), however, considered *Misumenops* as being representative of a group of spiders quite different from related genera. Some species of *Misumenops* of the Afrotropical region, as recognized in this paper, has previously been placed in the genus *Misumena*. De Lessert (1919) regarded *Misumenops* as a subgenus of *Misumena*. Members of the genus *Misumenops* resemble those of *Misumena* in shape and colour, but differ in having many erect setae on the body and legs. According to Dondale & Redner (1978) the status of this genus should be re-evaluated.

Misumenops is not well represented in the Afrotropical region and is now for the first time recorded from southern Africa. It is represented by one species which has a wide distribution in this area.

On the basis of the African material at hand, the genus *Misumenops* is defined as follows.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size: small spiders, 4,4-6,7 mm. Colour: yellow to pale green (green fades in alcohol to yellow); sometimes with red or brown patterns or

lines on carapace and abdomen; legs I and II sometimes banded with red or brown.

Carapace as wide as long, low and slightly convex; surface clothed with numerous erect spiniform setae. Eyes in two recurved rows (Fig. 31a); lateral eyes larger than median eyes, situated on conjoined tubercles; MOQ wider than long. Clypeus vertical, with 4 pairs of long primary setae on margin. Sternum heart-shaped. Abdomen round in dorsal view (Fig. 31b); flattened, clothed with numerous erect, spiniform setae. Legs: anterior two pairs approximately equal in length and thickness, longer and stronger than posterior pairs; prolateral surface of femora I and II with strong setae; ventral surface of tibiae and metatarsi with double row of macrosetae. Epigynum simple, usually with shallow atrium, a narrow median septum and a small hood anteriorly.

Male. Size: smaller than female (1,5-4,0 mm). Colour: similar to female, except anterior legs with dark bands. The male differs structurally from the female as follows. Setae on body, especially those on abdomen, longer and more numerous; legs longer and thinner and macrosetae on tibiae and metatarsi I and II weakly developed. Palp: RTA sharply pointed; VTA absent or very short; embolus slender, terminal part of embolus follows margin of bulb closely.

Juvenile. Very similar to females in shape, colour and type of integument.

DISTRIBUTION

Misumenops is a large genus and comprises about 60 species with the following distribution: Afrotropical region (3); Palaearctic region (1); Oriental region (1); Australian region (17); Nearctic region (27) and the Neotropical region (1). This indicates that the species of *Misumenops* are more concentrated in the warmer countries of the western hemisphere (Fig. 32).

SPECIES FROM THE AFROTROPICAL REGION

Misumenops is not well represented in the Afrotropical region and only four species have been recorded to date, of which two were formerly placed in the genus *Misumena*. *Misumenops* is now for the first time recorded from southern Africa and is represented by one species, *M. rubrodecorata* Millot.

FIG. 31a-b *Misumenops* sp. female/wyfie. (a). Carapace, anterior view/Karapaks, anterioraansig. (b). Body, dorsal view/Liggaam, dorsale aansig

FIG. 32 Known geographical distribution of *Misumenops* F. Pickard-Cambridge/Bekende geografiese verspreiding van *Misumenops* F. Pickard-Cambridge

Appendix 3 lists the species of the Afrotropical region as well as their known distribution.

DISCUSSION

Morphological characters. The epigynum of the female is relatively simple in shape and seems to be subject to some variation among species (Gertsch, 1939; Millot, 1941). In some cases descriptions of new species were based on material where the females were not fully mature and the epigynum only partly developed.

Morphological adaptations. Spiders of the genus *Misumenops* have pale green to yellowish bodies sometimes with red patterns. Their appearance and locomotion are crab-like and they ambush their prey in the blossoms of herbs, shrubs and trees. They were collected by means of suction traps and beating.

Biology. Very little is known about the biology of *Misumenops*. A biological study of *M. celer*

(Hentz) was done by Muniappan & Chada (1970) in North America. Gertsch (1939) studied the mating behaviour of *M. asperatus* (Hentz) and he made some observations on its feeding behaviour.

Misumenops rubrodecorata Millot, Fig. 33a-f

Misumenops rubrodecorata Millot, 1941: 37.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size (n=10): TL 3,8 (3,3-4,1); CL 1,4 (1,3-1,5); CW 1,5 (1,4-1,6); CI 0,9.

Colour: body and legs yellowish with a greenish tint (in alcohol it fades to yellow); carapace usually a little darker than abdomen; eye area white; anterior part of abdomen with a broad red horseshoe-shaped band (Fig. 31b); legs sometimes banded.

Millot (1941) gave a complete description of the female. Some variation in the shape of the epigynum was observed (Fig. 33b and c).

FIG. 33a-f

Misumenops rubrodecorata Millot. (a). Internal genitalia, dorsal view/*Inwendige genitalieë, dorsale aansig.* (b-c). Epigynum, ventral view (variations)/*Epigynium, ventrale aansig (variasies).* (d). Female, dorsal view/*Wyfie, dorsale aansig.* (e). Palp, retrolateral view/*Palp, retrolaterale aansig.* (f). Palp, ventral view/*Palp, ventrale aansig.*

The internal genitalia are shown in Fig. 33a.

Male. The male of this species is described here for the first time.

Size (n=10); TL 1,8 (1,6-1,9); CL 0,7 (0,7-0,8); CW 0,8 (0,7-1,1); CI 0,9.

Colour: body and legs uniformly yellowish brown; basal parts of tibiae, metatarsi and tarsi of legs I and II darkened (Fig. 33d).

Carapace almost as wide as long, clothed with numerous long and dark, spiniform setae. Abdomen ovate (Fig. 33d), covered with the same type of setae. Legs long and thin, especially I and II; macrosetae on legs I and II much reduced; tibiae and metatarsi I and II clothed with long thin hairs. Palp: RTA long and thin; VTA absent (Fig. 33e and f).

Juvenile. Similar to females, spiny appearance very distinct.

RELATIONSHIPS

The genitalia of *Misumenops rubrodecorata* resemble those of *Misumena nana* while they are morphologically closest to *M. spinulosissima*. The placement of the last two species in the genus *Misumena* is doubtful. According to their descriptions their bodies are clothed with numerous erect setae, which indicate a closer relationship with *Misumenops*.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Kindia, Guinea (10° 0'N, 12° 52'W), ♀ (M.N.H.P. 1482).

DISTRIBUTION

Guinea, Sudan, Upper Volta.

New records: Mali, Zimbabwe, South West Africa, South Africa.

MATERIAL EXAMINED

MALI: Zamblara, viii.1970, G. Pierrard, ♂ (M.R.A.C. 138.834); Fana, ix.1969, G. Pierrard, 3 ♂ (M.R.A.C. 136.811), ♀ (M.R.A.C. 142.363). ZIMBABWE: Kezi, 6.iv.1980, C.A. Car, 3 ♀ (N.M.B. A852); Matopos Malene Dam, 12.iv.1980, C.A. Car, 3 ♀ (N.M.B. A464) SOUTH WEST AFRICA: Kaokoveld, 16.vi.1961, ♀ (swe. exp. A.M.); Kowares, Kaokoveld, 3.vi.1951, 2 ♀ (swe. exp. A.M.). SOUTH AFRICA: *Cape Province*: Mountain Zebra National Park, Cradock, 23.iii.1976, A.S. Dippenaar, juveniles (N.C.A. 76/623); Pineapple Research Station, East London, v-vi.1979, D. Keetch, immature ♂ (N.C.A. 79/326); East London, 26.xi.1973, L. Smit, ♂ (N.C.A. 76/1831); Upington, 23.xi.1950, ♀ (swe. exp. A.M.); Postmasburg, 3.ii.1979, E. Uecker-mann, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/313). *Orange Free State*: Reddersburg, 8.ii.1979, C. Kok, juvenile (N.C.A. 79/45); Winburg, 7.x.1974, H. de Lange, ♀ (N.C.A. 76/316); Edenville, 5.iv.1967, A.S. Dippenaar, ♂ (N.C.A. 77/830). *Natal*: Loteni Nature Reserve, 25.xii.1978, E. van den Berg, ♀♀, ♂♂ (N.C.A. 79/44 and 320); Pongola,

20.iv.1967, A.S. Dippenaar, 2 ♀ (N.C.A. 76/1298); 20 km N Mtubatuba, 31.iii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 77/679); 20 km E Dukuduku, 29.iii.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, juvenile (N.C.A. 79/327); between Jozini and Ndumi, 4.iv.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, 2 ♀, 4 ♂ (N.C.A. 77/713); Pietermaritzburg, iv.1944, R.F. Lawrence, ♀ (N.M. 4635); Champagne Castle, i.1968, R.F. Lawrence, 10 ♀ (N.M. 7329 and 6972); Paddock, 17.i.1979, C.J. Cilliers, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/42); Margate, 14.ii.1978, C.J. Cilliers, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/49); Shalkraal, 13.iii.1979, C.J. Cilliers, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/330). *Transvaal*: Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve, 4.iii.1979, A. le Roy, juvenile (N.C.A. 79/325); Abe Bailey Nature Reserve, 11.i.1979, A. le Roy, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/314); Buffelspoort, 15.iii.1970, M.K.P. Meyer, juveniles (N.C.A. 76/1855); Zeerust, 30.iii.1975, J. Oosthuizen, ♀♀, ♂♂ (N.C.A. 76/1607); Swartklip, 26.iii.1978, G. Nel, ♀, ♂ (N.C.A. 78/411, 79/122); Rustenburg, 20.ii.1975, A.S. Dippenaar, 2 ♂ (N.C.A. 76/1624); Pretoria, 25.ix.1975, E. Theron, ♀ (N.C.A. 76/1550); Roodeplaat, near Pretoria, 14.iii.1972, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/318); Kameeldrift, near Pretoria, 7.xii.1977, I. van Zyl, ♀ (N.C.A. 78/15); between Pretoria and Bronkhorstspuit, 26.iv.1977, A.S. Dippenaar, 2 ♀ (N.C.A. 77/785); 3 km Verena, 10.ii.1977, I. Vosloo, ♂ (N.C.A. 77/441); 8 km S Dennilton, 20.iv.1979, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/315); 20 km Molotto, 27.ii.1975, J. Oosthuizen, ♀ (N.C.A. 76/278); farm Enkeldoorn, near Molotto, 25.xii.1975, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/304); Rust de Winter (various occasions), L. Pretorius, 9 ♀, ♂ (N.C.A. 76/1147, 76/1164, 79/41, 79/47); 4 km Marble Hall, 27.ii.1975, J. Oosthuizen, ♀♀, ♂♂ (N.C.A. 76/277); Loskopdam Nature Reserve, 5.iv.1973, A.S. Dippenaar, 2 ♀ (N.C.A. 76/801, 76/1784); 7 km Groblersdal, 10.vii.1977, I. Vosloo, ♂ (N.C.A. 77/444); Warmbaths, 8.iii.1977, I. Vosloo, ♀ (N.C.A. 77/439); Sterkrievierdam, near Potgietersrust, xi.1973, L. Smit, ♂ (N.C.A. 76/772); Potgietersrust, 24.ii.1978, E. van den Berg, ♀ (N.C.A. 78/262); Nylsvley, near Naboomspruit, i-xii.1976, G. Ferreira, 2 ♀, ♂ (N.C.A. 78/492, 79/321); Pietersburg, 2.v.1979, C.J. Cilliers, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/312); 30 km W Louis Trichardt, 23.ii.1976, A.S. Dippenaar, 2 ♂ (N.C.A. 76/13); farm Amsterdam, near Dendron, 12.vi.1969, A.S. Dippenaar, ♀ (N.C.A. 77/843); Huwi Nature Reserve, near Ellisras, 12.iv.1974, A.S. Dippenaar, 5 ♀ (N.C.A. 76/791, 804); 14 km E Middelburg, 11.iv.1978, S. Stiemie, ♀ (N.C.A. 79/61); 10 km Bethal, 13.iv.1978, G. Nel, 2 ♂ (N.C.A. 78/362); 23 km Wonderfontein (on Hendrina road), 12.iv.1978, G. Nel, ♀, ♂ (N.C.A. 78/346); 20 km Nelspruit (on Plastron road), 19.iii.1977, U. Burger, ♀♀, ♂♂ (N.C.A. 77/300); Ohrigstad, 22.ii.1978, E. van den Berg, ♀ (N.C.A. 78/237); 15 km N Gravelotte, 25.ii.1976, A.S. Dippenaar, 4 ♀ (N.C.A. 76/68); 10 km Sabie, 20.ii.1978, E. van den Berg, ♀ (N.C.A. 78/216); 70 km Tzaneen, 24.ii.1978, E. van den Berg, 2 ♂ (N.C.A. 78/260); Levubu, 28.iii.1973, A.S. Dippenaar, 2 ♀, 4 ♂ (N.C.A. 76/802, 76/828).

BIONOMICS

M. rubrodecorata is by far the most common thomisid species yet recorded from South Africa. Adults were collected throughout the year, except in the winter months. They inhabit grass, shrubs, flowers and trees. It is the species most frequently encountered on cotton at Rust de Winter and Oudestad, near Groblersdal. They were also collected from strawberry plants and citrus.

MISUMENA Latreille, 1804

Misumena Latreille, 1804: 135; Simon, 1895: 1025; 1903b: 1012; F. Pickard-Cambridge, 1900: 141; Gertsch, 1939: 314; Schick, 1965: 107; Dondale & Redner, 1978: 131.

Type-species: *Araneus vatus* Clerck, 1757.

Misumena includes typical crab-like spiders with short, robust bodies and long powerful laterigrade front legs. It has attracted the attention of naturalists because of the ability of some species to change colour reversibly.

Members of the genus *Misumena* closely resemble those of *Misumenoides* and *Misumenops*, but they lack the white transverse ridge, or carina, found in the former genus and the spinose integument of the latter one. All three genera occur in the same type of habitat.

According to Simon (1895) the genus *Massuria*, known from two species described from Burma and Java, is close to *Misumena*. They differ only in the posterior eye row, which is a little more recurved than the anterior row in *Massuria*, and in the median eyes which are situated closer to each other than to the lateral eyes.

Misumena is not well represented in southern Africa and only two species are recorded. With the material at hand, the genus *Misumena* can be defined as follows.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size: small to moderate-large.

Colour: carapace fawn to yellow, sometimes with a greenish pink tint, body usually with red markings.

Carapace: as wide as long, smoothly convex along lateral margin (Fig. 34a); clypeus vertical with three pairs of primary setae on margin; carapace with a few pairs of primary setae, not as spinose as *Misumenops*. Eyes arranged into two transverse recurved rows, posterior row more so than anterior row; lateral eyes slightly larger than median eyes and situated on conjoined tubercles; MOQ wider than long. Abdomen round to slightly oval in dorsal view, flattened; lacking erect setae but clothed with numerous fine hairs (Fig. 34b). Legs I and II usually almost entirely devoid of macro-setae, except ventrally on the tibiae and metatarsi. Epigynum: simple, with a shallow atrium and small hood.

Male. Size: smaller than female.

Colour: similar to female, except anterior pair of legs which are banded. Male differs structurally from the female as follows. Legs longer and thinner with a few setae dorsally. Carapace a little more flattened and abdomen ovate. Palp: tibia with elaborated RTA; VTA shorter and simpler.

Juvenile. Very similar to female.

DISTRIBUTION

In all approximately 60 species, with the following endemic distribution, are currently recognized: Palaearctic (13); Afrotropical (5); Oriental (9); Australian (6); Neotropical (22) and Nearctic (4) (Fig. 35).

SPECIES FROM THE AFROTROPICAL REGION

Misumena is represented in the Afrotropical region by five species (Appendix 4). Two species, *M. tuckeri* and *M. natalensis* are known from southern Africa. The latter species was described from a single male, which was subsequently lost. According to the description and drawings of Lawrence (1947) it is doubtful whether this species actually belongs to *Misumena*.

DISCUSSION

Morphological characters. Simon (1895) suggested that *Misumena* should be separated from the other genera of the thomisids by the following combination of characters: shape of lateral ocular protrusions, which is obtuse and not carinate or tuberculate; the armature of the legs and the vestiture of the tarsi. He thereby reduced the number of species previously placed in *Misumena*. However, a number of species still remain intermediate between *Misumena*, *Diaea* and *Misumenops*.

The placement of species like *nana* and *spinulosissima* in the genus *Misumena* is doubtful. According to their descriptions their bodies are clothed with numerous erect setae, which indicate a closer relationship with *Misumenops*. De Lessert (1919), however, treated *Misumenops* as a subgenus of *Misumena*.

The genitalia are the characters most frequently used to distinguish between species of *Misumena*. The epigynum is simple and resembles that of the species of *Misumenops*, whereas the palp is provided with large RTA.

Morphological adaptations. *Misumena* is common in the U.S.A. and Europe and has attracted much attention because of the ability of the adult female of some species to change colour reversibly. Our knowledge on colour changes in this genus is based entirely on observations made on one species, *M. vatia* (Clerck) by Packard (1905), De Ker-ville (1907), Gabritschewsky (1927) and Weigel (1941). This phenomenon has not yet been observed in African species.

FIG. 34a-b *Misumena* sp. (a). Carapace, anterior view/*Karapaks, anterioraansig*. (b). Body, dorsal view/*Liggaam, dorsale aansig*

FIG. 55 Known geographical distribution of *Misumena* Latreille/*Bekende geografiese verspreiding van Misumena Latreille*

Hinton (1976) studied the significance of the red patches on the abdomen of the adult female. He found that the patches function as a warning colour for birds and other vertebrates, which are not red-blind.

Members of the genus *Misumena*, like those of *Misumenops* and *Thomisus*, ambush their prey in the inflorescences of herbs, shrubs and trees. Their behaviour differs from that of *Thomisus* in that the spider awaits its prey between the leaves of the flowers. Prey, captured by the spider leaping forward, is dragged over the edge of the flower to the leaves beneath where it is fed on. These observations are in

concordance with those of Lovell (1915) on *Misumena* species from Canada.

Morse (1979) studied the prey captured by *Misumena calycina* (L.) and found that on pasture roses it captures large numbers of bumble bees, solitary bees and syrphid flies which visit the flowers solely for their pollen.

Biology. Very little is known about the biology of *Misumena*. According to Comstock (1971) the egg-sac is made on a leaf and protected by a part of the leaf which is folded over. It is held in position with a sheet of silk. The female sits on the sac until

a

b

c

d

FIG. 36a-d

Misumena tuckeri De Lessert. (a). Internal genitalia, dorsal view/*Inwendige genitalieë, dorsale aansig.* (b). Epigynum, ventral view/*Epigynium, ventrale aansig.* (c). Palp, ventral view/*Palp, ventrale aansig.* (d). Palp, retrolateral view/*Palp, retrolaterale aansig.*

the spiderlings emerge. Bristowe (1926) recorded some observations on the mating behaviour of *Misumena vatia*.

Misumena tuckeri De Lessert, Fig. 36a-d

Misumena (Misumenops) tuckeri De Lessert, 1919: 133.

Misumenops tuckeri Millot, 1941: 35.

DESCRIPTION

Female. Size (n=2): TL 3,2; CL 1,5; CW 1,6; CI 0,9

Colour: carapace and legs fawn; eye area white; metatarsi and tarsi of legs brownish, more distinct in legs I and II. Abdomen white, usually with two reddish brown spots slanting on each side.

Carapace slightly wider than long (CI 0,9); thoracic area sloping strongly posteriorly. Lateral eyes situated on low tubercles of which bases are confluent; both eye rows recurved; anterior eyes slightly larger than posterior eyes; ALE larger than AME; posterior eyes almost same size; MOQ wider posteriorly than anteriorly; carapace devoid of setae except for primary setae, C₂ and C₄ on the clypeus, P₄ on ocular area and S₁ posterior to PLE. Abdomen wider than long, provided with faint striae, clothed with fine hairs. Legs: femur 1 with 4 setae dorsally; femora II-IV with one seta each; metatarsi I and II with 3-4 pairs of macro-setae ventrally and tibiae I and II with 2-3 pairs. Epigynum: simple, rounded with slightly darkened edges (Fig. 36b); internal genitalia shown in Fig. 36a.

Male. Size (n=4): TL 2,4 (2,0-2,7); CL 1,2 (1,1-1,4); CW 1,3 (1,2-1,4); CI 0,9.

Male differs in colour from female as follows. Carapace fawn to pale brown, usually with two distinct mediolateral lines; abdomen off-white; legs fawn, distal part of each segment with a reddish brown band.

Carapace slightly wider than long; eyes as in female; primary setae the same as in female, with S₁ very distinct. Abdomen with faint striae, ovate. Legs long and thin; femora dorsally with a few setae; tibiae and metatarsi I and II with 2-3 pairs of macro-setae each. Palp: RTA and VTA well separated, almost the same length (Fig. 36d); embolus dark and long (Fig. 36c).

Juvenile. Similar to female, distinct in shape of eye tubercles and the presence of the primary setae, especially S₁.

RELATIONSHIPS

According to De Lessert (1919) this species is intermediate between the genera *Misumena* and *Diaea*. He also considered it close to the genus *Misumenops*, which he treated as a subgenus of *Misumena*. However, if the spinosity of *Misumenops* has generic value *Misumena tuckeri* definitely belongs to *Misumena*, especially when compared with *Misumenops rubrodecorata*.

TYPE-LOCALITY

Kibonoto, Kilimanjaro. It is likely that Kibonoto is a misspelling of Kibongota, south-western foothills of Mt Kilimanjaro, Moshi district, Tanzania (03° 12'S, 37° 07'E), ♀, ♂ (M.N.H.G.).

DISTRIBUTION

Tanzania, Ivory Coast, Zaïre, South Africa (Natal).

New records: South Africa (Transvaal, Cape Province).

MATERIAL EXAMINED

ZAÏRE: Haut-Ouëllé, Moto, L. Burgeon, ♀ (M.R.A.C. 128232). SOUTH AFRICA: *Cape Province*: Grahamstown, 28.xi.1979, A.S. Dippenaar, juvenile (N.C.A. 80/336); Alexandria Coastal Forest, 46 km SSW Grahamstown, 21.x.1978, P. Croeser, ♀ (N.C.A. 80/335); Gretna Farm, 6 km SW Grahamstown, 22.x.1978, P. Croeser, ♀ (N.C.A. 80/334); Citrusdal, v.1973, G. Donaldson, ♂ (N.C.A. 76/821). *Natal*: Shakaskraal, 18.i.1979, C.J. Cilliers, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/43); Sodwana Bay, 5.v.1981, C. Car, 2 ♂ (S.A.M. C409 and C542). *Transvaal*: 12 km Blydepoort (Ohrigstad road), 23.ii.1978, E. van den Berg, ♂ (N.C.A. 79/331).

BIONOMICS

Females were collected during October and males during January, February and May from grass, trees and flowers.

SPECIES INCERTAE SEDIS

Misumena natalensis Lawrence

Misumena natalensis Lawrence, 1947: 28.

The holotype of this species from Durban, Natal is believed to have been lost. It was collected during an expedition of Dr I. Trägårdh (Sweden) to Natal and Zululand in 1904 and 1905. Dr R.F. Lawrence (formerly of the Natal Museum) was asked to identify the spiders and according to Dr H.W. Waldén (in litt) of the Naturhistoriska Museet Göteborg, Sweden the material was probably lost in transit, as it could not be located in either museum.

Some characters of this species as described by Lawrence (1947), namely the procurved posterior eye row, the PME being the largest of all eight eyes, and the shape of the palp, do not correspond with the definition of *Misumena*. The possibility exists that *M. natalensis* belongs to another genus but it cannot be positively identified from the original description alone.

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FIG. 37a-b Maps of Africa/*Kaarte van Afrika*. (a). Geographical areas/*Geografiese areas*. (b). Countries referred to in the text/*Lande waarna in teks verwys word*

APPENDIX 1 Species of *Thomisus* known from the Afrotropical region: their synonymy and distribution
 AANHANGSEL 1 Spesies van *Thomisus* van die Afrotropiese gebied: hul sinonieme en verspreiding

Species/ <i>Spesies</i>	Type-collections <i>Tiepversamelings</i>	Synonyms/ <i>Sinonieme</i>	Distribution <i>Verspreiding</i>
<i>albertianus</i> Strand, 1913:392	♀ (M.N.B.)	<i>Thomisus gabonensis</i> Comellini, 1957:13; 1959: 110 (♂, M.N.H.P.)	Central and East Africa
<i>albohirtus</i> Simon, 1884:13	♀ (M.N.H.P.)	<i>Thomisus milloti</i> De Lessert, 1943:325; Comellini, 1959: 110 (♂, M.N.H.G.)	North Africa
<i>angulatus</i> Roewer, 1951:449	♀ (? type)		Central Africa
<i>angustifrons</i> Lucas, 1858:402	♀ (? type)		Central Africa
<i>arabicus</i> Simon, 1882:225	♀ (B.M.)		North Africa, Yemen and Arabia
* <i>australis</i> Comellini, 1957:6	♂ (N.M.)	<i>Thomisus drakensbergensis</i> Comellini, 1959:114, syn. nov. (♀, N.M.)	East, Central and southern Africa
		<i>Thomisus mossambicus</i> Comellini, 1957:20, syn. nov. (♀, M.N.H.G.)	
		<i>T. mossambicus weidneri</i> Comellini, 1957:20, syn. nov. (♀, Z.M.H.)	
<i>benoiti</i> Comellini, 1959:112	♂ (M.R.A.C.)		Central Africa
<i>bidentatus</i> Kulczynski, 1901:3	♀,♂ (Museum Helsinki)	<i>Thomisus alboirroratus</i> Simon, 1907:316, syn. nov. (♀, M.N.H.P.)	North and East Africa
* <i>blandus</i> Karsch, 1880:382	♂ (M.N.B.)	<i>Thomisus malevolus</i> F. Pickard-Cambridge, 1907:825; Comellini, 1957:5 (♀, H.E.C.)	North, East, West, Central and southern Africa
		<i>Thomisus anthobius</i> Pocock, 1898a:225, syn. nov. (♀, B.M.)	
		<i>Thomisus sus</i> Strand, 1907a:539, syn. nov. (♂, M.N.B.)	
		<i>Thomisus malevolus delesserti</i> Di Caporiacco, 1941:125, syn. nov. (♂, ? type)	
		<i>Thomisus malevolus ocellitibiis</i> Di Caporiacco, 1949:455, syn. nov. (♀, ? type)	
<i>boesenbergi</i> Lenz, 1891:165	♂ (Z.M.H.)		Madagascar
<i>bonnieri</i> Simon, 1902:252	♀ (? type)		Arabia
<i>bueanus</i> Strand, 1915:146	♀ (Deutsches Ent. Inst., Berlin)		Central Africa

Species/Spesies	Type-collections Tieppersamelingen	Synonyms/Sinonieme	Distribution Verspreiding
<i>candidus</i> Blackwall, 1866:456 * <i>citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875:253	♀ (? type) ♀, ♂ (H.E.C.)	<i>Thomisus spinifer decorata</i> Millot, 1941:47, syn. nov. (♀, M.N.H.P.?) <i>Thomisus spinifer obscurus</i> Di Caporiacco, 1941:127, syn. nov. (♀, ? type) <i>Thomisus spinifer simoni</i> Di Caporiacco, 1941:126, syn. nov. (♀, ? type) <i>Thomisus spinifer maculitibiis</i> Di Caporiacco, 1947a:216, syn. nov. (♀, ? type)	Central Africa Africa, Israel, Yemen, Arabia and France
* <i>congoensis</i> Comellini, 1957:9 * <i>dalmasi</i> De Lessert, 1919:119	♂ (M.N.H.G.) ♂ (M.N.H.G.)	<i>Thomisus dalmasoides</i> Millot, 1941:47; Comellini, 1957:10 (♂, M.N.H.P.) <i>Thomisus anthobioides</i> Lawrence, 1942:154, syn. nov. (♀, N.M.) <i>Thomisus anthobioides mongbwalensis</i> Comellini, 1957:4, syn. nov. (♀, M.R.A.C.)	Central and southern Africa East, West, Central and southern Africa
* <i>daradioides</i> Simon, 1890:108	♀ (M.N.H.P.)	<i>Thomisus lesnei</i> De Lessert, 1936:256, syn. nov. (♂, M.N.H.G.) <i>Thomisus sepiosus</i> Lawrence, 1942: 152, syn. nov. (♀, N.M.)	East, Central and southern Africa, India and Arabia
<i>dartevellei</i> Comellini, 1957:10 <i>destefanii</i> Di Caporiacco, 1941:47 <i>quesquierei</i> De Lessert, 1943:323 * <i>granulatus</i> Karsch, 1880:382	♀ (M.R.A.C.) ♀, ♂ (? type) ♂ (M.R.A.C.) ♀ (M.N.B.)	<i>Thomisus hystrix</i> Lawrence, 1947:25 (name preoccupied Nicolet, 1849) <i>Thomisus lawrencei</i> Roewer, 1951: 449, syn. nov. (♂, type lost)	Central Africa East Africa Central Africa Southern Africa
<i>hararinus</i> Di Caporiacco, 1947a:217	♀ (Museum National Budapest)		East Africa
<i>hilarulus</i> Simon, 1875:252 * <i>hottentotus</i> Strand, 1907a:538	♀, ♂ (M.N.H.G.) ♀ (Museum Lübeck, type destroyed)		North Africa, Canary Islands Southern Africa
<i>janinae</i> Comellini, 1957:6 * <i>kalaharinus</i> Lawrence, 1936: 153	♀ (M.R.A.C.) ♀ (T.M.)	<i>Thomisus urbensis</i> Lawrence, 1942:153, syn. nov. (♀, N.M.)	Central Africa East, West, Central and southern Africa
<i>kiwuensis</i> Strand, 1913:391	♀ (M.R.A.C.)		Central Africa

Species/Spesies	Type-collections Tiepversamelings	Synonyms/Sinonieme	Distribution Verspreiding
<i>lamperti</i> Strand, 1907d:734	♀,♂ (Museum Lübeck, type destroyed)		Madagascar
* <i>lenzi</i> Strand, 1907a:538	♂ (Museum Lübeck, type destroyed)		Southern Africa
<i>litoris</i> Strand, 1913:394	Subadult ♀		Central Africa
* <i>machadoi</i> Comellini, 1959:117	♂ (Museum Dundo, Angola)		Central and southern Africa
<i>madagascariensis</i> Comellini, 1957:17	♀ (M.N.H.G.)		Madagascar
* <i>natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1942:156	♀ (N.M.)		Southern Africa
<i>nossibeensis</i> Strand, 1907d:734	♀ (Museum Lübeck, type destroyed)		Madagascar
<i>obscuratus</i> Di Caporiacco, 1947a:216	♀ (National Museum Budapest)		East Africa
<i>onustus</i> Walckenaer, 1805:32	(? type)		North Africa, Europe
<i>obtusetulosis</i> Roewer, 1961:73	(? type)		West Africa
<i>roeweri</i> Comellini, 1957:21	♀ (M.N.H.G.)		East Africa
<i>schoutedeni</i> Comellini, 1957:22	♂ (M.R.A.C.)		Central Africa
* <i>schantzei</i> Simon, 1910:194	♀ (M.N.H.P.)		Southern Africa
* <i>scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886a): 363	♂ (M.N.H.P.)	<i>Thomisus caffer</i> Simon, 1904:69; Comellini, 1957:26 (♀, M.N.H.G.)	East, West, Central and southern Africa
		<i>Thomisus amanicus</i> Strand, 1907a:537; Comellini, 1957:26 (♀, M.N.B.)	
		<i>Thomisus quadrituberculatus</i> De Lessert, 1943:327; Comellini, 1957:26 (♂, M.R.A.C.)	
		<i>Thomisus lindneri</i> Roewer, 1956:47, syn. nov. (♂, ? type)	
* <i>spiculosus</i> Pocock, 1901:340	♀ (B.M.?)	<i>Thomisus dottrensi</i> Comellini, 1957:10, syn. nov. (♂, M.R.A.C.)	Central, West and southern Africa
* <i>steningi</i> Pocock, 1900:332	♀ (B.M.)	<i>Thomisus weberi</i> De Lessert, 1923:147, syn. nov. (♂, A.M.?)	East, West, Central and southern Africa
<i>tripunctatus</i> Lucas, 1858:400	♀ (? type)		Central and West Africa
* <i>zuluanus</i> Lawrence, 1942:155	♀ (N.M.)		Southern Africa

* Species discussed in text/Spesies bespreek in teks

APPENDIX 2 Species of *Runcinia* known from the Afrotropical region: their synonymy and distribution
 AANHANGSEL 2 Spesies van *Runcinia* van die Afrotropiese gebied: hul sinonieme en verspreiding

Species/ <i>Spesies</i>	Type-collections <i>Tiepversamelings</i>	Synonyms/ <i>Sinonieme</i>	Distribution <i>Verspreiding</i>
<i>*aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901:21)	♀, ♂ (M.N.H.P.)		East, West, Central and southern Africa
<i>*affinis</i> Simon, 1897b:292	♀ (M.N.H.P.?)	<i>Runcinia cataracta</i> Lawrence, 1927:36; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980:317 (♀, S.A.M.)	North and southern Africa and India
<i>albida</i> (Marx, 1893:589)	Immature ♂ (? type)		Central Africa
<i>*carae</i> spec. nov.	♂, ♀ (N.M.B.)		East and southern Africa
<i>*depressa</i> Simon, 1906:1166	♀ (M.N.H.P.)		North, East, West, Central and southern Africa
<i>dubia</i> Di Caporiacco, 1940b:300	Immature ♀ (? type)		East Africa
<i>*erythrina</i> Jézéquel, 1964:1123	Immature ♀ (M.N.H.P.)		West and southern Africa
<i>*flavida</i> (Simon, 1881:1)	♀ (M.N.H.P.)	<i>Runcinia proxima</i> De Lessert, 1919:129; Dippenaar-Schoeman, ♂, 1980:307 (♀, M.N.H.G.) <i>Runcinia proxima voltaensis</i> Millot, 1941:39; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980:307 (♂, M.N.H.P.) <i>Runcinia littorina</i> Lawrence, 1942:157; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980:307 (♀, N.M.)	North, West, East, Central and southern Africa
<i>*johnstoni</i> De Lessert 1919:127	♂ (M.N.H.G.)	<i>Runcinia sjoestedti</i> De Lessert, 1919:131; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980:310 (♂, ♀, M.N.H.G.)	East, West, Central and southern Africa
<i>*lateralis</i> (Koch, 1838:43)	♀ (? type)		Throughout Palearctic region and southern Africa
<i>longipes</i> Strand, 1906:625	Immature ♀ (Museum Lübeck)		East Africa
<i>multilineata</i> Roewer, 1961:72	♀ (? type)		West Africa
<i>oculifrons</i> Strand, 1907d:734	♂, immature ♀ (Museum Lübeck)		Madagascar
<i>*tropica</i> Simon, 1907:316	♀, ♂ (M.N.H.P.)		Annobon, East, Central and southern Africa

APPENDIX 3 Species of *Misumenops* known from the Afrotropical region: their synonymy and distribution
 AANHANGSEL 3 *Spesies van Misumenops van die Afrotropiese gebied: hul sinonieme en verspreiding*

Species/ <i>Spesies</i>	Type-collections <i>Tiepversamelings</i>	Synonyms/ <i>Sinonieme</i>	Distribution <i>verspreiding</i>
<i>decolor</i> (Kulczynski, 1901:3)	♀ (? type)		East Africa
<i>nana</i> (De Lessert, 1933:118)	♀ (M.N.H.G.)		Central Africa
* <i>rubrodecorata</i> Millot, 1941:37	♀ (M.N.H.G.)		West, North and southern Africa
<i>spinulosissima</i> Berland, 1936:77	♀ (? type)		Cape Verde

69

APPENDIX 4 Species of *Misumena* known from the Afrotropical region: their synonymy and distribution
 AANHANGSEL 4 *Spesies van Misumena van die Afrotropiese gebied: hul sinonieme en verspreiding*

Species/ <i>Spesies</i>	Type-collections <i>Tiepversamelings</i>	Synonyms/ <i>Sinonieme</i>	Distribution <i>Verspreiding</i>
<i>alluaudi</i> Simon, 1897b:279	♀ (M.N.H.P.)		Mauritius
<i>maronica</i> Di Caporiacco, 1954:139	♀ (? type)		West Africa
* <i>natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947:28	♂ (type lost)		Southern Africa
<i>pallescens</i> Di Caporiacco, 1949:457	♀ (? type)		East Africa
* <i>tuckeri</i> De Lessert, 1919:133	♀, ♂ (M.N.H.G.)		East, West, Central and southern Africa

INDEX

Species names are followed by their generic name in brackets. Synonyms are followed by the name recognized in this study.

A	Page		Page
aethiops (Runcinia)	46	lenzi (Thomisus)	36
affinis (Runcinia)	45	lesnei (Thomisus) = daradioides (Thomisus)	25
affinis tropica (Runcinia) = tropica (Runcinia)	44	lindneri (Thomisus) = scrupeus (Thomisus)	17
albertianus (Thomisus)	61	litoris (Thomisus)	63
albida (Runcinia)	64	littorina (Runcinia) = flavida (Runcinia)	39
albohirtus (Thomisus)	61	longipes (Runcinia)	64
alboirroratus (Thomisus) = blandus (Thomisus)	13	M	
alluaudi (Misumena)	65	machadoi (Thomisus)	36
amanicus (Thomisus) = scrupeus (Thomisus)	17	madagascariensis (Thomisus)	63
angulatulus (Thomisus)	61	malevolus (Thomisus) = blandus (Thomisus)	13
angustifrons (Thomisus)	61	malevolus delessertii (Thomisus) = blandus (Thomisus)	13
anthobioides (Thomisus) = dalmasi (Thomisus)	33	malevolus ocellitibiis (Thomisus) = blandus (Thomisus)	13
anthobioides mongbwalensis = dalmasi (Thomisus)	33	maronica (Misumena)	65
anthobius (Thomisus) = blandus (Thomisus)	13	milloti (Thomisus) = albertianus (Thomisus)	61
anthobius alboirroratus (Thomisus) = blandus (Thomisus)	13	Misumena	53
Aphantochilinae	7	Misumena-group of genera	8
arabicus (Thomisus)	61	Misumeninae	7
australis (Thomisus)	30	Misumenops	48
B		mossambicus (Thomisus) = australis (Thomisus)	30
benoiti (Thomisus)	61	mossambicus weidneri (Thomisus) = australis (Thomisus)	30
bidentatus (Thomisus)	61	multilineata (Runcinia)	64
blandus (Thomisus)	13	N	
boesenbergi (Thomisus)	61	nana (Misumenops)	65
bonnieri (Thomisus)	61	natalensis (Misumena)	56
bueanus (Thomisus)	61	natalensis (Thomisus)	19
C		O	
caffer (Thomisus) = scrupeus (Thomisus)	17	obscuratus (Thomisus)	63
candidus (Thomisus)	62	obtusulosis (Thomisus)	63
carae (Runcinia)	41	oculifrons (Runcinia)	64
cataracta (Runcinia) = affinis (Runcinia)	45	onustus (Thomisus)	63
citrinellus (Thomisus)	22	P	
congoensis (Thomisus)	35	pallescens (Misumena)	65
D		Philodrominae	7
dalmasi (Thomisus)	33	proxima (Runcinia) = flavida (Runcinia)	39
dalmasoides (Thomisus) = dalmasi (Thomisus)	33	proxima voltaensis (Runcinia) = flavida (Runcinia)	39
daradioides (Thomisus)	25	Q	
dartevellei (Thomisus)	62	quadrituberculatus (Thomisus) = scrupeus (Thomisus)	17
decolor (Misumenops)	65	R	
depressa (Runcinia)	43	roeweri (Thomisus)	63
destefanii (Thomisus)	62	rubrodecorata (Misumenops)	51
dottrensi (Thomisus) = spiculosus (Thomisus)	11	Runcinia	36
drakensbergensis (Thomisus) = australis (Thomisus)	30	S	
dubia (Runcinia)	64	schoutedeni (Thomisus)	63
E		schultzei (Thomisus)	21
erythrina (Runcinia)	64	scrupeus (Thomisus)	17
F		sepius (Thomisus) = daradioides (Thomisus)	25
flavida (Runcinia)	39	sjoestedti (Runcinia) = johnstoni (Runcinia)	40
G		spiculosus (Thomisus)	11
gabonensis (Thomisus) = albertianus (Thomisus)	61	spinifer (Thomisus) = citrinellus (Thomisus)	22
granulatus (Thomisus)	15	spinifer decorata (Thomisus) = citrinellus (Thomisus)	22
H		spinifer maculitibiis (Thomisus) = citrinellus (Thomisus)	22
hararinus (Thomisus)	62	spinifer obscurus (Thomisus) = citrinellus (Thomisus)	22
hottentotus (Thomisus)	36	spinifer simoni (Thomisus) = citrinellus (Thomisus)	22
hilarulus (Thomisus)	62	spinulosissima (Misumenops)	65
hystrix (Thomisus) = granulatus (Thomisus)	15	steningi (Thomisus)	28
J		Stephanopsinae	7
janinae (Thomisus)	62	Stiphropodinae	7
johnstoni (Runcinia)	40	Strophinae	7
K		sus (Thomisus) = blandus (Thomisus)	13
kalaharinus (Thomisus) = urbensis (Thomisus)	27	T	
kiwuensis (Thomisus)	62	Thomisidae	7
L		Thomisus	8
lamperti (Thomisus)	63	tripunctatus (Thomisus)	63
lateralis (Runcinia)	48	tropica (Runcinia)	44
lawrencei (Thomisus) = granulatus (Thomisus)	15	tuckeri (Misumena)	55
		U	
		urbensis (Thomisus)	27
		W	
		weberi (Thomisus) = steningi (Thomisus)	28
		Z	
		zuluanus (Thomisus)	20